

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

COWORKING MODELS

[SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 12

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1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, increasing globalization and technological advancements have substantially altered the ways we work, digitizing contemporary society and making the world of work more individual. Highly specialized workers tend to be location-independent and work on a flexible basis, frequently changing their workplace, with a growing sense of personal control over their professional commitments.

In the return to a "new normality" after the COVID-19 pandemic, many workers faced the limitations of remote work: alienation, isolation, and deterioration of social life, blurring of the boundaries between private and professional life, and lack of access to office facilities (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020). Reluctance to return to the office was often reported (OECD, 2021), along with a trend for home-workers toward hybrid schemes with multiple work locations (Reuschke et al., 2021). It is in this scenario that new types of work spaces have emerged.

Coworking spaces (CWSs) embody a new concept of work spaces, and their spread reflects a growing demand for flexible and professionally equipped work spaces in the context of the expanding knowledge and sharing economy (Huang et al., 2020). They can be considered a "third place," distinct from the home as a workplace (the "first place") and the corporate office (the "second place") (Bouncken & Reuschel, 2018; Oldenburg, 1999), offering an alternative to working from home or long-distance commuting. In reality, *"coworking is more than just a third space. It unites a whole range of business concepts and a special culture aimed at meeting the needs of flexible, agile, self-responsible, and creative professionals"* (Krause, 2019, p. 57). These spaces differ from traditional offices because they provide economically convenient and service-rich shared workspaces, fostering mutual support among freelancers and self-employed professionals (Zhang, Liang & Yin, 2025).

Coworking *"challenges classic organisation approaches and raises human, social, managerial and organisational issues that are particularly salient to management sciences, as well as to society as a whole"* (Leclercq-Vandelannoitte & Isaac, 2016, p. 3). Recent literature places CWSs within the broader category of "new working spaces" (Mariotti et al., 2024), which emerged with (but not only with) digitalization. As such, coworking spaces share some characteristics with Fab labs, Maker-spaces, Hackerspaces, Living labs, Innovation hubs, and other non-traditional work spaces (Micek, Baycan & Lange, 2024; Tomaz & Aboutaleb Tabrizi, 2024). While remaining essentially concentrated in metropolitan areas, where financial, political, and corporate networks intersect, CWSs are present on all continents, in smaller cities, and, increasingly, in rural areas. In terms of intra-urban location, CWSs tend to establish themselves in creative districts and business districts. Most of these spaces are privately owned, although alternative forms of ownership exist (Fast & Jansson, 2024). Coworking spaces generally adopt a profit-making business model (e.g., coworking hotels, incubators, and shared studios), but can also operate as non-profit spaces (e.g., public offices, third places, and collaboration hubs). They differ in design characteristics, offerings, membership levels, and sponsorship. In some cases, they overlap with other innovative types of workspaces, such as incubators and accelerators.

The first coworking space opened in San Francisco, USA, in 2005, and many CWSs still maintain the basic shared office model used by independent workers who rent desks (Blagoev, Costas & Kärreman, 2019). Many of the early CWSs were established by “*small, self-organized groups of independent workers*” to “*pool economic resources to reduce the cost of rent and to counter isolation*” (de Peuter et al., 2017, p. 700). After the pandemic, the number of coworking spaces grew very rapidly, attracting the interest of large multinational corporations that progressively began to dominate the scene, developing a business model in which they act as “*market intermediaries, enabling workers to connect with others and [to] develop professional relationships in an office-like environment*” (Gandini & Cossu, 2019, p. 4). CWSs are also increasingly being used by multinational corporations whose workforce leverages the opportunities of hot-desking and remote work (Aroles, Mitev & de Vaujany, 2019). Within these work environments, coworkers are expected to participate in community life, sharing ideas and knowledge with other members and collaborating.

The number of coworking spaces has increased exponentially in recent years. According to the Global Coworking Survey, the number of CWSs globally rose from 160 in 2008 to around 22,000 in 2019 (Deskmag, 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the spread of remote work worldwide, further stimulating the presence of CWSs in peripheral and rural areas (Tomaz, Moriset & Teller, 2022). In 2025, the coworking industry is experiencing significant growth, with global market value projected to reach \$25.11 billion. CWSs are expanding, with over 40,000 spaces globally, serving an estimated 5 million members, according to HuntOffices. Occupancy rates are also on the rise, averaging 68% worldwide, and even higher in major cities. The highest concentration is found in the United States, the United Kingdom, and India (Johns et al., 2024). The proliferation of CWSs reflects a trend in knowledge work towards flexible and project-based assignments (Nakano et al., 2020), and demonstrates cost-mitigation strategies for companies and entrepreneurs facing economic downturns (Mariotti, Akhavan & Rossi, 2023).

CWSs, considered hybrid workspaces, are perceived not only as optimal work environments but also as a source of social support for freelancers and as a physical context capable of promoting the creation of collaborative communities. These spaces facilitate interactions both through predetermined mechanisms of formal mediation and through fortuitous encounters with individuals outside one's own social circle. By co-building a sense of community, these environments have reshuffled flexible work practices with a significant impact on the lives of flexible workers worldwide (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020). CWSs often offer a wide range of services, such as regularly organized events and workshops, coaching, mentoring, or administrative task management for their members. Coworking is characterized by a lack of direct monitoring of goals or task management by other employees or supervisors, promoting personal autonomy, mutual trust, and the reduction or absence of organizational hierarchies (Bouncken et al., 2020; Bouncken & Reuschl, 2018).

Rather than being simply places where self-employed digital nomads connect through atomized forms of work, CWSs often also provide services to teams of employees from organizations (Johns et al., 2024). Globally recognized companies like Uber and Spotify, for example, were originally conceived as start-ups within CWSs, highlighting the potential of coworking to

function as venues for the development of disruptive innovations capable of revolutionizing product and technology markets.

Several business models have been developed for CWSs, aimed at solving a series of problems, including:

- The need for the start-up community to pool resources and interconnect actors within a professional network context;
- The shortage of affordable offices and workspaces for the creative community in overcrowded cities;
- The forces to build socioeconomic development projects in structurally weak regions through the provision of spaces for joint activities.

Considering the perspective of coworking users, these spaces seek to meet the following needs: they respond to the needs of workers isolated in their home offices, integrating them into a professional community and local networks; they solve the problem of daily or weekly commutes to the workplace, thus overcoming the need for an alternative workplace and providing the opportunity to create work communities in employees' places of residence (Krause, 2019). In addition to reinventing the workspace, the culture of coworking is also changing the nature of daily work through interdisciplinary cooperation and the formation of local organizational structures, as well as the development of life and work skills in a heterogeneous and complex environment.

As part of the digital economy and a witness to changes in traditional work practices and locations, CWSs have been studied in the fields of economics, management, and labor sociology. A small but growing number of studies has begun to use a geographical approach, examining factors related to the location of CWSs and their implications for public policy (Ananian et al., 2024).

2. The Phenomenon of Coworking

2.1. Definition

The hybrid and ever-evolving nature of coworking is reflected in the diversity of definitions present in the literature. While "coworking space" constitutes a notion that is in some ways elastic (e.g., Orel & Bennis, 2021; Mariotti et al., 2024), it is common to describe this type of environment as: *"a digital connected workspace where freelancers and other 'flexible' knowledge workers can access a 'hot desk' and other work facilities for a limited period"* (Fast & Jansson, 2024, p. 1).

Johns et al. (2024) define CWSs *"as nonhome, nonconventional office sites where individuals, teams, or even entire organisations engage in work, with the aim of benefitting from synergistic encounters with a community of other coworkers"* (p. 1). As such, these spaces can be conceptualized as *"a sharing economy in two dimensions providing the access to shared physical asset (office, infrastructure, cafeteria etc.)"* (Bouncken & Reuschl, 2018, p. 322).

For Ananian et al. (2024) CWSs *"are shared physical workspaces that offer amenities (kitchen, fully equipped meeting rooms, lounges), flexible occupancy, and that are structured around a community of members. Some offer a wide range of services (mentoring, events, and training) and others also offer virtual spaces and platforms. Some CSs are global organizations, such as WeWork, Impact Hub and Green Desk, whereas others are local"* (p. 1).

Howell (2022) defines them as subscription-based workspaces in which individuals and groups belonging to different companies work in a shared common space. The coworking business model is essentially a rental arbitrage, that is, the practice of short-term renting of a long-term asset: coworking companies rent buildings from owners with long-term, multi-year contracts, transform the spaces by adding common areas, cafeterias, and other facilities functional to community life, then rent the space in a more fragmented way to tenants at significantly higher prices and on much more flexible terms (e.g., month-to-month). Tenants are generally entrepreneurs, freelancers, remote workers, and other independent and non-traditional workers who could not afford their own office.

Often the emphasis is placed on the fundamental value of collaboration, although this can sometimes be a superficial aspect. *"Beyond just creating better places to work, coworking spaces are built around the idea of community-building and sustainability. Coworking spaces uphold the values set forth by those who developed the concept in the first place: collaboration, community, sustainability, openness, and accessibility"* (Coworking.com, 2023). It is the sense of community, the vibe, and the social capital formation generated by coworking that releases the greatest benefits of membership. These include intangible benefits such as a reduced risk of social isolation compared to working from home and improved mental well-being (Merrell et al., 2021).

Some companies have placed their employees within coworking spaces to scout for new ideas or to test them, across a diverse range of sectors and/or supplementary initiatives or operations in a new regional market (Heinzel, Georgiades & Engstler, 2021).

CWSs facilitate the possibility of working close to home, overcoming the disadvantages of working from home, including social isolation, poor mental health, lack of access to professional services and supplies such as printers, scanners, and photocopiers, which are some of the benefits of working in a traditional office, while also overcoming the disadvantages of working at the company office, including a long commute, poor work-life balance, and sustainability issues related to travel (Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto, 2024).

“There is a variety of CWS configurations (and offerings to coworkers), but typically each offers desks, a kitchenette and wi-fi, and – depending on the CWS – the use of computer monitors, printers, mailbox services and private meeting spaces. Some CWSs may even provide a 'communal' lounge/relaxation area (with soft furnishings and/or 'funky' furniture) and games room” (Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto, 2024, pp. 2-3). For coworkers, these spaces offer a low-cost and flexible option to access a variety of shared services and equipment, without significant real estate expenses and associated costs, with the possibility of reaching the coworking space in a short time and becoming part of a community. Indeed, the essence of coworking is the emphasis on building a community of coworkers.

“The broader CWS genre also includes makerspaces, fabrication laboratories (fablabs) and hackerspaces, which are kitted out with a range of equipment from lathes, computer-aided design (CAD) software to 3D printing and augmented/virtual reality (AR/VR) devices, to allow users to design, experiment and produce physical prototypes and/or virtual goods” (Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto, 2024, p. 3). Coworking spaces differ substantially from accelerators, incubators, and maker spaces (Howell, 2022). Accelerators and incubators typically have a centralized organizational hierarchy, are structured in terms of programming or length of stay (3-6 months in the first case, 6-12 months in the second), and have formalized entry procedures, where startups are selected based on their development potential. Coworking spaces do not have these selection criteria: anyone who can pay the rent can occupy the space, consequently they host a wide variety of users. They also differ in the number of facilities, required payments, and resources provided. CWSs also differ from maker spaces, which are generally frequented by inventors, hobbyists, or thinkers, and which can be free for certain classes (e.g., university students). The space offers a wide variety of hardware and software tools that members can use freely. CWSs have little or no programming, so the sense of community that prevails within the space is created by bottom-up rather than top-down dynamics. These dynamics make organizational boundaries more blurred and fluid, and entrepreneurs can identify not only as members of their own entrepreneurial initiatives, but also as members of the coworking space and the community within which they are embedded. All of this has implications for theories related to interdisciplinary collaborations, knowledge sharing and spillover, and labor mobility (Ibidem).

The concept of coworking was mainly a Euro-American invention that gradually spread to other parts of the world (Gandini, 2015). Since the coworking industry is relatively new, it has not yet gone through a full business cycle (Howell, 2022). Considering the different geographical, economic, and socio-cultural conditions, the spatial development of coworking in emerging economies may not follow the same patterns as their counterparts in economically advanced countries.

2.2. Changes in the Organizational Model of Work

Starting from the 1990s, the organization of work has included the emergence of digital forms of employment, fitting into the evolution of work that occurred during the twentieth century and the beginning of the twenty-first, which can be divided into 3 periods: postwar industrialization, the era of automation and digitalization, and the rise of the virtual economy. Each of these periods corresponds to a certain production model: Fordism, Toyotism, and Uberism (or Waymoism), with specific work organization models and the demand for different skill sets.

With the advent of the third industrial revolution in the late 1980s, a change occurred driven by four technological innovations: the rise of electronically controlled systems; the miniaturization of electronic components; the digitalization of information; and the development of user-friendly software. The virtual revolution, which began with the mass use of smartphone technology in the late 2010s, provides constant access to a virtual environment. This allows for the development of business models that don't require the purchase of expensive and technically complex goods or services, thanks to the concept of *shared use*. Such an approach can revolutionize the basic value chain because it blurs the lines between the roles of producers, consumers, mediators, and users. Virtual space opens up an area where time and space are no longer fixed coordinates for cooperative action. This aspect helps in understanding the logic of virtual value chains.

Thanks to automation and digitalization, manual labor is being progressively replaced by knowledge work, leading to a growing demand for professional skills. At the same time, this process has accentuated the polarization between those who perform manual labor and those engaged in intellectual activities. Over the past decade, the virtualization of the work environment has caused many professionals to lose their direct connection to a physical company or workplace.

Krause (2019) analyzed the concept of coworking as a cultural foundation of virtual work. In the near future, digitalization—automation, informatization, and transformation—will modify the types of work and the workload of people globally. In the view of Generation Z, the word "work" appears connected to a way of life that "digital natives" reject, embodying a social order that clearly differentiates work from free time and where the workplace is distinctly separate from private spaces. This includes a paradigm in which "working" means acting according to hierarchies in a rational and goal-oriented way, while the private and family environment is a space where one can act in a more emotional and cooperative way. *"Coworking can be considered the matrix of a production mentality in an individualized virtual society, which serves to integrate separate (often geographically isolated) creative individuals in a working community and is quite different from the traditional forms of work organization"* (Krause, 2019, p. 57).

2.3. Origins and Developments

Around the mid-2000s, research on work in the urban knowledge and creative economy focused on the critique of the spread of precarity and the contextual affirmation of a neoliberal entrepreneurial work culture, as reflected in the ethos and practices of 'being creative'. CWSs

emerged at the exact same moment as a response to the growing fragmentation and individualization of work practices within the creative economy (Gandini & Cossu, 2019). In its initial phase, the coworking phenomenon represented a grassroots movement that promoted a communal model of shared workspace that would meet the practical and emotional needs of freelancers, offering them the opportunity to socialize and work from a place other than the home environment (Spinuzzi, 2012).

In August 2005, programmer and entrepreneur Brad Neuberg was struggling with social isolation after launching a new venture from his home studio. In a 2018 interview, Neuberg explained that, as a software developer, he craved *“the community and structure of a job, but the freedom and independence of working for myself”*. Determined to experiment with a new form of workspace, he rented an available room within the feminist collective The Spiral Muse in San Francisco, USA, which he furnished with simple desks and chairs (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020). He then began advertising the San Francisco Coworking Space, using the term "coworking" for the first time to describe the condition of unaffiliated professionals working together within a shared workspace to build community and support one another. Other people followed his lead, opening their own coworking spaces in various cities across the United States.

It was the movement of people that made coworking popular as a model for flexible use of a workspace (Putra & Agirachman, 2016). In early 2006, two self-employed, U.S. roommates in New York organized the first meeting of independent workers, calling it a Jelly event. The goal was to open the doors of their apartment to acquaintances and strangers who, due to the independent nature of their work from home, were subject to isolation and alienation. That same year, Solos Working Alone Together (SWAT) began organizing similar events in Chicago with the aim of connecting people once or twice a week in one of the previously selected cafés (Jones et al., 2009). Both events were based on the principle of sharing economies, which in turn are based on the sharing of human and material resources among people (Tæihagh, 2017). Through their online promotion, these collaborative collective meetings attracted individual stakeholders and quickly expanded from cities in the U.S. to Europe and then to other continents (De Guzman & Tang, 2011).

The following points were recognized as necessary for organizing Jelly-like events, which were widely adopted among individuals and organizations that hosted meetings in open-space environments (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020):

- a) Free internet access;
- b) A free, central, and easily accessible location for meetings;
- c) A space with one or more small tables that could be used as a work area;
- d) A sufficient number of electrical outlets;
- e) Access to food (hot and cold beverages) or the possibility of bringing one's own food and drinks.

Jelly-style events can be considered indicators of several social changes related to the transformation of knowledge work and the rise of flexible work. All of this highlighted the need to create permanent situations, the interest in valuing self-employed workers and smaller work teams, and the development of a form of digital and creative tourism that would allow self-

employed workers to facilitate the transition (and work) between different existing collaborative spaces (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020). The organization of these events, which were free and therefore accessible to a large number of people, was essential for subsequent developments and for the articulation of the coworking model. Furthermore, scheduled visits to collaborative spaces were a sign of the need to permanently establish collaborative workspaces (Salovaara, 2015). This aspect represents a predisposition and a starting point for the subsequent developments of a shared workspace through a bottom-up approach (Rus & Orel, 2015). Moreover, Jelly-style events served as a real-time promotional platform for individuals or groups. In the first years of their diffusion, Jelly-style events can be understood as a movement towards the creation of heterogeneous communities based on the principles of cooperation and the sharing of premises. These collaborative environments were defined as *individual accommodation units* or as a dwelling whose tenants can be seen as a smaller community of interconnected people who, occasionally and in exchange for a small fee or other forms of compensation, share the workspace (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020). In parallel with these events and temporary workspaces, the first coworking model grew mainly on the basis of the common interests of people who strived for the creation of collaboration-based workspaces. The first permanent coworking spaces and their temporary counterparts in the form of Jelly events emphasized the aspect of solidarity before the monetization of similar and related services.

From a historical perspective, the idea of coworking, which has gained great popularity in Western Europe, constitutes a modern-day revival of the 19th-century Viennese coffee house culture.

The first coworking model was created by the participation of independently operating individuals based on the principles of the *sharing economy* (Hamari, Sjöklint & Ukkonen, 2016). In particular, these collaborative spaces differed from the beginning from similar spatial structures, fundamentally due to their informal and reciprocal organizational culture and their emphasis on cooperative practices similar to those of cooperatives. Based on this, the period between 2005 and 2010 can be identified as the genesis of coworking spaces, followed by a period of diffusion between 2010 and 2014, and the further hybridization of the model that began in 2014 and is still ongoing.

The first phase of the coworking model's development was characterized by a high level of user solidarity within cooperative communities, which was primarily visible in the mutual assistance and reciprocity among members and in the early micro-financing of coworking spaces (Spinuzzi, 2015). When the idea of coworking began to be considered, the coworking movement became more structured and cohesive. The development of the coworking model has been marked by several milestones, including the start of the Global Coworking Unconference Conferences (GCUC) in 2009 to network and exchange ideas, and the organization of the first Coworking Day in 2010. The reopening of the New York City coworking space in 2010, funded by its users through a crowdfunding campaign, was also a significant event. As the concept of coworking became more widespread, large companies like Microsoft and IBM began experimenting with these spaces by sending groups of their employees, hoping to improve job satisfaction and create networking opportunities with people outside their domain (Spreitzer, Garrett & Bacevice, 2015b). Noticing these trends, along with the great shift from traditional

to non-traditional work, investors began to invest capital in these new spaces, contributing to the global spread of CWSs. Forms of pre-financing and the integration of hegemonic structures introduce the particular interests of stakeholders into coworking spaces, directly influencing not only the establishment of the physical space—thus circumventing the co-creation process—but also the establishment of defined acceptance norms (e.g., who can use a single space or a preference for target groups), values (monetization of services before the concept of sharing), and the culture itself.

Coworking spaces aren't just found in strategic entrepreneurial hubs (e.g., Silicon Valley, New York, Boston, or Los Angeles), but also in all other American states and in most metropolitan areas, making coworking an international phenomenon (Howell, 2022).

The period of diffusion for the coworking model between 2010 and 2014 was characterized by a rapid growth in the number of new coworking spaces created and a corresponding increase in users. Several key factors are associated with the growth of this trend: a) rapid technological development and the consequent digitalization of work; b) changes in the occupational structures of organizations; c) the fluidity of work and the fluctuation of generally smaller teams.

The exponential growth in the number of coworking spaces has led to a new trend in the model's development, which has become appealing for corporate use (Sargent et al., 2018). An illustrative example is the case of TechHub, a coworking space opened in 2011 within the Google Campus in London, UK. Members of this franchise can move freely between its various locations. A similar example is the U.S. company WeWork, launched in 2010. In early May 2019, CNN published an article describing how WeWork had transformed into the world's largest physical network for users of flexible office spaces (O'Brien, 2019). In this case too, members are encouraged to travel between its coworking spaces (Leclercq-Vandelannoitte & Isaac, 2016). Through motivational phrases like "Thank God it's Monday," the construction of co-living apartments, and the development of educational facilities, WeWork has transformed from a community-oriented office provider into a global trendsetter of social change. It's an indicator of a growing demand for all-inclusive ecosystems that have effects not only on how people work, but also on how they live their lives. In both cases, the concept of digital tourism is promoted to attract digital nomads or traveling knowledge workers who accelerate the flow of knowledge as they move between different locations.

The strong expansion of the coworking model in recent years has created a certain distance from the heterogeneity of its members, which was typical of the initial phase, with a growing specialization of spaces to cater to potential clients who require a specific and defined work environment (Marchegiani & Arcese, 2018). For example, there are coworking spaces specialized in the culinary arts sector (Raphael, 2017), for musicians (Di Risio, 2018), and for working parents (van Blokland, 2018). Furthermore, generic coworking spaces are expanding their range of services to be more competitive and to position themselves in local markets. In addition to office spaces with fixed and flexible desks, they commonly offer cafes, childcare, recreational areas, and living units (e.g., Halvitigala, Antoniadou & Eves, 2018). This points toward an intensified hybridization of the model, as coworking spaces strive to recreate an environment that can be described as a *fourth living place* in addition to being a collaborative

workspace (Morisson, 2018). According to Orel & Dvouletý (2020), hybridized coworking spaces will increasingly focus on localizing all operational and desired services in a single place to fully cover the living, working, and social segments of human existence.

Gandini and Cossu (2019), outlining the evolution of coworking (Table 1), have characterized the consolidation and expansion of coworking spaces as a 'mainstream neo-corporate' phase that began to accelerate following the 2007-2008 Global Financial Crisis and has continued beyond the COVID-19 pandemic (Yates et al., 2024). *“Coworking spaces have been affirmed in recent years as a mainstream, 'neo-corporate' model of flexible work in post-recession, urban knowledge economies”* (Gandini & Cossu, 2019, p. 430). The two scholars illustrate the emergence of coworking initiatives that oppose the neo-corporate model, describing it as 'resilient.' [...] *“resilient coworking spaces are organisational actors that interact with the surrounding context much more than their counterparts, blending entrepreneurial logics with forms of political and social activism”* (Ibidem). Their emergence could be the harbinger of a new phase in the evolution of the coworking phenomenon and as an alternative to the neo-corporate model (Merkel, 2019). Some of these spaces have also appeared outside of the usual contexts of large metropolitan areas, in peripheral or disadvantaged areas, or in emerging economies. Resilient would be those shared workspaces that do not oppose the evolution of work toward flexibility and independence but position themselves against the entrepreneurial ideology of 'collaborative individualism' (Bandinelli & Gandini, 2019) that characterizes the neo-corporate coworking model. This alternative model integrates with the context in which it operates to a much greater extent than the neo-corporate model, blending entrepreneurial logics with forms of political and social activism. All of this should be seen as a counter-movement to the trend of neo-corporate coworking practices, aspiring to reassert the original ethos of community-based, sharing-focused workspaces that characterized the avant-garde phase.

<i>Phase</i>	<i>Value logic</i>	<i>Imaginery</i>	<i>Subjects in context</i>
Avant-garde phase	Social value is prioritised regardless of space sustainability	Crafting pre-existing work cultures into new meanings and practices	Communitarian relations to answer pressing needs of knowledge and creative workers
Mainstream, “neo-corporate” phase	Economic value is prioritised and discursively framed as innovation-driven	New set of meanings and practices consolidate into a coherent neoliberal model	Centralised, urban-based and top-down logics of space-sharing among workers with economic barriers to access (e.g. membership fee)
“Resilient” phase	Seeking economy sustainability and social impact	Political attempt to destabilise the hegemonic “neo-corporate” model of coworking and reaffirm its grassroots origins	Refusal of the top-down logic, attempt to recalibrate practices within and around new spaces and territories

Fonte: Gandini & Cossu (2019).

Table 1 – The evolution of coworking

2.4. Future Perspectives

As already noted during the COVID-19 pandemic, opportunities for future transformations of coworking spaces are highlighted by early signs of an emerging trend of hotels, hospitality, and commercial spaces adapting their structures to accommodate coworking and other types of flexible workspaces in the wake of the pandemic (Grazian, 2020). There are indications that coworking spaces may continue to expand and change as remote work becomes more feasible, acceptable, and even preferable for both employers and employees, and as larger organizations and firms seek to decentralize their workforce into smaller branches and remote teams in flexible offices. These changes pose new challenges for managers increasingly called upon to coordinate distributed workforces. Human resource managers, in particular, face specific challenges related to performance management, maintaining morale, and a sense of attachment to the employer in relation to physical distance from central headquarters (Donnelly & Johns, 2020).

As evidenced by the review from Johns and colleagues (2024), there are many different types of coworking spaces, with various—and sometimes opposing—goals and business models. Currently, the business model of corporate coworking spaces has grown, but it is not yet predominant, meaning that alternative business models and substantial variations can still exist.

Small, independent coworking spaces operate in competitive markets by attracting a specific group of individual users, for example, freelancers working in a particular sector, and they strive to maintain at least some of the sense of community that was a hallmark of early coworking.

In a context of relative openness and competition in the coworking space market, the existence of competitive pressures will stimulate innovation, facilitating interaction with local contexts. The lack of a predominant business model will mean a continued need to seek out new users by customizing the offering to the specificities of the context.

Two competing trends could potentially shape the future development of coworking markets: homogenization and disembeddedness or differentiation and embeddedness of CWSs (Johns et al., 2024).

The rise of large-scale coworking space operators, managing multiple locations, is leading to a greater prevalence of a homogenized form of coworking. As the market progressively matures, further homogenization is likely to occur, converging toward a single business model.

A standardized coworking scenario would primarily be based on attracting corporate clients as the main source of revenue, thereby reducing the focus on freelancers. This scenario is consistent with the concept of "corpworking" as analyzed in the relevant literature (Mayerhoffer, 2020). The original ethos of coworking—to bring diverse people together in the same work environment to facilitate serendipitous encounters—would be further undermined by the increasing demand from companies for more privacy and exclusive spaces for their employees.

This homogenization would lead to a situation where coworking spaces become disembedded from their broader urban ecosystems, limiting opportunities for them to absorb from and be influenced by local realities. This uprooting is driven by the same processes that have reproduced the homogenization evident in most urban areas, characterized by the proliferation of identical chain stores (Hughes & Jackson, 2015), leading to a particular business model that dominates and replaces any form of competition.

For users, homogenization would likely result in a larger number of coworking spaces but a reduction in the diversity of space types. Highly localized, community-driven coworking spaces would take a backseat to highly professionalized coworking spaces with more predictable business models and lower management costs. Workers would experience less flexibility in terms of membership and conditions. This would have a greater impact on freelancers and independent workers compared to company employees working remotely or in a hybrid model (Johns et al., 2024).

If, instead, the trend toward differentiation and embeddedness of CWSs were to prevail, the coworking sector could fragment into a plethora of diverse business models and organizational forms, from large corporate coworking spaces to small, independent ones, with no single type dominating. This would lead to a high level of competition among spaces. There would also be a deep level of local embeddedness, as the forms taken by these spaces would be shaped by the needs, demands, and competitive pressures of their local contexts. High competition could also be linked to high levels of innovation. Human Resources (HR) departments would face significant pressure due to the increased complexity and variety of operational scenarios. They would need to adapt to different business models, which could become a barrier to growth. This situation might lead to a decrease in the stability and sustainability

of coworking spaces. Consequently, opportunities for both employers and employees would be undermined, as they would see reduced flexibility and access to a dynamic and diverse labor market (*Ibidem*).

2.5. A Critical Look

Over the last decade, the growing demand for flexibility, largely driven by the adoption of remote and hybrid work models, has led to a significant increase in academic interest in the coworking phenomenon. This field of study has now matured into a central theme in the discourse on the future of work spaces. Initially met with enthusiasm for its perceived communal nature, the academic debate on coworking has since adopted a more critical perspective, highlighting its contradictory nature. Empirical research has shown that the choice to work in a coworking space is often driven by instrumental motivations. These include the desire to alleviate the social isolation associated with working from home and the strategic need to build professional networks to foster collaborations. Contrary to popular belief, data suggests that spontaneous collaboration among coworkers is less frequent than commonly assumed. Coworking practices seem to consist more of "working alone together," where physical proximity does not necessarily translate into meaningful interaction or collaboration. In this context, the coworking model has evolved into what many scholars define as a "neo-corporate" form, deeply aligned with the ethos of the tech sector. This phenomenon was described by McWilliams (2015) as the "flat white economy" (Gandini & Cossu, 2019), a term that captures the fusion of a seemingly informal lifestyle and work culture with corporate economic and organizational logic.

Other research has highlighted how CWSs are inherently contradictory environments. On one hand, they are designed to be comfortable and welcoming, similar to a domestic setting, which encourages intense and continuous work. On the other, they are presented as sought-after and aesthetically curated destinations. This dual nature meets the needs of professionals who seek not only a work-life balance but also the opportunity for a partial disconnection.

Following a systematic literature review of the literature on coworking and coworking spaces, Johns et al. (2024) outlined the main research themes and identified three primary weaknesses in our general understanding of three key conceptual areas: *community*, *context*, and *change*.

The existing literature on coworking often presents a simplistic and uncritical view of the concept of community. Much of the research tends to portray coworking spaces as environments where collaboration emerges spontaneously or by chance, overlooking the complex dynamics that govern these interactions. This mainstream perspective underestimates both the processes of facilitation in building relationships among members and the role of spatial and organizational structures that can either foster or hinder inclusion. Furthermore, conceptualizing users as exclusively independent and entrepreneurial actors fails to fully grasp the reality of contemporary work. This view ignores the growing precarity, flexibility, and "platformization" (Richardson, 2021) that characterize much of the activity taking place within coworking spaces. Only a more critical line of research has focused on the crucial role of care and facili-

tation practices in fostering affinities among members, offering a deeper, less idealized understanding of the nature of coworking communities. From an academic perspective, further research is crucial to understanding the managerial nature of care and facilitation within coworking spaces. This inquiry should focus on the specific work processes through which these elements are delivered—a perspective that challenges the idealized view of coworking as a "third place" of creativity and autonomy. By adopting a more critical lens, these spaces are revealed as managed work environments, not unlike other corporate settings. In this sense, research could show how the value generated from collective productivity is not shared equally, but rather is "*appropriated and captured from the commons of collective productivity*" (Johns et al., 2024, p. 5). This view directly questions the common narrative of a liberating and autonomous collaborative space.

Current evidence suggests that coworking spaces tend to replicate existing socio-economic inequalities rather than subverting them. Consequently, they can be seen as places of exclusion rather than inclusion, debunking the narrative that portrays them as a progressive or egalitarian form of work opposed to traditional capitalism. The "community" that forms within these environments is, in most cases, defined by specific professional categories and exclusive identities (such as those in the creative, digital, or entrepreneurial sectors), confirming their role in reproducing pre-existing social structures. Research indicates that coworking spaces providing the best "user experience" are those that invest in targeted community care. However, it is precisely the exclusivity of these communities that fosters internal collaboration while simultaneously limiting diversity and inclusion.

According to de Peuter et al. (2017), the term community largely functions as an empty signifier in the coworking discourse. While it's a word widely used and repeated by managers and workers in interviews, it lacks a singular and substantial meaning. The authors argue that community and territoriality are two sides of the same coin: the supposed inclusivity of coworking conceals a reality of exclusion, where access is granted only to specific individuals while others are kept out. Despite its nature as an empty signifier, the concept of "community" is essential for defining and legitimizing coworking spaces as a post-work territory.

In terms of context, the extensive literature has not adequately accounted for the increasingly close link between coworking spaces and real estate dynamics, particularly the coworking business model as a profit-oriented enterprise. It is crucial for analysis to focus more on the specific context in which these spaces emerge. Their creation is often a product of urban real estate market dynamics, rather than a direct response to the need for collaborative work environments that foster professional networking. The revenue generated from office rentals is, in fact, one of the primary motivations for dedicating spaces to coworking (Saiz, 2020). Research often tends to study coworking spaces as isolated, self-contained entities, focusing exclusively on their internal dynamics. While this approach can deepen our understanding of work practices, it risks neglecting the broader context in which they operate. It is crucial, instead, to analyze coworking spaces as an integral part of the local markets where they compete. Their diverse business strategies reflect the influence of changes at various geographic scales, such as the growing fragmentation of work (across home, office, and third spaces). Therefore, future research should situate coworking spaces within their local, national, and international socio-political-economic contexts (Johns et al., 2024). Only by doing so will it be

possible to understand how different types of spaces attract specific segments of workers, freelancers, small businesses, and community groups, providing a more complete and less isolated view of the phenomenon.

The existing literature on coworking struggles to fully grasp the dynamics of change that shape its evolution, often remaining trapped in a dichotomy between two main approaches. Initially, research focused on the demand for these spaces by freelancers and self-employed individuals in the creative and digital sectors. These professionals were seen as motivated by the desire to maintain their autonomy while seeking a collective and collaborative work experience. More recent studies, in contrast, highlight an evolution in demand, shifting toward entrepreneurs and professionals in high-tech and innovation sectors. Their primary motivation is not solidarity, but the instrumental pursuit of resources, investments, networking opportunities, and collaborations. Regardless of the abundance of empirical studies on social and networking dynamics, the research often neglects the organizational dimension and the broader socio-economic and spatial context. There is a lack of analysis on changes in the real estate and labor markets that directly influence the development and differentiation of various coworking business models (Clifton, Füzi & Loudon, 2019). Johns et al. (2024) propose a deeper conceptualization of coworking spaces, viewing them as nested or embedded within various spatial scales where different stakeholders and actors interact. This perspective moves beyond the idea that coworking spaces are simply isolated work locations, allowing for a better understanding of them as dynamic sites within and through which work practices are undergoing significant change. Furthermore, these authors suggest that future research should delve deeper into the tension in coworking spaces between their role as sites of community and openness and their potential exclusionary nature. This tension is connected to larger issues, such as urban processes of gentrification and inequality. As privatized and exclusive urban spaces, coworking environments are supported by security technologies (such as electronic doors and online registrations, mediated by concierges and members) that create an exclusionary effect for those who cannot afford access. At the same time, the apparent "openness" of these spaces can mask the reproduction of dynamics that generate inequality. While coworking spaces can serve as positive environments for entrepreneurship, fostering innovation and knowledge exchange, they also present significant challenges for professionals, including social isolation, potential exploitation, and conflicts. To mitigate these issues, Bouncken, Aslam, and Reuschl (2018) suggest implementing targeted strategies such as mentoring programs, training, promoting pro-social community norms, and conflict resolution mechanisms. It should also be noted that the cultivation of a collaborative community, while often seeking diversity in professions and skills, frequently overlooks crucial aspects like social class, gender, and ethnicity (de Peuter et al., 2017), thereby perpetuating existing inequalities.

The article by Fast and Jansson (2024) contributes a critical perspective on coworking spaces through the general notion of "coworking spaces territoriality". Their starting point is the concept of *post-digital territoriality*, which captures how individuals and organizations seek to counteract the disadvantages of increasing digitalization and reclaim a sense of bounded space. They bring the 'post-digital' concept into conversation with 'post-work' and 'post-tourist'—two other 'post-' concepts that contain ideas and practices characterizing the contradictory nature of coworking spaces. At the intersection of these three facets of territoriality, the

authors discuss how coworking spaces emerge as a spatially and socially bounded comfort zone. This approach is situated within the broader discourse on the ambiguous role of coworking spaces in relation to wider societal transformations, particularly regarding social inclusion and exclusion. Their arguments are grounded in a literature review and empirical data collected from ten coworking spaces in Oslo, Denver, and Palma de Mallorca, using an ethnographic approach. At the core of their analysis is the understanding of coworking spaces as part of a broader post-digital transformation of society. This implies that constant connectivity and digital dependency are both normalized and contested. Framing coworking as post-digital territories allows for the exploration of their potential to act as a counterforce to problematic social phenomena. This perspective highlights how coworking can push back against troubling trends like surveillance capitalism (Zuboff, 2019), data colonialism (Couldry & Mejias, 2019), or, more generally, exploitative and self-harming work conditions.

Coworking spaces present a profound contradiction. On one hand, they are considered one of the most advanced forms of neoliberalism, given the type of workers (freelance, independent) and activities (start-ups, new economy) they attract (de Peuter, Cohen & Saraco, 2017). On the other, their business model is built on the rhetoric of community and self-realization ideals often labeled as "post-capitalist" (Vidaillet & Bousalham, 2020) or "post-work" (Gregg, 2018).

De Peuter et al. (2017) argue that while coworking spaces are promoted as a solution to neoliberal working conditions and job precarity, they actually do so *"in a manner that redoubles network sociality – a mode of conduct that requires one to be active, to take initiative and to seek out contacts."* Fast (2024) defines them as an "elite territory" as much as a space of precarity.

This ambiguity is also reflected in their territoriality. While promoting the idea of more open and inclusive cities, coworking spaces, as aestheticized and "touristified" places, tend to attract an audience with privileged habits and resources (Centner, 2008). Specifically, they attract individuals who possess a high degree of network capital (Urry, 2007), which refers to the skills and resources needed to support high mobility and connectivity, particularly within the digital media sphere.

The critical research stream on coworking argues that professionals who use these spaces are exposed to a new, more sophisticated form of exploitation, in which digital media serves as the tool for control (De Peuter et al., 2017; Gandini, 2015). From this perspective, coworking is seen as an extension of capitalist control. The paradox lies in the fact that workers' constant availability—their *extensibility*—is disguised and resold as flexibility. In this context, surveillance isn't an external imposition but is integrated directly into digital interactions, manifesting as *"the organizational form of surveillance capitalism in the platforms"* (Mazmanian, Orlikowski & Yates, 2013, p. 681).

According to Richardson (2021, p. 349), *"the tendency of contemporary technologies of work is less to divide space according to a specific function, and more to create spaces of coordination that can adjust the definition of purposeful activity."* They define platformization as *"a process of spatial definition of work through technology that does not necessarily fix location"*

but rather creates space (and time) for coordination that arranges different (more or less) territorialized actors and their networks" (p. 359). In post-digital conditions, where connectivity and distributed spatiality have become the norm, coworking spaces—emblematic of platformization—should provide boundaries, spatial anchoring, and, potentially, a refuge from digital over-extension and distraction. Through "disconnective workplace designs", Fast (2021) argues that coworking spaces are "also promoters of work fixity" (p. 1620).

Much business-oriented research tends to view the fundamental arguments of the coworking discourse—namely community, freedom, and autonomy—as mere rhetorical values. From this perspective, the promotion of a "post-work" culture that emphasizes belonging and the meaning of work, in contrast to alienation and exploitation, is seen as a strategic operation rather than an intrinsic value (Fast & Jansson, 2024).

Continuing a critical perspective on the coworking phenomenon, some critiques question the optimism that surrounds the coworking discourse. According to Gandini (2015), little evidence is available to assess whether such practices will lead to improvements in skills and tangible forms of empowerment for urban knowledge workers. For instance, the ideas of openness, serendipity, and collaboration frequently discussed in European and North American contexts hardly align with the freelance work culture of digital workers in the Philippines, who prefer more convenient solutions to coworking or choose to work from home (Zhang, Liang & Yin, 2025).

Lastly, CWSs, innovator houses, and other formats that provide infrastructure and networking opportunities to independent professionals do so without offering the social benefits typical of a traditional employer. This phenomenon represents a further liberalization of the labor market, accelerated by technological progress. This scenario raises a crucial question (Krause, 2019): how can we reintegrate these processes into an institutional structure that successfully combines the advantages of technological advancement with social solidarity, creating a virtual community in a context of intensive work?

3. Types and Users of Coworking Spaces

3.1. Development of the Coworking Model

In 1999, Bernard De Koven, a US-based software developer, was the first to propose the term "coworking." He used it to describe individuals interacting collaboratively, without strictly defined or hierarchically organized relationships (Brown, 2017). While working on computer games and programs with other independent or team-based developers, De Koven became aware of the connection between face-to-face communication and online tools, intuiting the importance of establishing meaningful mutual relationships.

In the following years, the word coworking was used multiple times, but in different contexts, to describe resource sharing among individuals connected within the same organizational network.

"The term 'coworking' refers to the cooperation and the sharing of the workspace between individuals working independently given mutual relationships formed on the basis of either spontaneous or moderated processes within a temporary-set or a permanent collaborative workspace" (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020, p. 15).

From this perspective, the first environment to be characterized and self-proclaimed as a modern coworking space was The Spiral Muse, which opened in August 2005 in San Francisco, an initiative by Brad Neuberg (see paragraph 2.3). In some academic publications, The Hat Factory is cited as the first modern coworking space; it opened in San Francisco in 2006 (Shepard, 2018) to replace The Spiral Muse, which had closed the following year due to financial difficulties (Merkel, 2015).

Neuberg has been recognized as the first person to connect the word coworking with a flexible workspace and its collaborative use (e.g., Josef & Back, 2018). He stated that there is no connection with the term coined in 1999 by De Koven and that the term he independently co-created is the most appropriate to describe the conceptual starting point for The Spiral Muse. Also in 2005, The Hub was founded in London, UK, a space that later evolved into the global network The Impact Hub, a group of collaboratively managed coworking spaces (Waters-Lynch & Potts, 2017). However, similar forms of open, collaborative offices had already been operating since the early 1990s, even without using the term coworking. These early spaces were designed for independent professionals, such as remote workers and freelancers who wanted to be part of a cooperative work culture.

Orel and Dvouletý (2020) noted the common misuse of the term coworking in both popular and academic publications. In a review by Johns et al. (2024), the terms "coworking" and "co-working" appeared with almost equal frequency in the literature (coworking generated 63 results, while co-working generated 64). The word "coworking" has often been replaced by "co-working," which represents a departure from the model's true meaning because it denotes cooperation between individuals interconnected within a given organization, where

they act as "co-workers". In May 2018, the Associated Press Stylebook removed the hyphenated version of the term, providing clarity on the often confusing academic and industry terminology in this field (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020).

The term "co-workplace" refers to a dedicated and shared work environment. In contrast, "office-lessness" indicates the lack of a traditional office, describing the condition of not having a fixed, physical place of work (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020).

The Coworking Manifesto, formulated by the early architects of coworking around 2005 and still serving as a statement of core values for many coworking spaces, envisions *"a new economic engine composed of collaboration and community, in contrast to the silos and secrecy of the 19th/20th century economy"* (wiki.coworking.org). Therefore, coworking spaces promote themselves as smart, networked counter-spaces that defeat the downsides of digital capitalism—most notably the "loneliness epidemic" (King, 2017) caused by individualization and neoliberalism (de Peuter et al., 2017; Vidaillett & Bousalham, 2020). While coworking spaces challenge the fragmenting post-Fordist regime by re-territorializing work and offering stability to workers, they also reinforce the very norms and values they seek to challenge. Digital reliance is at the heart of this contradictory development.

CWSs are not configured as singular entities but rather as a complex ecosystem of interdependent variables. Research conducted by Privett (2020) highlights that the successful member experience relies upon the evolving and synergistic interactions between several structural dimensions. This analysis formalized a new conceptual model of coworking based on four interconnected variables: space, services, engagement (community involvement), and ethos (shared identity and values). The specific manifestation of these variables is contingent upon the orientation and demographic composition of the individual CWS. The distinctive contribution of this model lies in positioning the member experience at the core of the coworking offering, recognizing it as the critical and previously overlooked conceptual aspect. Consequently, the CWS is conceptualized as a work experience defined by its member community, with the four structural variables entirely focused on meeting their needs.

3.2. Neo-Corporate vs. Resilient Coworking Model

"The 'neo-corporate' coworking model emerged in recent years as a combination of real estate business and market intermediation, appealing to freelance workers but also to a larger pool of other subjects, including entrepreneurs, social entrepreneurs and startups" (Gandini & Cossu, 2019, p. 4). This model of coworking, promoted by global giants like WeWork, Google, or Impact Hub, essentially functions as a real estate brokerage service. It responds to the growing demand for flexibility in the workplace by offering "cool" spaces that reflect the lifestyle and values of the tech sector. In practice, it rents workstations to individual professionals, often through a franchise system or with periodic payments from members (Gandini & Cossu, 2019).

Spatially, WeWork environments are designed as vibrant, high-tech offices. They generally feature noisy common areas on the ground floor, marked by a cafeteria, and one or more quiet zones, usually located on upper floors and accessible only to members. These areas are interspersed with recreational spaces that include food and beverage dispensers and leisure

items, all intended to stimulate creativity and casual encounters among workers. Visually, these spaces are characterized by a significant presence of banners or signage often displaying the word "community." The goal is to emphasize a carefully engineered sociality which, however, *"enacts a watered-down notion of community"* (Gandini & Cossu, 2019, p. 4).

For neo-corporate coworking spaces, the word community very often functions as a marketing tool, used to collectively build an image that aims to add value to participants' activities and distinguish them from competitors. Their connection to local reality often appears weak, and many coworking spaces remain disconnected from their surrounding urban context (Arvidsson, 2018). These aspects reinforce the interpretation of coworking by de Peuters et al. (2017) as an inherently ambivalent set of meanings and practices. It holds an unfulfilled potential for implementing work practices based on collectivity, but ultimately, it reinforces a neoliberal entrepreneurial ethos.

Despite the neo-corporate trend, smaller, independently managed coworking spaces remain a vital component of the sector. These spaces focus on creating new infrastructures for freelance workers, facilitating alternative organizational approaches to work. In this sense, they represent a significant movement of opposition to neoliberal culture.

Gandini and Cossu (2019) propose the term "resilient coworking" to describe this new model. The adjective resilient signifies a perspective that doesn't resist change but rather embraces and accepts it as a core part of existence, with a focus on sustainable living. *"Thus, we define as 'resilient' those coworking spaces that embrace the evolution of work in a direction of flexibility and independence but, in so doing, oppose the entrepreneurial ideology of 'collaborative individualism' that characterises the neo-corporate model"* (Gandini & Cossu, 2019, p. 6).

At their core, resilient spaces strive to bring the quality of the social relations to the centre of the purpose and ethos of their practice, looking to shape coworking in a direction of developing 'actually communitarian' interaction. This entails:

- a) Proactively working to maintain a closer relationship between the space and the geographical context in which it appears;
- b) Producing outcomes, as a space, that do not reproduce the individualized ethos the neo-corporate model engenders;
- c) Making use of some of the same discourses and practices that characterise coworking also in its neo-corporate version, such as the 'community' signifier, yet in the pursuit of combining economic sustainability with social impact (Gandini & Cossu, 2019, p. 6).

"Resilient coworking" practices have begun to spread beyond "creative cities" (d'Ovidio & Cossu, 2016). However, nearly all empirical research on coworking focuses on experiences in global creative cities, particularly in the West (e.g., San Francisco, Berlin, Barcelona, New York, Athens) and in Southeast Asia. This reflects the presumed natural connection between coworking and the urban environment, given that these spaces are viewed as a crucial interface for knowledge production and the dissemination of creative projects. Despite this, the literature highlights a significant lack of research on coworking practices in non-urban contexts (Gandini & Cossu, 2019).

“The affirmation of collaborative workspaces should be seen as one side of a broader transformation – the other being the ‘platformization’ of work (Gandini, 2019) – towards the institutionalisation of ‘post-employment’ work regimes, whereby the displacement and individualization of work in its entrenched relationship with digital technology becomes the status quo” (Gandini & Cossu, 2019, p. 15).

3.3. Classifications

Over the last decade, the concept of coworking has expanded, evolving with its associated industry. As a result, references to coworking often refer to notions that are quite different from the original concept. A simple historical overview would be insufficient, as different forms of collaborative workspaces have emerged over time, particularly between the late 20th and early 21st centuries. For this reason, an appropriate classification is necessary to distinguish these different forms from the modern understanding of coworking.

Scientific literature highlights the extreme heterogeneity of the coworking phenomenon. For this reason, a wide variety of practices and spaces have been grouped together under the generic term "coworking". In recent years, academic research has focused on various aspects of coworking and flexible workspaces. However, the historical development of coworking models remains sparsely studied (Orel & Dvoutý, 2020). The 21st-century economy, increasingly based on knowledge and concentrated in urban areas, has favored the rapid growth of coworking. However, this expansion has led to such a diversification of the phenomenon that it has become difficult to define the precise characteristics a space must have to be considered a coworking space.

As King (2017) pointed out, we are no longer sure how to define coworking in a way that allows for meaningful forecasts. There is a great deal of confusion about what is and is not a coworking space. The confusion stems from two main issues: coworking is a trending term, and the media and many "coworking-like" organizations have used the label vaguely. Additionally, as the coworking industry has grown and become more hybridized, different forms have emerged that partially overlap (Orel & Bennis, 2021). Coworking has become a popular umbrella term. Scholars, the media, and coworking-related businesses have all used the label to describe the broader, more flexible serviced office industry. With the intense hybridization of the model, the very concept of coworking is at risk of losing a coherent meaning, even as the coworking business continues to grow.

Because coworking is an emerging topic, the existing research is still limited and heterogeneous. In general, empirical studies on coworking spaces are more numerous than theoretical publications. There is also an excessive focus on urban areas at the expense of rural ones (Josef, 2017). Finally, the literature shows a lack of complete and rigorous classifications for the different types of coworking spaces (Thornton et al., 2023).

The growth of coworking has led to a strong differentiation among spaces, prompting researchers to classify their various forms and variants (Kraus et al., 2022). Most authors categorize these models based on the added value each space offers. Others, however, use the type of governance as a distinguishing feature, while some focus on their openness to specific user groups (Thornton et al., 2023).

Several studies have classified multi-tenant offices into different subgroups: serviced offices, incubators, regular business centers, and coworking spaces. "A *multi-tenant office* can be described as a building in which office space and possibly a number of shared facilities and/or services are offered to multiple organizations" (Weijs-Perrée et al., 2019, p. 534).

Spinuzzi (2012) classified coworking spaces based on the level of cooperation among users. He identified two models:

- *Good Neighbors model*: members collaborate by helping each other on their individual projects.
- *Good Partners model*: members work together on joint projects.

Building on Spinuzzi's approach, Merkel (2015) proposed a classification based on the level of involvement and mediation by managers, differentiating hosts into two groups: *Service providers* focus on the physical environment (creating a pleasant, professional, and productive workspace, leaving collaboration and collective innovation to the initiatives of the workers); *Visionary hosts* (community managers) focus on the social environment (actively building the community and facilitating connections among workers).

According to the definition of coworking proposed by Parrino (2015, p. 11), a coworking space is characterized by:

1. *The co-localisation of various coworkers within the same work environment;*
2. *The presence of workers heterogeneous by occupation and/or sector in which they operate and/or organisational status and affiliation;*
3. *The presence (or not) of activities and tools designed to stimulate the emergence of relationships and collaboration among coworkers.*

Fuzi (2015) noted that different types of coworking spaces offer their users varying levels of moral, emotional, financial, and professional support to aid their entrepreneurial efforts, but he did not provide a precise classification.

Kojo and Nenonen (2016), after analyzing 15 coworking spaces in Finland, identified six types of coworking spaces: public offices that act as coworking environments (e.g., free coworking spaces such as libraries), third places (e.g., public spaces that require the purchase of services, like a café), collaboration hubs (e.g., spaces that focus on collaboration among workers), coworking hotels (e.g., shared office spaces with a short-term lease and a compact package of services), incubators (e.g., shared office spaces focused on entrepreneurship), and shared studios (e.g., shared offices where a company or an entrepreneur rents a space based on a flexible contract, with a selection criterion related to community fit). However, their proposal is limited because it only considered the business model (non-profit or profit) and accessibility (public, private, or semi-private) as parameters.

Weijs-Perrée et al. (2016), after analyzing various infrastructures, classified different shared offices into the following categories: business centers, serviced offices, coworking offices, and incubators.

Capdevila (2017) defines two organizational dimensions, distinguishing between top-down and bottom-up management, as well as between exploratory and exploitative approaches.

Other scholars have highlighted how different design choices characterize various types of coworking spaces, including their aesthetic features and the services they offer.

Ivaldi, Pais & Scaratti (2018), based on the roles, goals, and motivations of managers, identified four types of coworking spaces:

- **Infrastructural coworking:** These spaces aim to provide optimal work infrastructure and consider community activities to be complementary.
- **Relational coworking:** They promote knowledge sharing among workers, facilitate interactions, and view the community manager's role as central.
- **Networked coworking:** These spaces serve as matchmakers, strengthening relationships between coworkers and the outside world.
- **Welfare coworking:** They emphasize worker well-being, comfort, and business success.

Avdikos and Merkel (2019) divide coworking spaces into two general types:

- **Entrepreneurial-led coworking spaces:** These are deeply rooted in the startup ecosystem, with the goal of supporting business growth.
- **Community-led coworking spaces:** This category corresponds to the "individual-purposed" spaces identified by Orel and Bennis (2021).

Grazian (2020) identifies a small number of emerging segments, which include professional women, young men who endorse ideals of hard work and beer-drinking, Black and Latino entrepreneurs, non-profit organizations, and business people attracted to more conservative settings.

Privett (2020) distinguishes between a permissive and participatory approach to coworking spaces, where members have a high degree of autonomy to make changes, and a service-oriented model, which can be more closely compared to hospitality environments where members make requests that the manager seeks to satisfy. This distinction is made with the goal of making the coworking experience as positive as possible.

Akhavan (2021) differentiates between coworking spaces that are generally attractive to freelancers and entrepreneurs seeking a comfortable "third space" to work, and more specialized venues belonging to specific sectors or market segments.

Orel and Bennis (2021) distinguish between the traditional coworking model, which they define as "individual-purposed coworking spaces," and three alternative models that take into account other significant aspects of coworking. They also identify three types of "non-coworking shared offices" that are sometimes mistakenly seen as coworking spaces. Their proposal is a taxonomy of coworking spaces that could form the basis for further research and be open to revision as the industry evolves. The characteristics of the four identified models are outlined below:

Individual-purposed CWSs: Certain necessary and sufficient characteristics allow us to distinguish the traditional coworking model from other settings. These include open-plan corporate offices with flexible workstations that promote collaboration and innovation among employees, as well as cafés, hotel lobbies, libraries, or airport business centers where freelancers or business travelers work temporarily without any mediated social interaction. The defining characteristics of this model are:

1. Coworking involves work.
2. That work is alongside other people who are also working.
3. The kind of work tends to be knowledge work.

Two additional characteristics distinguish coworking from other non-coworking activities:

4. Coworking spaces intentionally bring people together in that work environment (through knowledge sharing, collaboration, mentorship, support, and education).
5. Coworking spaces overcome institutional and project-specific barriers, connecting people who otherwise wouldn't work together.

Creation-purposed CWSs: A specific type of coworking space provides physical tools, material substrates, and specialized activities for creating physical objects (Bergner & Chen, 2017). This type of space, considered a form of coworking by most scholars, is not designed like an office but rather like a laboratory. It targets specialists (hobbyists, creative artists, or others who do not use the space as their primary source of income), providing them with equipment, materials, and training. These spaces share the following characteristics with traditional coworking: they emphasize a sense of community, share physical resources that would be too expensive or underutilized for individual users, allow unaffiliated individuals to work in the same environment, and offer opportunities for professional development, training, and support.

A particular subcategory includes spaces related to engineering and high-tech sectors, often divided into two subgroups: hackerspaces (which are typically bottom-up and strongly community-focused; Kera, 2012) and makerspaces (which are more top-down and focus more on training and knowledge transfer to their users, often allowing for the construction of larger-scale products; Bergner & Chen, 2018). The differences between these two are not significant enough to justify a separate coworking category. In summary, Creation-purposed coworking spaces shift the emphasis from office work to more specialized types of labor.

Group-purposed CWSs: This category highlights the increase in coworking spaces that target companies and teams rather than individual workers (Spreitzer, Bacevice & Garrett, 2017). Flexibility seems to come before community (short-term leases, capacity for growth). Similar examples, such as executive suites or serviced offices, existed before the coworking industry. Individual independent professionals are replaced by entire teams with their own separate offices, and inter-institutional connections are made at the floor or building level, or virtually using Internet-based social networking tools. Formal events and informal occasions in common social areas, cafés, or game rooms connect people across institutions, but most of the work happens among people who work for the same organization. Although these spaces also have open-plan workstations for freelancers and other individuals, this is a secondary target

market, allowing the spaces to fill empty desks and enabling their primary clients to use the "coworking" label.

The concept of coworking is becoming increasingly attractive to companies, which are progressively encouraging the development of flexible and agile products, and outsourcing their workforce through short-term contracts to remote freelancers. This dynamic is exemplified by the "gig economy" (e.g., Bughin, Lund & Remes, 2016), the "Hollywood model" of work (Davidson, 2015), and the outsourcing of flexible office spaces like coworking. Corporate users are increasingly drawn to the social resources offered by coworking, such as intentional community and inter-institutional collaboration. These aspects, which have been emphasized by coworking since its origins, were not typically offered by traditional providers of flexible office spaces. Furthermore, the presence of other professionals within a coworking space allows corporate users to easily outsource talent and expertise. Organizations have turned to coworking to explore alternative work scenarios, find a substitute for the traditional corporate office, and discover innovative ways to promote co-creation with external stakeholders (Josef & Back, 2018). Many traditional providers of flexible office space have reinvented themselves as coworking spaces. This phenomenon reflects a significant change in the office real estate market and in the needs of companies and professionals.

Schopf et al. (2015) used the term *corpworking* to describe coworking spaces for corporate employees that can also function as a company showroom, creating brand value for both current employees, who are gratified by the quality of their workspace, and for potential employees who work independently within the same coworking space. Mitev et al. (2019) developed the definition of corpworking by describing it as a "third corporate space" that allows a company's employees to mix with external entrepreneurs, innovators, and other knowledge workers. Corpworking is, in effect, coworking aimed primarily at corporate teams, provided by multinational corporations operating on a large scale in the serviced office market. Informal networking mechanisms are generally minimized and replaced by more formal interactions, and the space is characterized by more luxurious facilities than a traditional coworking space to maintain the pre-existing corporate culture. The literature offers two subtypes of this kind of coworking: an open house model (companies offer workspace as a public service to non-employees, usually with the goal of building their brand) and a campsite model (an internal, invitation-only space where teams from one company collaborate side-by-side with colleagues from another).

As with creation-focused coworking spaces, one could reasonably argue that team-purposed coworking spaces should not be called "coworking" at all. The key message is that team-purposed coworking spaces must promote social interactions across different institutions to earn the title of coworking (otherwise, they are simply outsourced, flexible, serviced offices)—and many of them do (Orel & Bennis, 2021).

Startup-purposed spaces: They are called incubators, accelerators, or university innovation spaces and they cater to startup teams or individuals who need help to transform their initial idea or business into a successful startup. They emphasize inter-institutional cooperation, bringing together mentors and investors, and facilitating connections between novice entrepreneurs and experienced team members who can help them bring a great idea or technology

to fruition. They also offer a collaborative workspace where different startup teams can interact and have access to freelancers who might join the teams, either to solve a short-term problem or as founding employees.

Although these spaces usually take the form of "office coworking," this is not strictly necessary. Similar to team-purposed coworking, incubators and accelerators often target teams—though these are less structured startup teams, which they often help to form. The community they promote is not the one Brad Neuberg was looking for when he started his coworking space in San Francisco, but rather the type of investment and mentorship needed to build a successful business. These spaces do not promote independence of location or work; they often require startups to give up much of their autonomy and relocate far from home to join the space. Above all, the coworking component in these spaces is often secondary to their main goal of promoting entrepreneurial success and, ultimately, creating financial value in ways that are not as central to traditional, individual-focused coworking spaces.

Startup incubators and business accelerators tend to differ in a few important ways (Waters-Lynch et al., 2016). Accelerators exchange their mentorship and help for an ownership stake in the companies they are accelerating. This is because business accelerators are backed by investors who hope to gain significant profits from their investment in these companies, in exchange for the money, time, and connections they provide. Incubators, on the other hand, are more likely to operate as non-profits, to promote entrepreneurship, innovation, and small business success as an end in itself. Without a profit motive, they depend on external funding sources. In fact, they are often direct government mandates to support innovation and business growth at a regional level, or they are university centers that help students transition from theory to applied business success. They often fill available extra seating by marketing it as coworking space. Unlike other forms of coworking, however, the mentorship, funding, and networking of members with external experts and investors are the primary purpose of these spaces, and coworking serves only as a means to an end. They help develop a successful business and, as such, are conceived for temporary support.

Based on the conclusions of Orel and Bennis (2021), the wide variety of coworking styles and types suggests a reformulation of the necessary and sufficient conditions for defining a true coworking space. These conditions are:

- CWSs must be work-purposed environments;
- A certain amount of support for social interaction among members is an integral part of the concept;
- A certain degree of social interaction between different institutions (inter-institutional) is also fundamental.

Regarding the support for social interaction, spaces can vary significantly in several ways:

- The level of activity with which they promote such interactions;
- The type of connections they facilitate;
- The formality of the interactions;
- The depth of the social ties;

- The extent of collaboration;
- The physical design features that encourage interaction.

There are valid arguments suggesting that both homogeneity and heterogeneity can best represent coworking. On one hand, homogeneity fosters a stronger community and facilitates collaboration (Bouncken and Reuschl, 2018). On the other hand, heterogeneity promotes the diversity and openness that were core values embraced by the movement's early founders (Rus and Orel, 2015). This latter approach aligns better with the institutional independence emphasized by traditional, individual-focused coworking, where maintaining autonomy from often bureaucratic or dysfunctional corporate cultures was a key motivating force (Neuberg, 2005).

3.4. Types of Users

CWSs are dynamic, low-cost, and stimulating work environments where professionals from different backgrounds can interact, share knowledge, and collaborate. Although these spaces are often associated with freelancers (independent workers who need a professional workspace without high costs), various studies indicate that the user base is more heterogeneous, also including remote workers (employees looking for a workspace that offers more structure and fewer distractions than working from home), extended workers, corporations (large companies using coworking spaces for remote teams, client meetings, and temporary offices), small firms, startups and small businesses (new companies that need an affordable, flexible office and networking opportunities), and students (Bednár & Danko, 2020; Weijs-Perrée et al., 2019). Research shows that the typical profile of a coworking user is a 36-year-old, educated, white man who works as a freelancer (Deskmag, 2022; Lorne, 2020). Generally, users value the environment for its opportunities for informal conversation, knowledge sharing, and brainstorming with other members.

“This variety of users from different organizations sharing a space makes 'coworkers/coworking' distinct from 'co-workers/co-working' which describes the more commonly understood situation of workers from the same organisation working in a project together” (Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto, 2024, p. 1).

CWSs primarily focus on creating a community by interconnecting and stimulating tenants who generally work alone. Interactions between users are mainly fostered by hosts or managers who facilitate the creation of social events (Parrino, 2015). The number of members influences the nature of the community. Smaller spaces tend to foster greater cohesion and closer interactions among members. In contrast, larger coworking spaces offer a broader network of professional and social opportunities (Howell, 2022).

CWSs also differ in the types of users they welcome. Some adopt an "open" approach, accepting anyone who pays a membership fee, which leads to a heterogeneous mix of professionals. Others, however, focus on specific groups (e.g., only startups or only freelancers) or on a particular sector (such as media, healthcare, or programming). As highlighted by Howell (2022), while a more homogeneous community may limit the potential user base, it often generates a greater sense of belonging and deeper interactions due to the similarities among members.

This variability is also reflected in the lease terms offered. Almost all spaces offer flexible contracts, typically "month-to-month" with the possibility of cancellation at any time, a formula that particularly attracts founders of young startups and individual workers. Others offer daily passes, ideal for digital nomads or freelancers who need flexibility. There are also spaces that offer multi-year contracts, which are designed to attract corporate clients.

A crucial shift in market dynamics is the growing population of employees utilizing these spaces. This segment is a rising percentage of coworking membership, and new partnerships between coworking providers and traditional organizations—such as WeWork managing IBM's Manhattan campus—raise fundamental questions about the evolving relationship between the organization, the workspace, and the employee experience (Privett, 2020).

CWSs also vary in relation to their external partners. From an economic standpoint, not all CWSs are able to be self-sufficient. Consequently, many seek funding and sponsorships from local governments, universities, or companies. These sponsors can not only provide crucial financial support but also add prestige and legitimacy to the space itself. Furthermore, CWSs can form partnerships with other organizations to offer their members additional services or specialized resources, enriching their value proposition beyond just a workspace.

The concept of coworking is extending beyond the corporate world, particularly into the academic sector. Remote higher education and research have distinct costs and benefits, much like remote work does for companies. Just as coworking has allowed businesses to retain the benefits of in-person work while reducing the costs of remote work, it has the potential to do the same for academic research. As Bennis and Orel (2025) point out, coworking spaces can help preserve face-to-face social relationships and interactions while also improving flexibility, inclusivity, and collaboration among different university institutions. This aspect becomes crucial as remote research becomes an increasingly common and necessary practice.

Much of the existing literature tends to uncritically adopt a view of coworking members as "independent" and "entrepreneurial" individuals, conceptualizing these spaces as tools for open innovation and collective capacity. However, this perspective does not sufficiently consider the reality of many users whose condition is characterized by job precarity and flexibility. For these professionals, coworking spaces can reproduce and even stabilize a situation of constant struggle for economic survival. Therefore, future conceptualizations of coworking and its members should move beyond the utopian vision of a new world of work. Instead, it is necessary to pay greater attention to dynamics such as forced mobility, flexibility, and "platformisation" (Richardson, 2021) that characterize a large portion of the work done within these spaces.

3.5. Motivations and User Preferences

The rapid growth of coworking is due to the increasing awareness of the limitations offered by traditional alternatives, such as the corporate office, working from home, or using a local café. These disadvantages include a lack of social and professional interactions, isolation, and the increasingly blurred line between private and professional life. The main factors driving the evolution of coworking spaces and attracting users are related to several aspects:

- New ways of working: A more flexible and autonomous approach.
- Attractiveness: The demand for a space that offers more than just a desk in a good location.
- Work-life balance: The ability to separate the home environment from the work environment.
- Economic efficiency: Access to flexible and short-term rental agreements.
- Sustainability: The sharing of facilities, equipment, and services.

These combined elements effectively meet the needs of modern professionals who are looking for a more dynamic and advantageous work environment.

Specific studies on coworking users are exploratory in nature and focus primarily on their motivations for choosing this type of work environment. Research indicates that rental costs are one of the most important factors, along with location, a sense of community, and a stimulating and dynamic atmosphere.

The study by Bacevice and Spreitzer (2023) explored how CWSs allow people to shape their professional identity “providing other important attributes of work to help it feel embodied and grounded” (p. 59). CWS “serve as identity anchoring environments” (*Ibidem*) for the construction of professional identity, as they allow workers to interact with the material environment in specific ways. This occurs primarily through three interconnected processes. First, the strategic use of the physical elements of the space allows professionals to establish and validate their credibility. Second, the physical environment facilitates the promotion of a common ethic, strengthening a sense of belonging and sharing among users. Finally, the spatial organization and the arrangement of furnishings act as catalysts to energize social and professional interactions. More generally, the managers of these spaces act as active mediators, curating and offering a strategic combination of physical, spatial, and symbolic aspects of work. Their purpose is to assist workers in communicating and consolidating their professional identity within a well-defined social and professional context.

A survey-based study conducted by Weijs-Perrée et al. (2019) in the Netherlands explored the motivations behind professionals' choice of a coworking space and the factors that led to their final decision. The results showed that the most important characteristics in their selection were accessibility, a stimulating atmosphere, and economic affordability. In contrast, facilities and services such as reception, hospitality, events, and a variety of space offerings were considered less relevant. Similarly, Appel-Meulenbroek et al. (2021) conducted a comparative analysis across three European countries, finding that for many members, a sense of community, networking**, and social interactions were the least significant motivations for their choice. These studies, along with other recent research (e.g., Ayodele et al., 2022; Berdicchia, Fortezza & Masino, 2023), highlight a disparity between the idealized models of coworking (often emphasized for their social component) and the actual practical needs of their users.

A study by Lescarret et al. (2022), based on an online questionnaire completed by 268 French remote workers, analyzed the factors influencing employees' intention to work remotely in a coworking space. The research was based on the premise that the negative aspects of working

from home, such as perceived social isolation, would impact this decision. The authors also investigated participants' opinions on teleworking in a coworking space, measuring their perceived usefulness, perceived feasibility, attitude, and behavioral intention. The results showed that perceived social isolation and a lack of perceived work comfort at home directly influenced participants' perceived usefulness of coworking and, consequently, their intention to continue working there in the future. However, factors such as budget, management agreement, and job compatibility were identified as elements that moderate participants' intentions to work remotely in a coworking space, even when it was perceived as beneficial.

One of the few studies on the characteristics of multi-tenant offices focused on user satisfaction, which is directly linked to their preferences (Hartog, Weijs-Perrée & Appel-Meulenbroek, 2018). The different physical characteristics of these offices were analyzed and grouped into ten main factors: location, office exterior and division, décor, facilities and services, seclusion rooms, leisure areas, information and communication technology (ICT) and equipment, privacy, and indoor climate. The study's results revealed that users of these facilities were least satisfied with their personal control over the indoor climate. In contrast, they were most satisfied with accessibility and the availability of fixed workstations.

Individual differences (such as age, gender, time spent in the office, and previous self-employment experience) influence preferences for various aspects of workspaces. For example, it has been observed that younger workers tend to prefer an environment that stimulates teamwork, while older workers place greater importance on personal control over the indoor climate (Rothe et al., 2011).

User preferences in coworking are also influenced by their professional sector. For example, professionals in the creative industry tend to prefer a flexible layout that includes shared areas, meeting spaces, and interiors that reflect their company's identity (Remøy & Van der Voordt, 2013). In line with previous research (e.g., Capdevila, 2013), the aforementioned study by Weijs-Perrée et al. (2019) confirms that accessibility is the most important factor in choosing a coworking space. Coworkers often seek a space in the immediate vicinity of their home. In contrast, services and facilities such as reception, hospitality, events, and a wide variety of spaces are not considered priorities. In particular, users prefer a workspace that offers a combination of open and enclosed spaces, which helps to avoid noise issues and a lack of privacy typical of entirely open-plan environments. Finally, preferences also extend to the community's composition. Coworkers tend to favor a diverse group but not one that is too varied. This allows them to exchange knowledge on different areas of expertise and complement each other, thereby promoting collaboration and mutual learning.

Based on the user motivations and preferences analyzed, clear implications emerge for the design and management of coworking spaces. To attract and retain members, it's essential to offer a stimulating and creative atmosphere with a welcoming interior. From a functional standpoint, a layout that combines open and enclosed spaces is crucial to support various activities and ensure both socialization and concentration. The variety of spaces, which includes meeting rooms, kitchen areas, event zones, and informal corners, is equally vital to meet the needs of an increasingly diverse user base. Another key factor is accessibility, which includes the convenience of reaching the space, even by car. At the same time, to align with

users' primary economic motivations, it's imperative to offer workstations at a reasonable price with flexible or short-term rental agreements. Finally, the design must incorporate the capacity for continuous adaptation. Managers should constantly monitor users' needs and preferences, using modular furnishings and flexible solutions to customize the space based on individual and collective needs.

3.6. Coworking and Remote Working

The relationship between coworking and remote working is a topic of growing interest in the scholarly literature. Remote work is a practice where individuals operate outside of a conventional office, often from home. Coworking, on the other hand, offers a shared workspace to professionals from different companies or who are freelancers. Initially seen as two distinct approaches, the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated their interaction. The term "remote working" is an umbrella term that includes various work arrangements performed outside the main workplace, referring to both employees and self-employed individuals (ILO, 2020). The past decade has seen a progressive increase in the portion of work that can be done remotely. This increase has coincided with the opening of collaborative workspaces, such as CWSs, which represent a valuable alternative to both traditional offices and the home (Mariotti, Akhavan & Rossi, 2023).

The literature has highlighted how CWSs can serve as local hubs for remote workers. This model, known as "hybrid remote work" allows companies to reduce traditional office costs while offering employees the flexibility to work from home or from a coworking space. Several studies show that the use of coworking spaces by remote workers can improve socialization, creativity, and psychological well-being, counteracting the isolation often associated with working from home (Spinuzzi, 2012). Research suggests that coworking can increase the productivity of remote workers by providing a supportive community and social stimulation not always available in a home environment (Bouncken & Reuschl, 2018). The networking opportunities and spontaneous collaboration within these spaces also foster knowledge sharing and innovation (Gandini, 2015). Therefore, coworking is establishing itself not just as an alternative to office work, but as a strategic complement to remote work, promoting a more flexible and effective model for both organizations and workers.

In-depth studies on the impact of working from home on worker well-being highlight significant challenges. Research has particularly brought to light social and professional isolation (Charalampous et al., 2019) and the difficulties in achieving work-life balance, especially when considering gender differences (Alfano et al., 2023). Work-life balance, defined as "the aim of working women and men to achieve a balance between work and other spheres of their lives" (Eurofound, 2022, p. 87), is recognized as an essential dimension of the quality of working life. Its contribution to health, well-being, and overall quality of life is widely documented (Grote & Guest, 2017; Lunau et al., 2014). However, recent developments in information and communication technologies (ICTs) and the adoption of mobile technologies have allowed work to increasingly invade the private sphere (Orlikowski, 2007). The resulting blurring of spatial and temporal boundaries between different spheres of life (Webster & Randle, 2016) makes the study of work-life balance an urgent research issue.

The results of numerous studies confirm the advantages of teleworking, such as reduced traffic and the resulting environmental benefits (Cerqueira et al., 2020), as well as the flexibility to achieve a more satisfying work-life balance, allowing for more time to be spent with family (Herrera et al., 2022). However, research also identifies disadvantages, including low work performance (Allen, Golden & Shockley, 2015), work-life conflict (Zhang et al., 2020), a perceived sense of social isolation when working from home (Lescarret, Lemerrier & Le Floch, 2022), and difficulty concentrating on work (Ton et al., 2022). In some respects, these problems are inevitable, for example, in a family with children.

On a critical level, however, the use of the concept of work-life balance in this context is often subject to contestation. Rather than promoting an increase in free time for personal interests, the expression risks justifying the absorption of aspects of private life into the work sphere. This architecture, which blends spatial and temporal boundaries, supports a system that renders invisible other forms of unpaid labor and devalues personal and recreational activities, thereby promoting a vision of society that is totally work-centric (Jalili, 2021). In fact, instead of guaranteeing more free time, this model incorporates personal time and space into the working day, which then inevitably extends and diffuses into the private sphere.

The emergence of these issues has stimulated the development of alternative solutions. The concept of the Remote Working Center (RWC), initially proposed to solve the problems experienced by home-based teleworkers, identifies a centralized space for various types of work. RWCs are often located in different parts of the city (e.g., residential areas) and offer a variety of workspaces for teleworkers, accommodating the needs of versatile activities and providing services such as internet connectivity, meeting rooms, etc. (Lan & Feng, 2025). People must physically travel to reach these spaces, which entails additional time, costs, and effort compared to working from home. Commuting to remote working centers has important implications for the real estate market and for transportation planning.

In recent decades, various terms have been used for this third workplace, such as Telecenters (Johnson, 2003), Smart Work Centers (Errichiello & Pianese, 2019), and CWSs (Houghton, Foth & Hearn, 2018). These facilities differ from one another in terms of their user groups, locations, financial resources, and tools for collaboration. Telecenters accommodate employees who live in their vicinity, are heavily dependent on public funding, and are designed to provide basic services like internet access in low-income areas. Smart working centers are supported by private organizations that cover both metropolitan and rural areas. CWSs, on the other hand, tend to accommodate innovative projects for self-employed workers and entrepreneurs. As integral parts of urban development, these centers have the potential to promote a mixed-use model in central areas and encourage a type of sustainable mobility.

An emerging trend is the adoption of a hybrid workplace culture, which combines three locations: home, remote work centers, and the office. These centers appeal to workers because they blend the benefits of both working from home and working from a traditional office (Lan & Feng, 2025).

Recent studies aim to identify the factors that motivate teleworkers to use RWCs. A determining factor is accessibility, whether by public transit or private car. Since commuting to

these centers requires transport mode choices, it's essential to fully understand the mobility dynamics of teleworkers. For example, the availability of parking can be a relevant policy to promote the use of these facilities, given that most commuters travel on foot, by bicycle, by public transport, or by private car (Corvec, 2023). The use of these centers is also incentivized by negative experiences with working from home, such as a strong sense of social isolation and a feeling of discomfort (Lescarret et al., 2022). However, in the context of a hybrid work culture, the decision to use an RWC is intrinsically influenced by the conditions of both the home environment and the traditional office. In fact, research has shown that the design of internal spaces is a crucial factor in improving work performance (Wijngaarden, 2023).

In CWSs, work can be analyzed along two fundamental dimensions: the practical and technical modalities of using these spaces, and the experience of social interactions. The hybrid work experience (i.e., alternating between working in a coworking space and working from home or other locations) significantly influences the overall experience of its members. For this reason, coworking managers must understand it thoroughly in order to ensure the satisfaction and loyalty of their community. This dynamic presents a crucial challenge for the cohesion and spirit of community that develops within these environments, as highlighted by Pfeffer (2024).

Lan and Feng's (2025) research, conducted in the Tokyo metropolitan area of Japan, shows that despite the existence of RWCs, working from home remains the preferred option post-pandemic. People show a greater preference for the office over RWCs and choose rail transport for their commute. The decision on where to work is influenced by various factors, particularly the nature of the job. The findings indicate that the choice of workplace is not static but depends on specific conditions:

- **Work Intensity and Type:** People are less inclined to work from home when the workload is high or when teamwork is required. This suggests that the office or external work centers are perceived as more suitable for tasks that demand collaboration or greater concentration.
- **Duration of the Workday:** The research highlights an interesting correlation with the number of hours worked: A workday of 4-6 hours makes people more likely to work away from home (in the office or at RWCs). However, with an 8-hour workday, working from home becomes the preferred option again. For very short workdays, of only 2 hours, no clear preference emerges between RWCs and the office, indicating greater variability in choices.

Based on the attributes of RWCs, the preference is for the services surrounding the facility, especially if they are within a 5-minute walk. Other important factors are the indoor environmental conditions and the size of the workspace (preference increases if the desk size is 6 sqm). The cost of using these centers is generally covered by the company. Transport subsidies for commuting to the office or a remote work center do not appear to have a significant effect on guiding the choice. Since getting to one of these centers requires travel, travel time has a significant effect on the intention to work at an RWC for almost all modes of transportation. Women are more likely to work in an RWC, as working from home or closer to home makes it easier to manage household duties in relation to traditional gender roles. Younger

people (18-44 years old) are more likely to choose to work in an RWC regardless of the mode of transport. Younger generations are relatively more willing to embrace new forms of work compared to older ones. In general, people with higher incomes tend to work from an RWC more than those with lower incomes. Previous positive experiences of working at an RWC could also influence the likelihood of choosing this workplace (Lan & Feng, 2025).

4. Working Remotely: Challenges to Labour Law from the Perspective of Individual and Collective Rights

4.1. Introductory Remarks

Dealing with co-working issues in a legal perspective requires addressing a range of side topics concerning the current social, economic and technological scenario as well as confronting with the ongoing transformations of labour law to the point of questioning the very future of labour.

In both cases, a major role has been played by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has brought about unparalleled worldwide changes, impacting all facets of human existence, including the discussion on hybrid work and, namely, on what working life and workplaces should be like.

A crucial point of this discussion is the assumption of the decoupling of 'work' from the traditional concept of 'the workplace'.

Though in many ways "revolutionary", this does not imply that work may happen nowhere or that the actual place of work does not have an impact on the very performance of work (Countouris et al., 2023).

An issue present in many forms of remote work is indeed that not only is the work not being done on an employer's premises, but it is also being performed in a private home or a private property owned by a third party (e.g. a café, a hotel or a co-working space).

As a consequence, tackling co-working issues essentially means questioning the concept of workspaces which, in turns, inevitably recall other major problems and issues: when a worker has to be considered an employee and, if so, how traditional employee protections apply?

At the same time, it is assumed that "managerial practices built around the notion of the presence and visibility of workers in the workplace are increasingly being challenged, as are the power relations on which they are premised" (Countouris et al., 2023). It is true, indeed, that with the disintegration of the traditional concept of managerial oversight, the very rationale behind employing workers under traditional employment contracts is being questioned.

More in general, it is also true that not everyone has access to the same quality of working space at home and that, when working from home, there are different sets of roles and duties – many of them 'gendered' and socially constructed – competing for workers' time and attention. The departure from a shared and standardised place of work into highly individualised locations with unequal potential and constraints can deepen existing inequalities as well as generate new ones.

The following discussion will focus on some of the issues just mentioned, attempting to show and explore the most relevant aspects thereof from a labour law perspective.

4.2. The Transformations of the Social, Economic and Technological Scenario

With the spread of digital technology and high levels of automation in production processes, the need to be actually present at the workplace has decreased further, allowing people to focus only on certain stages of these processes (Donini, 2017, p. 81; Tiraboschi, 2017, p. 931). Digital manufacturing work is indeed conceived to be carried out both inside and outside company premises (Salento, 2017, 183).

As it is well known, since the introduction of the first information technologies, which happened around the same time as what's commonly called the third industrial revolution, the classic view of the employment relationship based on unity of place (working on company premises), time (working within a single time sequence) and action (a single professional activity) has started to weaken.

Technological and organisational variables, in fact, significantly influence the way in which work is performed (Veneziani, 1987).

Case law, moreover, in its largely prevailing orientation, has singled out the identifying, determining and essential element of subordination, pursuant to Article 2094 of the Italian Civil Code, as the external direction of the work performed and, therefore, the worker's subordination to the employer's directive, supervisory and disciplinary power, which also marks the boundary with self-employment.

However, the management power may behave differently depending on the situation, in other words, it may manifest itself with varying intensity depending on the specific organisational context, such as when, for example, the employment relationship is characterised by work performance with a significant intellectual content, which may hardly be carried out under the strict directives of the employer (Cass. 4.12.2013, no. 27138; Cass. 21.10.2014, no. 22289).

As it is well known, the introduction of new technologies and new models of work organisation can erode managerial power without eliminating subordination; if anything, they increase the range of expression of the power of supervision and, consequently, accentuate its importance, to the point of challenging the primacy of the power to specify and shape the provision of work (Spinelli, 2018, p. 97 ff.).

The fluidity of space and time and, therefore, the absence of a static workplace and a pre-established working schedule in agile working do not invalidate its classification as subordinate work and do not affect the existence of the constraint of subjection to the managerial power of the employer.

The case may be different when remote work is concentrated in co-working spaces, depending on whether or not these are made available by the employer.

In the case of satellite locations of the company, the considerations already made regarding subordination apply.

In the case of spaces made available by third parties, these may be occupied by self-employed workers, quasi-subordinate workers and even employees who are free to choose their place of work. The respective labour regulations will apply to each of these types of work. The geographical distance of the worker from the organisation headquarter must not, in fact, be detrimental to the worker by negatively affecting the legal classification of the employment relationship, thereby depriving them of the corresponding protections.

4.3. What Economic and Social Impact for Remote Working?

A second area of debate on the deconstruction of the workplace, which focuses on the collective dimension of labour relations and, therefore, on the role of social partners, is connected to the analysis of the economic and social impact of remote working.

Such organisational innovation, in fact, has the potential to significantly affect not only the regulation of work in companies and public administrations, but also the transformation of socio-economic relations in local areas.

Where will knowledge workers live? Those who will increasingly be the main players in digital capitalism.

The development of remote working can enhance peripheral communities and promote the territory as a whole. It can also be a measure to tackle the so-called “brain drain”.

Yet, remote working can also lead to the depopulation of large towns, with significant consequences for commerce, construction, etc.

Today, the attractiveness of places is no longer driven solely by the availability of economic activities, but increasingly depends on the personal choices of workers.

The phenomenon of so-called south working, i.e. the opportunity to work in marginal territories (or simply on the periphery of large towns) for companies based in highly industrialised areas or even abroad, demonstrates this.

However, good intentions and even a good level of digitalisation are not enough (Aloisi & Corazza, 2022).

Internal areas are indeed often characterised by the insufficiency – or even lack – of some essential services (health, education, mobility), which makes everyday life difficult. Hence, the importance to invest in order to meet expectations of digital nomads, so to avoid the aforementioned phenomenon becoming a passing trend.

In addition, an appealing solution for promoting the so-called south-working and preventing the ongoing phenomenon of urban desertification could be the creation of co-working spaces, mostly intended as incubators for start-ups of young people or centres for developing circular economy projects at the local level.

Co-working spaces very often involve the activation of abandoned or underused buildings and encourage the creation of networks. They bring together different skills, making them available remotely and offering great opportunities to companies, workers and territories.

However, all this requires suitable policy strategies at the local level, specifically aimed at addressing issues or challenges there involved.

In the current scenario of substantial uncertainty, a top-down “one-size-fits-all” solution would be ineffective. On the contrary, local authorities should adopt strategies aimed at fostering social cohesion by promoting broad mobilisation, that is to say involving all relevant actors – companies, trade unions, local authorities – so to effectively establish a new virtuous relationship between work and the local area, being aware that the disintegration of the unity of place between business and work performance, generated by the pandemic, is now a point of no return.

Local governments should therefore adopt strategic policies to promote social cohesion through synergy between stakeholders, so as to enhance sustainable economic growth and overcome inequalities.

In this perspective, the experience of territorial social bargaining should be enhanced.

4.4. The Role of Territorial Social Bargaining

Territorial social bargaining is the most fluid, variable and least systemised aspect of our industrial relations system, on the borderline between territorial consultation and real bargaining. It is, in fact, a negotiating activity that mainly involves trade unions and local governments at various levels, aimed at influencing distributive choices (allocation of resources) and regulatory choices (definition of rules, administrative procedures, public service practices).

This activity varies greatly from one area to another, but to a certain extent it is now routine, since it has its roots in the period between the mid-1980s and early 1990s, coinciding with the growth of the third sector, the introduction of rules on the administrative autonomy of local authorities and the development of the integrated social services system promoted by Law No 328 of 2000.

The social bargaining agenda is mainly focused on local social policies, public services and local taxation, but more recently, labour and development policies have become predominant in order to combat the crisis. It is aimed at the community as a whole and/or specific population groups.

Social bargaining mainly involves pensioners' unions and local trade union confederations while trade unions representing workers are more rarely involved. However, depending on the issues and levels concerned, other local actors and stakeholders may also be involved: from the third sector (associations, social cooperatives, foundations) to business organisations, from associations representing local authorities to local public and semi-public companies.

The 14th CGIL Report on local social bargaining highlights that, with regard to the main topics covered, the distribution of their relative weight has remained fairly consistent over the years. In 2022, the two pillars of social bargaining continue to be local welfare (social, health, social-health, etc., accounting for 77.6% of agreements) and fiscal and revenue policies (71.2%). This is followed by labour and development policies, accounting for 60% of agreements.

The area of labour and development policies is the only one to have grown during the three-year pandemic and post-pandemic period. In terms of specific measures, around 25% of agreements (compared to less than 10% in the pre-Covid period) relate to territorial development agreements and plans. However, the report notes that this only partially translates into concrete measures – particularly with regard to support for businesses and economic activities – and often expresses references to the launch of PNRR projects and the sharing of strategic guidelines between the parties (from the revitalisation of the territory to measures to ease the burden on the local economy), but also includes support for employment through the regulation of public procurement.

There is also interest in environmental policies (34.3%), in particular the definition of innovation measures: from small energy-saving measures to the modernisation of the urban hygiene system, waste cycle treatment and local transport to cover internal areas.

In conclusion, both considering the potential of remote working and the enhancement of coworking, it does not appear that local social bargaining has yet addressed the most relevant issues, maybe except for some sporadic positive experiences, but it at least contributes to creating the necessary conditions.

On the contrary, social partners should increasingly engage in this direction to better address employment transformations due to increasingly far-reaching social changes.

5. Coworking and Entrepreneurship

5.1. A New Workspace for Entrepreneurs

Coworking spaces represent a new and promising entrepreneurial phenomenon (Seo et al., 2017). From an entrepreneurial perspective, the general offering of coworking spaces can best be summarized as an 'office-as-a-service' or described as an 'on-demand office facility' (Blagoev et al., 2019, p. 895). CWSs represent a new type of workspace for entrepreneurs. Considering the rapid growth of this new organizational form, its implications still appear to be understudied. Its disruptive potential and its theoretical and practical implications in the field of entrepreneurship, as well as its potential influences on economic policies, are still largely unexplored. It is therefore necessary for research to intensify in order to provide coworking space owners, policymakers, and entrepreneurs with concrete data and detailed information on the effects of this new organizational form (Howell, 2022).

The most significant aspect of coworking, which differentiates it from other forms of entrepreneurial support like accelerators, incubators, and maker spaces, is its community dimension. This community plays a crucial role by offering founders of new businesses support in problem-solving, feedback, and new ideas. Furthermore, it provides important social support, which can lead to friendships and assistance during difficult times—a particularly relevant aspect for less-advantaged entrepreneurs. CWSs promote "collaborating independently" among various populations in a single location (Danko et al., 2024). Based on studies by Garrett et al. (2017), the sense of community within coworking spaces develops through three types of collective actions: endorsing, encountering, and engaging. Overall, CWSs offer entrepreneurs unique opportunities to build communities and to interact and learn from their peers (Howell, 2022).

Exploring the "sense of ambivalence" among peers in coworking spaces, they would act as "affective commons" (Waters-Lynch & Duff, 2019). Using a Lacanian framework for collaborative work in coworking spaces, Resch et al. (2021) theorized how this tendency is sustained by emotional fantasies of community-driven co-creation.

According to Social theory, a central element is the concept of a *social foci* — defined by Feld (1981) as “a social, psychological, legal or physical entity around which joint activities are organized” (p. 1016). In this context, CWSs can be considered a new and significant type of social foci.

Furthermore, the physical proximity among members in these spaces can promote knowledge exchange, as highlighted by Parrino (2015). Regarding the effects of social interactions on individual, group, and organizational performance, research suggests that spatial proximity is a primary driver of peer interactions. Studies, such as the one by Stam (2010), have shown that workers in close physical contact are more likely to form social bonds and exchange information. This phenomenon has been observed at various scales, ranging from the same room to the same building and even an entire geographical area (Howell, 2022).

In the entrepreneurial context, the real estate sector often presents a significant obstacle. Traditional offices are generally prohibitive due to high costs and multi-year lease agreements, which are incompatible with the uncertain nature of new ventures. This uncertainty makes entrepreneurs reluctant to take on long-term commitments, as they cannot predict their growth, the potential need for larger spaces, or even guarantee the survival of their business within a few months. To overcome these challenges, many choose to start their business from home, using makeshift offices in rooms, kitchens, or garages. Although this solution is economical and flexible, it has obvious limitations: these spaces are not ideal for managing a team or meeting clients. Furthermore, the isolation and loneliness that often accompany working from home tend to accentuate the inherent difficulties of launching a new business (Howell, 2022).

According to a study by Howell (2022), the main reason individuals choose a coworking space is not the physical infrastructure itself, but rather the community that animates it. The concentration of professionals and entrepreneurs in these environments creates a unique context that provides distinct advantages, including:

- Connections: Networking opportunities with potential clients, employees, investors, and partners.
- Solutions: Access to a pool of knowledge and experience for problem-solving and generating new ideas.
- Energy and motivation: A dynamic and stimulating environment that fuels passion and determination in pursuing one's goals.
- Social support: A context of friendship and mutual encouragement, which is essential for facing moments of difficulty and uncertainty.

According to Clayton et al. (2018), CWSs offer services that complement those provided by other players within entrepreneurial ecosystems. Entrepreneurs benefit from these spaces because the very nature of coworking helps them to perceive their work as meaningful, to have greater control over their activities, and to feel part of a community. Furthermore, Spreitzer et al. (2015a,b) highlight that large companies can also benefit from coworking. For their employees, these spaces facilitate the development of new ideas, help to reduce real estate costs, and improve job satisfaction.

5.2. Implications of Coworking Spaces for Entrepreneurs

The study by Howell (2022) provides an exploratory and empirical analysis of coworking, based on an extensive collection of data from two main sources. The first source is the online platform Coworker.com, founded in 2015, which contains a vast list of coworking spaces globally. The second source consists of a dataset personally collected by the author from a large coworking space in the Eastern United States, active since 2010. This data includes both qualitative and quantitative information derived from surveys, interviews, and archival documents.

The following outlines the benefits and drawbacks for entrepreneurs working in a coworking space.

Benefits:

- **Efficiency:** Coworking allows entrepreneurs to focus on their company's core business, reducing the time and resources dedicated to managing logistics such as utilities, furniture, internet connectivity, and security. Furthermore, these spaces provide access to resources that would otherwise be economically unsustainable for a single startup, such as conference rooms and professional equipment.
- **Flexibility:** One of the main advantages of coworking over large organizations is its flexibility. Unlike traditional lease agreements, coworking spaces offer monthly rental options and a high degree of adaptability (Hampel, Tracey & Weber, 2020). This modularity allows entrepreneurs to easily scale their workspace based on business growth or contraction, adding or reducing workstations or private offices with ease.
- **Legitimacy:** Coworking provides a professional work environment, overcoming the typical limitations of working from home or in public spaces. Having an appropriate physical location to meet clients, investors, and employees lends an image of greater credibility and reliability to the business.

Disadvantages and challenges:

- **Distraction and loss of productivity:** Among the drawbacks of coworking, distractions represent one of the most common issues. Although they offer a professional environment, shared spaces can be noisy and crowded, compromising productivity. The literature on open-plan offices confirms that these environments tend to generate higher levels of noise and distraction, leading to a decrease in job satisfaction and productivity (e.g., Shalley, 1995). Similarly, while the wide range of events and services offered in coworking spaces is a benefit, it can also become a source of distraction if members participate excessively, taking time away from their work.

5.3. Implications of the Coworking Communities

Regarding the implications of the coworking communities, Howell (2022) also identifies a series of benefits and their corresponding drawbacks.

Benefits:

- **Connections:** Research shows that entrepreneurs tend to mobilize resources primarily through their pre-existing networks (such as family, friends, and former colleagues), which can limit their opportunities. Joining a coworking community provides automatic access to a vast network of weak ties, generating unprecedented networking opportunities. Physical proximity and participation in formal events facilitate interactions that can lead to new clients, employees, investors, and suppliers.
- **Solutions:** Entrepreneurs often lack the necessary skills and knowledge to address the complexities of their businesses. Coworking communities offer valuable informal support, allowing members to draw on the knowledge and experiences of others to solve problems and find answers to daily challenges.

- Energy and motivation: Many entrepreneurs experience feelings of isolation and disconnect. The dynamic atmosphere and intrinsic energy of coworking spaces act as a motivational factor, pushing individuals to work with greater intensity and strengthen their sense of purpose.
- Social support: The entrepreneurial journey, characterized by stress, ambiguity, and long working hours, can have a significant psychological impact. The friendships and social support that develop within a coworking community can alleviate these stressful pressures. Sharing challenges with people who face the same difficulties and understand the risks of entrepreneurship provides a sense of validation and a constant reminder of the value of one's work.

Disadvantages and challenges:

- Failing slow: Failure is often considered an essential component of the entrepreneurial learning process, as suggested by the motto, "fail fast, fail cheap, and move on" (Saxenian, 2014). The literature confirms this perspective, highlighting how failure can provide valuable feedback and increase the chances of success in future ventures (Khanna, Guler & Nerkar, 2016). However, within coworking communities, the strong social support among members can inadvertently delay the abandonment of a doomed initiative. The social pressure and fear of disappointing colleagues and friends can make it difficult for an entrepreneur to "give up", leading to a "slow failure" and a prolonged loss of resources.

5.4. The Coworking Experience: Who Benefits Most?

Howell (2022) studied which types of entrepreneurs benefit most from the coworking experience. Through his analysis, he documented associations between individual characteristics and the perceived sense of community. However, the author emphasizes that further research is needed to explore the causal links of these correlations. The study is based on two main theoretical perspectives:

- Local structuralism: This perspective suggests that entrepreneurs tend to form bonds with others who are similar to them, within or in close proximity to their current networks. This process, in which social embeddedness plays a key role, suggests a cumulative advantage following a "rich-get-richer" logic. Various characteristics, such as age, race, and gender, have been shown to influence the likelihood of forming bonds (Hallen, Davis & Murray, 2020).
- Agentic network change: This more recent perspective suggests that entrepreneurs can proactively overcome the limitations of their social structure and create new connections through networking processes (Vissa, 2012).

To measure the experience of members within the coworking community, Howell used four dependent variables: *Sense of Community*, *Engagement in Community*, *Importance of Community*, and *Investors from Community*. Howell analyzed how different entrepreneurial profiles experience and benefit from coworking, reaching the following conclusions.

Minority vs. non-minority entrepreneurs: Previous research suggests that minority entrepreneurs are overrepresented in the entrepreneurial field due to the additional obstacles they face compared to their non-minority counterparts, especially in obtaining resources after the startup phase. In this context, their experience in coworking communities can be viewed from two perspectives:

- Possible disadvantages: One hypothesis is that minority entrepreneurs may encounter the same biases present in other settings, finding it more difficult to form connections with other members and, consequently, to fully benefit from the opportunities offered by the community.
- Potential advantages: Another perspective suggests that minority founders may engage more with the coworking community. This is because, being less likely to have other founders in their pre-existing informal networks, they may have a greater need for and benefit more from the community.

Overall, the findings indicate that minority entrepreneurs tend to engage more with the coworking community they work in, and thus benefit more from it. This dynamic is consistent with studies highlighting that minorities tend to exhibit higher levels of collectivism (an orientation toward the well-being of the entire community), which leads them to dedicate more time and emphasis to community interactions.

Women vs. men: Previous studies show that women entrepreneurs face greater challenges than men, particularly regarding access to funding. Investors tend to disproportionately finance male entrepreneurs (Balachandra et al., 2019), a phenomenon that may be attributed to personal biases, stereotypes about the "prototype" of a successful entrepreneur, and/or homophily, where male investors more easily build relationships with their male counterparts (Greenberg & Mollick, 2017). In light of this, women may need to rely more on coworking communities to secure funding and build their businesses. These considerations suggest that the coworking experience may be different for women than for men. Specifically, women tend to be more involved in the community, place greater importance on it, and are more likely to find investors within it. Consequently, coworking spaces may prove to be more advantageous for women than for men.

Local vs. non-local entrepreneurs: Previous studies suggest that entrepreneurs who establish themselves in a new area may face competitive disadvantages, primarily due to a lack of familiarity with the local market and the absence of a local network (Zaheer & Mosakowski, 1997). Consequently, entrepreneurs tend to choose to operate in contexts where they have established roots, recognizing the strategic importance of location choice. In this scenario, non-local entrepreneurs may have a greater need to rely on coworking communities to bridge their network gap. It is, in fact, more likely that newcomers to an area will seek and desire assistance from local entrepreneurs.

Founders vs. employees: Unlike employees, for whom a job can be perceived as a mere occupation, entrepreneurs invest in their ventures at a deep level, which includes personal, financial, and emotional aspects. This commitment can generate high levels of stress and anxiety (Wasserman, 2012). Consequently, entrepreneurs are more inclined to seek out and rely

on coworking communities than employees. Howell's research (2022) confirms this dynamic, showing that founders perceive a stronger sense of community, are more engaged at a community level, and attribute greater importance to it than employees.

Entrepreneurs with market vs. non-market logic: Entrepreneurs can operate following two different logics: a market logic, which guides actions based on economic rationality and personal interest, and a non-market logic, which orients actions towards goals that transcend profit, such as family, religious, or community values. Entrepreneurs who adopt this second logic tend to view social relationships and the cultural context as an integral part of their business. Although entrepreneurs primarily focus on their core activities, it's often the spontaneous interactions within coworking spaces that generate the most significant opportunities. Entrepreneurs with a non-market logic are more likely to engage in these regular and spontaneous interactions and to spend time helping other community members. It is during these periods that stronger bonds are formed, which can lead to new opportunities. The findings from Howell's (2022) study confirm this dynamic, showing that entrepreneurs with a market logic are less inclined to perceive a sense of community, engage with it, attribute importance to it, or find investors through the community network.

In conclusion, Howell (2022) investigates whether coworking can act as an equalizer in the entrepreneurial landscape. His findings indicate that some entrepreneurs benefit from a better coworking experience than others. Specifically, the research reveals that a more positive experience is associated with:

- Minority entrepreneurs compared to non-minority ones;
- Women compared to men;
- Non-local entrepreneurs compared to local ones;
- Founders compared to employees;
- Entrepreneurs with a non-market logic compared to those with a market logic.

These correlations suggest a well-defined pattern: entrepreneurs starting from a disadvantaged position seem to reap greater benefits from coworking. Previous literature has already documented that minorities, women, and non-local entrepreneurs face competitive disadvantages, biases, and obstacles that others do not. From this perspective, coworking spaces have the potential to promote greater equality in entrepreneurship by providing crucial support to those who need it most.

6. Coworking in Peripheral and Rural Areas

6.1. Coworking in Peripheral Areas

A vast body of literature in the field of economic geography has explored peripherality, analyzing the mechanisms that consolidate the center-periphery dichotomy. Specifically, peripheral cities and regions face the challenge of balancing specialization and diversification due to a scarcity of resources and an insufficient critical mass. Studies on the development of innovative industries show that creating new development paths and clusters in non-metropolitan areas is a difficult process, even in highly developed economies (Danko et al., 2024). New development trajectories emerge in complex peripheral landscapes and are articulated across multiple territorial scales. The diffusion of innovation, including new work models, typically follows a hierarchical path that starts in urban centers and is then adopted more broadly in later stages of development (Bokányi et al., 2022).

Although CWSs are often located in close proximity to cultural and creative industries and other economic activities (Mendez-Ortega, Micek & Malochleb, 2022), they are predominantly an urban phenomenon. Initially, CWSs emerged to meet the need of self-employed workers to overcome isolation (Waters-Lynch et al., 2016). The concept gained momentum following the 2008 financial crisis, when many offices left vacant due to layoffs were converted into coworking spaces. Simultaneously, economic uncertainty, the rise of gig-work, and unemployment drove an increasing number of people toward self-employment and, consequently, toward these shared workspaces. After this initial opportunistic occupation of central offices, CWSs gradually began to spread outward from city centers, contributing to the economic revitalization of semi-central areas and the redevelopment of post-industrial buildings.

In recent years, however, their presence has also been expanding into peripheral areas, where they must contend with a limited critical mass of clients, which creates a more restricted competitive environment (Hölzel, Kolsch & de Vries, 2022). The various forms of peripherality (e.g., non-metropolitan cities or rural areas) have a direct impact on the formation of CWSs, producing specific local and non-local effects. This allows for a comparison of the evolutionary trajectories of CWSs in peripheral areas with those in central regions (Benner, 2021).

In non-metropolitan cities, CWSs foster increasing forms of collaboration among local stakeholders, combining work and leisure activities and thereby stimulating the local creative economy. Peripheral areas are establishing themselves as attractive work environments, capable of offering community-anchored spaces that promote cooperation and knowledge exchange within small clusters.

Research by Danko et al. (2024), based on data from selected cities in Central and Eastern Europe, suggests that coworking spaces in peripheral areas primarily contribute to local path renewal. This occurs through the integration of local stakeholders with the remote workers and digital nomads who frequent these spaces. These dynamics trigger forms of change capable of initiating an industrial and institutional co-evolution. In this way, coworking spaces

help to refocus local creative ecosystems, strengthening the competitiveness of the territory's micro-clusters.

The limited results of top-down urban regeneration policies and "quick fix" solutions highlight the risk of ignoring the local context. This occurs when policy transfer fails to adapt, relying instead on a geographically distorted understanding of creativity. Large-scale creative projects risk failing to connect effectively with the local environment or, worse, may stifle bottom-up initiatives, especially when there is a mismatch in scale between development policies and the characteristics of the peripheral context. Such projects can also exacerbate dependence on external funding and make the area vulnerable to unforeseen events. To foster the development of new innovation paths, small-scale interventions may be necessary to remove barriers before significant growth can be triggered.

6.2. Coworking in Rural Areas

Even though CWSs remain predominantly associated with urban centers—linked to traditional factors like population density, proximity to service providers, and public transport—growing work flexibility and technological advancements are changing this scenario. Several studies show that CWSs are emerging with increasing frequency in suburban and rural areas. In these locations, they play a crucial role in diversifying local economies and bridging the digital divide between urban and rural areas (Ananian et al., 2024).

Recent research indicates a growing spread of CWSs that extends from large metropolises to less urbanized areas, including rural and suburban regions. This phenomenon, accelerated particularly by the COVID-19 pandemic, reflects a shift in the preferences and needs of workers. This migration towards rural areas is driven by various key factors:

- **Economic and well-being advantages:** Prices for rent and services are more accessible, and the perceived quality of life is often higher due to less pollution and reduced traffic.
- **Social and community capital:** Small communities offer a strong sense of belonging, which fosters the creation of professional networks and synergies.
- **Institutional flexibility:** Local entities tend to be more agile in supporting and facilitating the establishment of new businesses.

This dynamic not only represents an option for professionals seeking alternatives to urban centers but also serves as a significant economic development opportunity for less-favored areas. The arrival of coworking spaces and their members (freelancers, entrepreneurs, etc.) can, in fact, stimulate the local economy, bringing new skills and job opportunities directly to rural communities. These communities would otherwise be at a disadvantage compared to cities, which already have a fertile ecosystem for innovation (Zhang, Liang & Yin, 2025).

The arrival of coworking in rural areas also offers an innovative solution to the problem of unused spaces. Due to progressive depopulation, many historic buildings and structures have been abandoned, at risk of falling into disrepair. The current trend, which sees a return of people and businesses to the countryside, makes it possible to repurpose these spaces as coworking locations. This revitalization not only gives new life to decaying buildings but also

helps create a sustainable, future-oriented work ecosystem. However, entrepreneurs interested in this model face a challenge: a lack of clear guidelines on how to best configure these spaces and what business models to adopt to ensure the initiative's success. More research and practical guidance are needed to support the establishment of these new work hubs (Thornton et al., 2023).

The rise of rural coworking is intrinsically linked to the growing acceptance of the "work from anywhere" concept. This trend, adopted by major companies like Siemens and Facebook following the COVID-19 pandemic (Choudhury, 2020), has encouraged a genuine exodus from urban areas to the countryside. This migration isn't just about space; it also offers a unique opportunity for differentiation. Rural coworking spaces can provide additional services, such as recreational activities and a deeper immersion in the local community, which their urban counterparts cannot replicate. However, this potential for revitalization (Engstler & Mörgenthaler, 2018) faces several unknowns. Little is still known about their effective implementation, from architectural structure to economic sustainability and profitability (Fuzi, 2015). Often, these spaces are managed by micro-enterprises founded by highly motivated entrepreneurs with limited resources and experience, who struggle to launch new initiatives on a large scale (Bähr et al., 2020).

Understanding the business models of rural coworking spaces is complex due to their variety and the limited information available in literature (Voll, Cordes & Henkels, 2021). This remarkable heterogeneity suggests greater diversification compared to urban spaces, with numerous categories and hybrid forms that make it difficult to define clear boundaries between the different types (Thornton et al., 2023). This diversity is primarily due to the unique environmental context of rural areas, which differs sharply from the homogeneous urban one (Ferreira et al., 2015). While urban areas are characterized by high population density and a consolidated entrepreneurial environment (Nakano et al., 2020), the business models of rural CWSs are strongly influenced by the specificities of the location, such as the presence of forests or waterways (Voll, Cordes & Henkels, 2021). This explains the variety of activities and the different types of clientele observed in these settings.

The approach of leveraging local resources and characteristics fits into the broader context of frugal and sustainable entrepreneurship, which aims to create social value and promote sustainability through its offerings (Hossain & Sarkar, 2023; le Loarne et al., 2022). An example of this trend, as previously mentioned, is the repurposing of historical and disused buildings. As stated by Wright (2018), "historic sacred places match well with coworking" (p. 57), as they often inherit useful features like accessibility, proximity to services, and a variety of internal spaces. Their reuse as coworking spaces prevents demolition, a common fate for these buildings if left vacant (Dähner et al., 2019).

In summary, integrating rural CWSs into unused buildings offers a dual opportunity: on one hand, it guarantees the sustainable reuse of abandoned structures, revitalizing entire town centers (Engstler & Mörgenthaler, 2018). On the other hand, when these spaces are housed in community-owned buildings, they bring new ideas and skills in innovation and digitalization to local communities (Prochazka & Wingartz, 2019). The potential of these hubs extends be-

yond simple workspace sharing. They act as connecting bridges between rural and urban areas, facilitating collaborations and exchanges (Avdikos & Merkel, 2019). Furthermore, thanks to their more diversified and pluralistic service offerings, typical of less populated areas (Marchegiani & Arcese, 2018), they transform into genuine social infrastructures. Although this model is still evolving and difficult to fit into a rigid taxonomy (Thornton et al., 2023), it is clear that rural coworking spaces represent a new and promising resource for the development and revitalization of less-favored areas.

6.3. Coworking Users in Rural Areas

The clientele of rural CWSs is notably diverse, and it can be analyzed based on several key characteristics, including work affiliation, motivation, and length of commitment. For example, there are employees of an organization who use the space on a continuous, medium- to long-term basis as their primary or supplementary workplace. There are also work groups or boards of directors who rely on these spaces only for specific events like workshops and meetings. Another category is made up of independent entrepreneurs, both freelancers and micro-business owners, who choose rural coworking as their permanent or partial workplace for the medium to long term. They are joined by independent service providers who use these spaces more sporadically for short-term needs. Finally, there is a group of users who frequent these places for non-strictly professional reasons, such as students, doctoral candidates, or "workationists" who combine work with vacation (Thornton et al., 2023).

The relationships between CWSs and their clients in rural areas are diverse, ranging from more traditional models to complex dynamics that intertwine professional and social aspects. Beyond a simple office rental (tenancy) or occasional use of services (service relationship), rural CWSs often offer the option of a membership, which grants access to events, information, and a network of locations. The community dimension is particularly relevant and hard to measure, emerging from personal connections and synergies that coworking companies actively encourage. In some cases, the governance model takes the form of a cooperative, where users become shareholders and autonomously manage the space (Co-Operation). In others, a phenomenon of Co-Creation occurs, where clients actively participate in creating and developing new value for the space itself. For their survival and growth, these spaces also rely on key partnerships. Strategic alliances are often formed with non-competing entities, such as local municipalities, or they opt for "coopetition," a form of collaboration between competitors that leads to mutual benefits. In rarer cases, a merger occurs (Ibidem).

6.4. Value of Coworking in Rural Areas

The fundamental resources for a rural coworking space are divided into three groups. First, site factors are crucial: the building's structure and its location largely determine the type of business model components. Proximity to nature is a tourism advantage, while a logistical location can simplify access and organization. Second, internal infrastructure is essential, particularly a robust and stable internet connection, which is often superior to what is typically available in the surrounding area. The decor and details, such as the use of recycled materials, can also signal a commitment to sustainability. Finally, the human and social resources derived from the community itself represent a fundamental asset for the growth and success of the CWS.

According to research by Thornton et al. (2023), the value of rural coworking can be divided into three main categories that outline their importance and functionalities. The first category is the Exchange Facilitation Platform. These spaces are designed to promote social and professional connection, often through organizing events and active community management. At the same time, they serve as (Re-)Presentation Platforms, offering clients a stage to showcase their projects, products, or services to a predefined audience or to casual visitors. The second category is Workplace-as-a-Service. This model offers a wide range of solutions: from freely accessible individual workstations (hot desks) to permanent offices, team rooms, or shared offices. Rural CWSs can also provide virtual offices, which offer a business address and mail handling services. Another option is Workation or Co-Living, which combines accommodation with workspaces, often including recreational activities and meals. The internal environment plays a crucial role: the presence of plants, well-kept furnishings, and an appealing design help create a stimulating atmosphere, while specific quality standards or distinctive elements reinforce the corporate image. Finally, the third category of value is linked to the External Environment. The value of a rural CWS is intrinsically tied to its location, which can offer access to a lake, a forest, or a unique, tranquil atmosphere—elements that sharply distinguish these spaces from their urban counterparts (Thornton et al., 2023).

Regarding revenue streams, the most common models include renting (selling the right to use a space for a specific time), Subscription Plans (allowing continuous access to services), and Pay-as-you-go (selling time-limited usage quotas). Pricing can be negotiated, fixed, or based on a future-based model (Ibidem).

7. Technological Aspects

7.1. Internet Connectivity

The most important feature of any coworking space is its internet connectivity. High-speed fiber optic networks, with symmetrical upload and download speeds exceeding 1 Gbps, ensure seamless use of cloud services, video conferencing, and file transfers.

Beyond pure speed, it is essential to ensure stability and service continuity. In a coworking space, even a few minutes of downtime can result in a complete standstill for dozens of professionals. For this reason, the principle of redundancy is adopted: at least two Internet connections from different providers, configured in failover. Through professional routers with load balancing capabilities, the network can dynamically distribute traffic or instantly switch to a secondary line in case the primary one fails.

In wireless access, enterprise WiFi systems with centralized control and real-time monitoring enable stable and secure connectivity for hundreds of simultaneous users and network segmentation (e.g., separate networks for members, guests, and Internet of Things devices). The configuration must also include secure authentication, WPA3 encryption, and real-time monitoring systems to prevent congestion or intrusions.

7.2. Electrical Infrastructure, Power Backup and Continuity

A coworking environment hosts an array of devices ranging from laptops to smartphones. To support this diversity, electrical infrastructure must be robust and versatile. Each workstation should provide multiple outlets, surge-protected circuits, and overload-safe wiring.

Modular power distribution (via floor boxes and columns) adds flexibility for reconfiguring spaces and it must be designed to handle high loads without the risk of overload. It is advisable to divide the power supply into multiple independent circuits and equip the system with properly rated residual-current and circuit breakers. The use of modular outlets with surge protection helps safeguard users' devices.

Additionally, the integration of USB-A and USB-C outlets with Power Delivery (up to 100W) allows members to charge both mobile devices and professional laptops, reducing reliance on personal adapters. They should support Power Delivery technology and be certified to ensure electrical safety.

No technological infrastructure can be considered reliable without an electrical continuity plan. Blackouts and voltage drops, even brief ones, can compromise ongoing activities and data. To mitigate these risks, UPS (Uninterruptible Power Supply) systems are used, connected to servers, routers, and critical devices.

UPS units provide immediate and stable power for a limited time sufficient to allow controlled shutdowns or the activation of backup generators. In large spaces, natural gas or diesel generators ensure continuity for hours or even days, keeping the workspace operational during extended outages.

From a technical perspective, it is crucial to properly size UPS capacity according to the total expected load. Preventive maintenance and remote monitoring systems should also be implemented to ensure full efficiency. A coworking space that never interrupts its services conveys reliability and professionalism.

7.3. Shared Tools

Despite digitalization, printing, scanning, and projection remain important. From a technical standpoint, the systems must support secure printing with user authentication, so that documents are released only in the presence of the requester. This feature protects privacy and prevents paper waste. Scanners should be able to digitize in various formats and send files directly to email or cloud storage.

For collaboration, coworking spaces integrate Full HD or 4K projectors, large LED displays, HDMI cables and wireless presentation tools such as Miracast or AirPlay.

With a brightness exceeding 3,000 ANSI lumens, it ensures visibility even in well-lit environments.

These solutions enable efficient meetings and support hybrid collaboration models.

7.4. Lighting and Energy Efficiency

Lighting is directly tied to productivity and user well-being. LED-based systems with high color rendering (CRI > 90), adjustable brightness, and tunable white technology (from warm white to cool white) create adaptive environments aligned with circadian rhythms and could be essential for professionals working in artistic and design fields. Integration with sensors ensures automatic adjustment, lowering both energy costs and visual fatigue.

Coworking operators increasingly combine these with renewable energy solutions such as photovoltaic systems, supported by smart inverters and battery storage, to enhance sustainability. A properly sized solar system can cover a significant portion of the daily electricity demand. With next-generation inverters and storage systems, the energy produced can be stored and used during peak hours. In addition to reducing costs, this choice enhances the coworking space's appeal to startups and companies focused on sustainability, creating a competitive advantage.

7.5 Technological Advantages

CWSs are not just physical locations for sharing desks and services. Their true strength lies in their ability to integrate advanced technologies that create added value for professionals and businesses. Unlike traditional offices, where technological solutions are often rigid and costly to update, coworking spaces are built with an innovation-oriented DNA, offering a digital ecosystem that amplifies work opportunities and lowers access barriers.

- **Enhanced Connectivity:** The article from Deskmag (2012) underlines that the most evident technological benefit of a coworking space is high-performance connectivity, of-

ten exceeding what a single professional or small company could afford independently. Symmetric fiber-optic connections, paired with enterprise-level WiFi networks, enable intensive use of cloud applications such as Google Workspace, Microsoft 365, software development platforms, or storage services like Dropbox and OneDrive. Cloud technologies are getting more central in every job as underlined in the article by Gartner (2025). This infrastructure drastically reduces latency and loading times, facilitating uninterrupted video conferences, rapid transfers of large files, and real-time access to remote databases. In practice, coworking spaces eliminate the “digital divide,” providing startups and freelancers with the same network quality found in large corporations.

- **Centralized Cybersecurity:** Another technological advantage concerns IT security, as detailed in the article by IEEE Spectrum (2023). Modern coworking spaces implement advanced firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and network segmentation—tools that would be costly for individuals or small companies to maintain. With centrally managed networks, users benefit from secure connections without needing to configure complex solutions themselves. The use of separate networks (for members, guests, and IoT devices) reduces the risk of unauthorized access. Many spaces also offer integrated VPNs or support for encrypted connections, ensuring that sensitive data and intellectual property remain protected. This focus on security not only safeguards members but also enhances the space’s reputation, making it attractive to companies handling confidential information.
- **Advanced Collaboration Technologies:** CWSs stand out for their extensive use of digital collaboration tools. Meeting rooms are equipped with high-definition video conferencing systems, interactive whiteboards, and co-creation software, allowing distributed teams to work as if they were in the same office. These solutions bridge geographic distances and reduce travel costs. In an era where remote working and hybrid models are increasingly common, coworking spaces provide a ready-made technological platform that connects members with colleagues and clients worldwide. Using shared professional tools also eliminates the need for costly individual investments: members gain access to enterprise-level infrastructure while paying only a proportional fee.
- **Automation and Smart Building Solutions:** Many CWSs are adopting building automation and Internet of Things (IoT) solutions. Presence sensors automatically adjust lighting and climate control, reducing energy waste and improving comfort. Smart thermostats and ventilation systems with air quality control create a healthy environment, a factor increasingly valued by workers. Technically, IoT integration allows real-time monitoring of workspace and meeting room occupancy. Collected data can be analyzed to optimize space management: underutilized areas can be reconfigured, while high-demand areas can be expanded or enhanced. This automation provides a dual benefit: lower operational costs for operators and a better experience for users, who enjoy consistently comfortable and available environments.
- **Simplified Access and Physical Security:** On the physical access side, coworking spaces implement digital entry control systems using RFID badges, QR codes, or mobile apps. These tools eliminate the need for physical keys, provide 24/7 access, and allow operators to monitor entry and exit in real time. Technology ensures security while offering

flexibility: new members can be enabled within seconds, and expired subscriptions can be automatically deactivated. Integration with management software also allows space usage to be linked with billing and reporting, streamlining administrative processes.

- **Scalability and Reduced Technological Costs:** A key advantage of CWSs is technological scalability. An independent professional working from home can rarely afford enterprise-level IT infrastructure, as detailed in the article by the International Workplace Group (IWG) (2022). In a coworking space, costs are shared among dozens or hundreds of users, making otherwise prohibitive solutions accessible. This model allows startups to grow without worrying about technological updates: network infrastructure, backup systems, collaboration platforms, and presentation tools are always up-to-date and ready to use. Users pay only for the time and resources they use, without long-term commitments.
- **Sustainability and Environmental Responsibility:** The article from Cisco Systems (2015) shows that the technologies implemented in CWSs benefit not only users but also the environment. The use of solar panels, LED lighting, and energy monitoring systems reduces emissions and consumption. Members indirectly enjoy a smaller ecological footprint, while operators can promote the space as a green workplace—a factor increasingly important to companies and professionals. The article from the U.S. Department of Energy (2021) shows a trend towards more environment friendly energy sources. From a technical standpoint, energy storage systems and intelligent load management allow for optimal use of generated energy, reducing dependence on the national grid and ensuring resilience during blackouts. These solutions give coworking spaces a distinctive market position, especially at a time when sustainability is also a competitive advantage.

7.6. Pros and Cons Summary

The technological infrastructure of coworking spaces brings with it a wide range of advantages. First and foremost, users benefit from a better overall experience: high-performance networks, professional tools, and reliable systems enhance productivity and satisfaction, allowing members to focus on their work without disruptions. Security is another significant strength, with segmented networks, VPNs, and advanced access control measures safeguarding both data and devices. Flexibility also plays a central role, thanks to IoT solutions and automation, lighting, climate, and even workspace allocation can be adjusted in real time, ensuring comfort and efficiency. Beyond functionality, coworking spaces foster digital communities and collaboration through integrated platforms and videoconferencing systems, creating opportunities for networking and teamwork that extend well beyond physical boundaries. Last but not least, scalability and cost efficiency make these spaces particularly attractive: by sharing infrastructure, users gain access to enterprise-level technologies that would be prohibitively expensive to maintain individually, while paying only for what they use.

Yet, despite these benefits, there are also challenges that cannot be overlooked. The most immediate drawback lies in the high initial costs required to set up such advanced infrastructures. Moreover, technology evolves rapidly, and hardware or software can become obsolete within a few years, demanding further upgrades. Another limitation stems from the strong

dependency on providers: internet services, cloud platforms, and IoT systems all rely on external vendors, which can pose risks in terms of reliability and costs. Security, although a strength when properly managed, can quickly turn into a weakness if misconfigured, exposing vulnerabilities that endanger both data and operations. Finally, the complexity of these systems requires specialized personnel and continuous maintenance, adding another layer of operational challenges.

8. Socio-Urban and Economic Aspects

8.1. General Aspects

Since the COVID-19 pandemic, CWSs have experienced exponential growth, not only in urban areas but also in suburban, rural, and coastal settings. This phenomenon, which has garnered significant attention at both academic and political levels, is driven by digital technologies, cloud-based networks, and the embrace of flexible and hybrid work practices by both employers and employees (Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto, 2024; Heinzl et al., 2021). While the internal operations of CWSs and their effects on work practices have been extensively studied, their relationship with cities and their interactions with the various urban areas in which they are located have only recently become a subject of research. Most studies focus on CWSs in urban contexts, where they are often situated in central, exposed, and attractive locations, integrating a well-designed interior with the surrounding urban space (Bounken, Kraus & Martínez-Pérez, 2020). Characteristically, CWSs tend to emerge in "vibrant" neighborhoods, defined by aesthetic and emotional intensity in "cool" city areas (cf. Waters-Lynch & Potts, 2017). These spaces combine the traditional desk with more informal and welcoming furnishings, such as "low-slung couches with decorative pillows" (Grazian, 2020, p. 997), creating a hybrid atmosphere.

The role of CWSs in the real estate market and their influence on gentrification processes are topics of growing importance. The rapid expansion of networks like WeWork can affect the local real estate market, generating socioeconomic effects, including an increase in rental prices, which accelerates gentrification processes (Merkel, 2015). For example, the opening of new WeWork spaces in underdeveloped areas of New York has suggested a consequent gradual increase in the rental prices for surrounding commercial properties and residential units (Babb, Curtis & McLeod, 2018). This dynamic reflects the growing trend since 2014 of investing capital in the coworking model to capitalize on opportunities offered by the real estate market (Wright, 2018). In this context, a key feature of some CWS business models is their ability to leverage the availability of unused or low-cost office spaces.

CWSs, perceived by some as a kind of "Airbnb for digital workers," offer not only workspaces but also non-work experiences, such as personal development programs and bold interior design. This has led to a touristification of work (Fast & Jansson, 2019, 2023), aligning with the industry slogan "a home away from home". This trend is particularly evident among digital nomads (Orel, 2021), for whom CWSs serve as anchoring environments (Bacevice & Spreitzer, 2023), offering hyper-connected workers opportunities for global encounters in stimulating contexts. These spaces are inherently ambiguous: they promote both remote work and recreational ease, acting as quasi-domestic environments for disembedded workers while also serving as experience-laden "destinations" for tourist-like workers. These post-digital trends, linked to territoriality, make CWSs true "sites of social power" that deserve careful analysis.

CWSs act as urban catalysts, generating direct effects at the community level and indirect effects at the organization-space level (Bednář, Danko & Smékalová, 2023). Their rise, fueled by remote work and digital nomadism, attracts communities of knowledge workers and knowledge-intensive business services (KIBS) (Mendez-Ortega, Micek & Malochleb, 2022).

These spaces facilitate both collaboration and competition through the interdependence among their users (Gandini & Cossu, 2019). While CWSs are often seen as collaborative environments, their non-linear development trajectories can foster competition rather than cooperation (Rozentale & Lavanga, 2014). This dynamic can push CWSs to evolve from a community-based, bottom-up approach to a profit-oriented, top-down one. The literature emphasizes that the impact of CWSs on the urban fabric differs significantly between metropolitan and non-metropolitan areas (Vogl & Akhavan, 2022). In metropolitan contexts, CWSs can create hubs of interaction and spontaneous aggregation. Additionally, a recent study found that workers in non-urban areas report higher levels of work-life balance compared to their counterparts in urban areas (Ciccarelli, Mariotti & Rossi, 2025).

8.2. Geography of Coworking Spaces

In the fields of geography and urban planning, researchers are particularly interested in the distribution patterns and local impacts of CWSs. These new shared work environments are changing the face of urban and non-urban geographies (Knapp & Sawy, 2021), not only in terms of the location of the spaces where they reside but also through their activities and potential spillovers in the broader region. The geographical distribution of CWSs in Europe and North America shows a clear concentration in metropolitan areas, particularly in or around urban centers. Factors driving this location include agglomeration economies, proximity to infrastructure and public transport, nearness to key institutions, the recreational needs of knowledge and creative workers, and the symbolic image of the urban center. In summary, the growth of creative and knowledge industries in large cities stimulates a rising demand for coworking spaces. However, small and medium-sized cities are becoming increasingly attractive for CWSs due to lower barriers to entry for new business ventures, which enhances economic development opportunities (Lin, 2021).

Western literature debates whether CWSs are predominantly concentrated in metropolitan areas or are helping to reduce spatial asymmetries by spreading to smaller urban centers. A recent study in China by Zhang, Liang & Yin (2025) provides evidence supporting both arguments, revealing a dual model of diffusion and agglomeration. In China, there is a dispersion of coworking, indicating the growth of these spaces in smaller cities and peripheral areas. However, most CWSs remain disproportionately agglomerated within demographically and politically significant large cities, especially in economically developed coastal regions. While CWSs in peripheral areas are often attracted by local advantages such as lower real estate prices, a better quality of life, and less pollution and congestion, in the Chinese context, the phenomenon is strongly supported at the institutional level. Many CWSs in China, particularly in smaller cities, rely significantly on political support and economic subsidies from local governments (Wang & Loo, 2017). This government-sponsored "coworking movement" is a distinctive factor that differentiates the Chinese model from the Western one. The concept of coworking in China differs significantly from the Western one, which idealizes these spaces as hubs for innovation, socialization, and entrepreneurial support. The current research debunks this notion, demonstrating that the function of Chinese CWSs is much more pragmatic. Instead of serving as platforms for socialization and knowledge sharing, many of these spaces operate as simple offices for profit. Consequently, their main clientele is not composed of "knowledge economy" professionals seeking networking opportunities, but rather a segment

of "non-professional users" who are more focused on prices, general conditions, and basic services. The research also found a surprising similarity in the user experience across geographically diverse cities, suggesting a standardization of services and a lack of functional specialization.

8.3. The Role of Coworking in Regional Development

The trend of CWSs expanding beyond major cities to meet the growing demand for local work options as an alternative to working from home (Foertsch, 2021), has created opportunities for small, independent coworking providers to compete with multinational corporations like WeWork and IWG, often by focusing on specific missions, such as promoting female entrepreneurship or supporting local social enterprises (Surman, 2013). Additionally, local universities and colleges are using their CWSs – especially fablabs – to build stronger connections with regional business communities.

Depending on their community and ecosystem, CWSs offer members opportunities for networking, co-learning, and idea exchange that not only foster their personal development but also generate positive spillovers for the broader local business community and society.

CWSs can enhance regional human capital by attracting and retaining skilled workers (Sobyra, Sigler & Charles-Edwards, 2022). Some have also gained a reputation for supporting traditionally disadvantaged entrepreneurs, such as ethnic minorities, women, and the LGBT community, thereby enriching the regional ecosystem (Howell, 2022).

As suggested by Fai et al. (2024), CWSs features can contribute to improving the six key "capitals" crucial for the recovery of depressed regions: physical (infrastructure/housing), intangible (innovation/ideas), human (skills/health), social (community relations/networks), financial (finance), and institutional capital (local leadership/capacity and capability) (DLUHC, 2022). These capitals are highly complementary; the presence of one often accompanies another. When they coexist in a given area, they drive the growth of agglomeration economies, innovation, and productivity. Within regional studies, these capitals are considered the core of strong regional innovation ecosystems (Grandstrand & Holgersson, 2020). Regions with a strong initial endowment of these "capitals" benefit the most, as they already possess robust entrepreneurial and financial networks along with technological capabilities. This cumulative process, however, can exacerbate regional inequalities. The research by Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto (2024), a qualitative study conducted through interviews and focus groups with managers, coworkers, policymakers, and other regional stakeholders of coworking spaces in three English provinces, suggests that CWSs provide opportunities to nurture and stimulate the "six capitals" in a bottom-up manner. The authors argue that CWSs should be seriously considered in future regional policy formulation, given the context of a new world of work and its organization. Furthermore, because CWSs in suburban and rural areas and small towns can be integrated into local realities, they have significant potential to be important placemaking agents, leading, shaping, and distributing local growth.

Remote, flexible, and hybrid work arrangements constitute new work modalities that have a significant spatial impact on, for example, the location of work, physical and digital infrastruc-

ture, and sustainability, as well as implications for regional policies. Due to their heterogeneous nature, CWSs can facilitate networking, collaboration, co-learning, and knowledge-sharing among members, while also fostering community-building that extends beyond the physical space. For this reason, the micro-ecosystem of a CWS has been compared to that of much larger territorial innovation clusters (e.g., Fiorentino, 2018, 2019).

The growing interest of local authorities in incorporating CWSs into regional urban planning and economic development strategies is a positive step. In Ireland, for example, the potential of CWSs to assist rural development and promote a more equitable economic distribution has been explicitly recognized in key national policies (Rural Development, Policy, 2021-2025; Foreign Direct Investment Strategy, 2021-2024; National Remote Work Strategy).

CWSs can offer a "bottom-up" approach to local regeneration, but careful consideration is required. Policymakers should analyze the type of spaces to attract, the goals of their owners, and the mix of potential coworkers. This underscores the need for regional metrics on the number, type, and mix of local CWSs, which could be collected and analyzed by a funded regional office acting as a "CWS network organizer" (Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto, 2024).

Despite their potential, some scholars express concern that many CWSs function primarily as a means for private real estate owners or multi-location companies to accumulate new rental income from urban real estate, rather than genuinely fostering innovative communities (Fai, Tomlinson & Barzotto, 2024). This raises questions about whether CWSs unintentionally act as a cover for exploitative and precarious employment practices, particularly as large companies use them as satellite offices for temporary and contract workers. A study in Shanghai and Shenzhen, for instance, found little evidence of knowledge-sharing or networking within these reconfigured office spaces. These CWSs offered few rental advantages to clients and were leased by large companies as satellite offices to house temporary and contract workers, consistent with the trend of work outsourcing and corporate risk reduction (Fu, Li & Li, 2023). Cases of this kind highlight the power asymmetries at play, which can benefit companies at the expense of developing local interests. However, it is noted that large CWS corporations are less interested in rural, coastal, or smaller provincial locations due to lower profitability, which creates an opening for local, mission-driven providers.

In conclusion, flexible and hybrid work arrangements, including the use of CWSs, are fundamentally reshaping urban and non-urban geographies (Knapp & Sawy, 2021). They are not merely physical spaces offering low-cost, flexible workstations; they are dynamic environments that can foster networking, co-learning, and idea exchange, with positive spillover effects for the wider business community and society at large.

8.4. Urban Dynamics

The urban dynamics of coworking spaces are a central theme in recent research, with a focus on understanding the key factors that influence their location and spatial structure within cities.

The key location factors for CWSs are consistent with those identified in the literature on business services. These include population density, accessibility to public transportation,

proximity to major knowledge institutions and knowledge-intensive services (KIS), as well as the availability and cost of buildings (Shearmur & Alvergne, 2002; Di Marino et al., 2021). Furthermore, some research indicates that certain CWSs are strategically located in residential areas, regardless of their centrality, which supports the idea of these spaces as "proximity workplaces" situated close to where workers live (e.g., Hölzel, Kolsch & de Vries, 2022).

Within metropolitan areas, the primary drivers for CWS location are the concentration of commercial activities and services, proximity to research centers and public transit, and overall convenience. At a more local scale, other factors also play a crucial role. These include the identity and reputation of the urban district (Babb et al., 2018), the multifunctionality of the area (e.g., Di Marino et al., 2018), and the presence of walkable and cycling-friendly services (Stam & van de Vrande, 2017).

The growth and diffusion of CWSs have the potential to significantly impact the local and community fabric. A vibrant CWS, for example, can become a new source of foot traffic and customers for struggling high streets, revitalizing surrounding shops, restaurants, and other businesses. By reducing commute times, these spaces also contribute to decreased traffic congestion and harmful emissions, yielding benefits for public health and the environment (Ross & Ressa, 2015). Moreover, CWSs can alter local energy consumption patterns, as coworkers share energy and air conditioning more efficiently within a single shared space (Mariotti, Akhavan & Di Matteo, 2021). Some CWSs owners also engage in local regeneration initiatives, collaborating with business improvement districts, schools, and charities.

CWSs also invest in unused commercial buildings or former factories due to their low cost, in some cases becoming levers for the redevelopment of areas that are losing their economic vitality (e.g., Bednář et al., 2021).

A crucial aspect for CWSs is access to transportation. CWSs are generally well-connected to both public transport and shared-mobility systems, and they are part of built environments that promote active modes of transport like walking and cycling (e.g., Di Marino et al., 2021).

Furthermore, CWSs can play a key role in consolidating local entrepreneurial ecosystems. By strategically positioning themselves near suppliers and partners and engaging in local collaborations, often within the same building or neighborhood, these spaces help to strengthen and develop existing cultural or creative clusters (e.g., Huang et al., 2020).

To understand the territorial positioning of CWSs, the literature draws on various theoretical approaches, as summarized by Brouwer et al. (2004). The neoclassical approach assumes that economic actors are rational. From this perspective, CWSs choose their location to optimize factors like accessibility, maximizing economic efficiency. The behavioral approach, in contrast, focuses on the internal operations and preferences of the organization. Lastly, the institutional approach conceptualizes actors as part of broader social and cultural networks, considering the influence of regulatory, governance, and business frameworks.

These models are not mutually exclusive. A location can be profitable (neoclassical criterion), meet specific requirements (behavioral criterion), and possess aesthetic and cultural qualities

that enhance the sense of place and institutional attachment (Wardner, 2012; Tuan, 1977; Ananian et al., 2024). This "sense of place" is an increasingly important factor.

Beyond these theoretical frameworks, the literature suggests that CWSs have developed new strategies in response to post-pandemic challenges. They have adjusted membership fees for vulnerable members (Leducq, 2021; Mayerhoffer, 2021), created online services like networking events (Manzini-Ceinar & Mariotti, 2021), and upgraded their facilities to meet the needs of a new corporate clientele (Mayerhoffer, 2021). These adaptive strategies suggest a strong place attachment for some of these spaces.

Finally, the rise of hybrid work (Pajevic & Shearmur, 2020) is forcing downtown areas and districts with high public transport accessibility to compete with emerging business hubs and suburban shopping centers, which offer higher car accessibility.

The case study of Montreal (Ananian et al., 2024) illustrates the evolution of the city's coworking ecosystem, which started slowly in the early 2000s and took off around 2014. Although the pandemic appears to have slowed this progression, the number of spaces still increased from 14 to over 60 in a single decade. To survive the crisis, CWSs adopted various strategies, such as collaborating with other spaces and local stakeholders to offer new services, including multi-location work options. Another key strategy was expanding into suburban areas, a trend the study confirms is on the rise. Accessibility and centrality are important determinants of CWS location. While some spaces emphasize a strong "sense of place" and attachment to the community, the data suggests that CWSs remain primarily businesses where people go to work. Creating a welcoming environment is part of the business model, but community engagement can vary, focusing more on the internal network than on the neighborhood. Nonetheless, the study supports the idea that CWSs can help revitalize urban centers by providing spaces and opportunities for self-employed workers and companies. As the authors state: "*They provide an alternative to working from home or working in an office: as such, they may be part of the solution to the hybrid work conundrum faced by many organizations*" (Ananian et al., 2024, p. 11).

A recent study by Lan and Feng (2025) in the Tokyo metropolitan area explored the use of remote work centers, analyzing how the transportation factor influences workers' choice between home, the traditional office, and CWSs. Based on 485 valid questionnaires, the research revealed that workers prefer to use these spaces for tasks requiring greater effort, teamwork, and longer durations (4-6 hours or more). Willingness to travel to a remote work center decreases as travel time increases. It was also found that women and individuals with higher incomes are more likely to use these types of spaces. Preferred modes of transport vary by income: low-income workers opt for active transportation (e.g., walking or cycling), while high-income workers choose public or private transport. These findings provide important insights for urban planners, helping them shape policies that promote the use of these spaces within the hybrid work culture.

8.5. Territoriality

Organizational territoriality, defined as the spatial practices of coworking companies (Brown, Lawrence & Robinson, 2005; Brown, 2009), is a key lens for understanding these spaces. According to Fast (2024), CWSs can be viewed as elite territories closely linked to gentrification and the experience economy. The latter promotes an aesthetically intense and vibrant urban life centered on a fascination with novelty and cultural differences.

The territoriality of CWSs unites and reinforces the cultural currents of the post-digital, post-work, and post-tourism eras (Fast & Jansson, 2024). Their "post-digital workstyles" are closely connected to post-tourism and urban space politics, as they attract some groups while excluding others. The dual nature of CWSs—as both productive spaces and "post-work" locations that encourage disconnection—makes them engines of an ongoing "touristification of work" (Fast & Jansson, 2024, p. 8). The digital nomad is the most emblematic example of this trend.

The notion of "post-tourism," coined by Feifer (1985), reflects the growing role of digital images in travel experiences. In this context, CWSs become part of an urban "hospitality ecosystem", offering clients a sense of being "hosted" in an attractive destination (Grazian, 2020). Digitalization has reshaped urban spaces, not only by expanding CWSs but also by transforming hotels, cafes, and restaurants into hybrid work environments. Similarly, entire tourist destinations are repositioning themselves to attract "workationers."

The territorial and political consequences of these social processes are ambiguous. The location of CWSs often follows a market-driven logic, concentrating where there is a greater opportunity to attract the right entrepreneurs. However, a distinction exists between *entrepreneurial-led* and *community-led* spaces (Avdikos & Merkel, 2019), with the former tending to integrate into business ecosystems rather than neighborhoods, potentially creating barriers to access for those who cannot afford the fees.

An example of this ambiguity is the "hipster economy" (Gerosa, 2024), where digital startups and innovation hubs (often in CWSs) coexist with artisanal businesses. In this context, CWSs reinforce a cultural order that views the ability to disconnect and consume "analog" and "authentic" services as a sign of post-digital and post-tourist privilege.

Fast & Jansson (2024) conclude that, at the intersection of these three dynamics (post-digital, post-work, and post-tourism), CWSs emerge as a "*humanized comfort zone in a digitally entangled working-culture that may otherwise feel intrusive, meaningless, and hostile*" (Fast & Jansson, 2024, p. 10). Despite their ambiguous role, their impact on issues of inclusion and exclusion is significant, raising questions about their capacity to challenge phenomena such as surveillance capitalism and data colonialism. While CWSs are often praised for their social dimension, it is important to recognize that these benefits can be co-opted by commercial interests (Zhang, Liang & Yin, 2025).

9. Socio-Relational Aspects

9.1. Promoting Interactions

There have been significant changes in how knowledge workers interact and collaborate. CWSs foster greater innovation and efficiency by allowing the best people for a particular project to quickly and conveniently come together. They also break down social barriers and connect individuals into supportive networks, as they are shared by people who don't typically work for the same organization. This not only leads to increased innovation, work efficiency, and collaboration but also provides members with emotional support, reduced alienation and isolation, and an improved work-life balance, which in turn leads to greater productivity, new products, and project opportunities (Orel & Dvouletý, 2020).

By combining work and social spaces, coworking environments aim to establish community-based social relationships among members, thus facilitating joint work, knowledge sharing, and the generation of new ideas and business opportunities. Consequently, CWSs are often regarded as microclusters that attract highly skilled professionals, new businesses, and investors, thereby contributing to local innovation and creativity (Zhang, Liang & Yin, 2025).

9.2. The Human Need for Community

The human need for collaborative communities is not a new phenomenon. Similar to modern CWSs, early, homogeneous communities existed in Renaissance Florence. Here, artisans, including painters and sculptors, worked together in interdisciplinary workshops, known as "botteghe" (Formica, 2016; Ceccarelli, 2008). Centuries later, in 19th-century Paris, French and foreign artists lived in communal spaces, creating similar collaborative environments (Timm-Bottos & Reilly, 2015). At the same time, comparable hubs for writers and creatives could be found in Parisian cafés and the Cabaret Voltaire in Zurich (Moriset, 2014). These spaces connected artists, helping them develop new styles and expressions. A similar environment was The Writers Room in 1970s New York, a space explicitly designed for writers' cooperation (Jones, Sundsted & Bacigalupo, 2009). These early models primarily aimed to provide a physical space for collective work.

In the late 20th century, with the rise of personal computers and the internet, cafes began to update their infrastructure to attract off-site workers needing a computer and a stable connection (Salvador, Sherry & Urrutia, 2005). The Electronic Café in Seoul (1988) and The SFnet Coffeehouse Network in San Francisco (1991) were pioneers in this trend, offering pay-as-you-go access to fixed computers (Liff & Lægren, 2003). While serving as temporary work environments for remote individuals, these early internet cafés became largely obsolete with the development of portable laptops in the late 1990s and early 2000s (Kellerman, 2009). However, they continue to be a presence in less developed countries today (Li et al., 2014).

The portability of electronic devices spurred the development of a new office space model. In 1989, Regus established the first hot-desk space in Belgium, allowing mobile professionals to share workspaces and conference rooms (Virginia & Colin, 2001). This, along with similar on-demand services, accelerated the adoption of non-territorial workspaces (Sullivan, 2017).

Parallel to these technological and social shifts, a need for more specialized, community-driven spaces began to grow. This led to the emergence of creative hubs and social innovation centers (Toivonen, 2016). The C-Base in Berlin, which opened in 1995, is considered a precursor to modern CWSs (Lindtner, Hertz & Dourish, 2014). Operating as a hackerspace for a homogeneous community of tech enthusiasts, it fostered user-led innovation. Although it's considered the world's first modern hackerspace, some authors mention a smaller, antecedent community in Michigan, USA, that began experimenting with new technologies at Grand Valley State University in 1994 (Dousay, 2017). However, one of the first shared work environments to truly embody the modern focus on diverse collaboration was Vienna's Schraubenfabrik, which opened in 2002 (Brübach-Schlickum, 2016). Though not self-identifying as a CWS, it served as a community center for entrepreneurs (Hartmann, 2016).

Until 2005, collaborative office environments were often linked to on-demand infrastructures that enabled office hoteling, a system of flexible, virtual space reservation (Davenport & Pearlson, 1998). The collaborative aspect was not central until the term "coworking" was coined. By building a sense of community and curating the "third place," these new workspaces with integrated social areas have co-created a sharing economy phenomenon (Bouncken & Reuschl, 2018).

9.3. The Social Experience of Co-presence

The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the widespread adoption of hybrid work practices, which combine in-office and remote work. Remote work influences the social relationships of workers, and a sense of isolation from the organization can emerge (e.g., Taskin, 2010). This situation can have negative work-related consequences at both the individual and collective levels (loss of motivation, disengagement, lower performance, higher employee turnover). In any case, a return to the traditional offices of the pre-COVID-19 era seems quite unlikely.

This shift in the "workscape" (Felstead et al., 2005, p. 16) was also made possible by the increasing efficiency of information and communication technologies (ICT), which allow for real-time collaboration without the need for physical co-location (Aroles et al., 2021).

Compared with more virtual work practices, large companies are turning to alternative spaces to restore body and materiality to work that is done outside traditional physical boundaries. CWSs provide a specific re-spatialization context for companies and are increasingly attracting the interest of firms and remote workers. Unlike home, these spaces offer remote workers a professional work and social environment, providing a possible solution to their isolation through face-to-face interactions and a collaborative setting (e.g., Blagoev et al., 2019).

These hybrid work models are likely to become even more prevalent in the future (Leclercq-Vandelannoitte, 2021), promoting a spatial redistribution of work (Hislop & Axtell, 2009). This is leading to the consolidation of a multi-located, hybrid space (Halford, 2005) where workers primarily move between the traditional office and their homes.

The re-spatialization of work in CWSs alters the social experience of remote workers. The re-spatialization of work refers *"to the process of spatial reconfiguration of work involving the*

hybridization of multiple work environments to accomplish one's professional activity" (Pfeffer, 2024, p. 59). This occurs through a dual co-presence: a remote co-presence with the company and mediated interactions with colleagues, a physical co-presence in the coworking space, with face-to-face interactions with coworkers who are not colleagues from their own company. The existing literature on co-presence does not provide sufficient insights to fully understand this hybrid, and even paradoxical, experience.

Developed from interactionist sociological approaches, the concept of co-presence is a cornerstone of sociological analysis and represents the most fundamental level of social interaction (Goffman, 1963). It refers to the reciprocal presence of individuals and their mutual influence, based on the idea that the presence of others shapes individual behavior (Grabher et al., 2018; Campos-Castillo & Hitlin, 2013).

The advancement of ICT has prompted researchers to reconsider the concept of co-presence to include mediated and virtual social interactions (Grabher et al., 2018). This evolution has introduced the concept of "electronic proximity", which allows individuals to be "here and elsewhere" at the same time (Le Nadant, Marinos & Krauss, 2018). Electronic proximity is defined as "*the extension of normal human sense perceptions through electronic mediations*" (Zhao, 2003, p. 124), making remote relationships and virtual co-presence possible, provided there's a reciprocal engagement between the actors. In light of these transformations, Campos-Castillo and Hitlin (2013) proposed an updated definition of co-presence as "*the degree to which one actor (1) perceives entrainment with a second actor and (2) sees the second actor reciprocating entrainment, where entrainment is a linear function of the synchronization of mutual attention, emotion, and behavior*" (2013, p. 171).

This redefinition of the concept of co-presence is crucial for understanding the social experience in non-traditional work contexts, such as telework, which corresponds to the exercise of a professional activity, in whole or in part at a distance and by means of ICT (Taskin, 2006).

Born in the 1970s, telework was initially associated with a fixed practice, often at home, before evolving towards more mobile and virtual modalities (Messenger & Gschwind, 2016). It is characterized by three essential elements: a spatial and/or temporal dispersion outside the premises of the employer, subcontractor, or client; the use of ICT (computers, email, and telephones); and the frequency of the arrangements (Pfeffer, 2024). This type of organization breaks the traditional units of space and time and influences the structure of work, particularly by modifying the employment relationship and the social interactions of remote workers, hindering face-to-face relationships (e.g., Hislop & Axtell, 2007). Consequently, the experience of relating to others is altered, both from a physical and psychological point of view (e.g., Sewell & Taskin, 2015), with a possible consequent sense of isolation, which constitutes the main disadvantage of telework (e.g., Kurland & Cooper, 2002).

The notions of distantiation and perceived proximity contribute to a more precise definition of the meaning of co-presence experienced by remote workers. Distantiation refers to the subjective experience of a loss of physical and psychological closeness to one's work environment, including colleagues, common spaces, formal and informal exchanges, and company culture. The intensity of distantiation can vary and is a function of the frequency of telework

and the degree of perceived isolation. It's essential to distinguish between two forms of isolation:

- Physical isolation: the absence of physical contact with the work environment and colleagues.
- Social isolation: the lack of support, understanding, and other social and emotional aspects of interactions.

Distantiation is characterized by both forms of isolation, with social isolation corresponding specifically to a dissatisfaction with the experience of social interactions (Taskin, 2010). Research on isolation and distantiation links to the literature on perceived proximity, defined as the subjective experience of closeness that an individual feels toward another person (Wilson et al., 2008; O'Leary et al., 2014). Consequently, remote co-presence in telework can oscillate between social isolation and perceived proximity. Research has identified several organizational factors that mitigate feelings of isolation and promote a sense of perceived closeness. Such practices emphasize shared values and identity, as well as the importance of communication and opportunities for collaborative interactions to limit the risk of isolation (Pfeffer, 2024).

CWSs were initially conceived as a solution to the isolation of freelancers and entrepreneurs. Their purpose was to allow for "working alone, together" (Spinuzzi, 2012) or even to work collaboratively (e.g., Scaillerez & Tremblay, 2019). These spaces offer an alternative to the traditional work environment, providing a physical and social context that teleworking from home often lacks (Petraglieri, Ashford & Wrzesniewski, 2019).

CWSs were initially defined by five fundamental dimensions—called the pillars of coworking—which include collaboration, openness, community, accessibility, and sustainability (Coworking wiki). These values not only form the foundation of the social experience within these spaces, but also highlight the themes of interaction, sharing, and reciprocity among members (Salovaara, 2015), which are essential for understanding co-presence in these environments.

Co-presence in coworking spaces is characterized by workers sharing the same physical space. This physical proximity facilitates encounters and interactions, which are often informal (Krauss, 2019). While the degree of social interaction can vary—from quick chats to genuine collaborations—it's the sum of these daily interactions that helps create a sense of community. However, physical proximity alone isn't always enough to trigger collaborative dynamics. Research has highlighted the crucial role of the organizational dimensions of coworking, leading to the concept of "organized proximity" (Rallet & Torre, 2004; Le Nadant et al., 2018). This concept, which is relational in nature, refers to the organization's ability to facilitate interactions among members. The importance of facilitators (such as coworking managers) is key to "*activating geographical proximity*" among members (Le Nadant et al., 2018, p. 127).

Co-presence in a CWS can fluctuate between social isolation and perceived proximity, depending on the experience of mutual presence among members. The level of engagement is

a matter of individual needs and choices. Research has highlighted the issue of coworker availability; while physically present, they may not always be willing or able to participate in social interactions or collaborative dynamics (Endrissat & Vandelannoitte, 2021). This lack of engagement can be attributed to a significant external social capital (e.g., a large professional network or loyal clients) or to working for a company outside the CWS.

An ethnographic study by Pfeffer (2024) conducted within two coworking networks introduced the notion of "hybrid copresence" to account for the experience of coworkers, defining it as *"the synthesis of experiences of social interactions lived simultaneously and associated with distinct organizational and spatiotemporal contexts"* (p. 74). The research revealed that the re-spatialization of work in these spaces generates a hybrid coexistence that can be experienced in four distinct ways:

- (Reinforced) isolation;
- Ubiquity;
- (Guilty) compensation;
- (Frustrated) refocusing.

The research analyzes the characteristics of each of these modes and the possible evolutions from one condition to another. CWS becomes a container for hybrid co-presence that involves distinct organizational spaces: the company (despite being far away), and an alternative physical workspace (the coworking space). The research findings highlight the crucial role of contextual factors associated with the company and the CWS, as well as the permeability of co-presence experiences between them. The crisis triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic forced numerous companies to adopt telework in an unplanned manner. Despite this lack of preparation, this period served as a large-scale experiment for remote work, accelerating its adoption.

The study suggests we view the re-spatialization of work as a network of interdependent spaces, connected by employee interactions, whether in-person or remote. In addition to the social isolation already recognized in the literature, the research identified three experiences of hybrid co-presence. Among these, ubiquity—the ideal state of hybrid co-presence—appears to be the most effective alternative for mitigating the risk of isolation for remote workers. However, it requires a symbiosis of all stakeholders: the employee-coworker, the company (through colleagues and managers), and the CWS (through coworkers and the space manager). Conversely, experiences of refocusing and compensation can create discomfort for employees due to their hybrid nature. While further research is needed to verify the long-term effects, the findings suggest that physical co-presence in a social environment alone is not enough to overcome the isolation associated with telework.

9.4. Work-Life Balance

Driven by rapid advancements in information and communication technologies, the search for an effective work-life balance has become critically important in the ongoing process of reshaping the ways and places of work. Recent literature has increasingly emphasized CWSs

as a potential solution to foster this balance by alleviating work-life conflicts and offering environments that promote the integration of work and leisure. Despite this growing interest, quantitative studies strictly focused on this domain remain limited (Ciccarelli, Mariotti & Rossi, 2025).

CWSs explicitly position themselves to promote a fundamental reconfiguration of the relationship between work and leisure, operating in a direction of integration rather than separation between the two domains. This ambition is underpinned by a pervasive rhetoric that claims to revolutionize working life. The values and aspirations of this ideology are often condensed into slogans that territorialise the coworking space, appearing in wall decorations, branded merchandise, or social media quotes: expressions like "Home away from home," "Do what you love," "More than a workplace," and "Thank God it is Monday" (Grazian, 2020) are key examples.

The coworking industry essentially promises "loveable work" (Sandoval, 2018)—work that seamlessly blends personal and professional values. In line with the slogan "more than just a workplace", many spaces offer programs such as mindfulness sessions, yoga, meditation, and similar spiritual activities, suggesting that self-care and personal well-being are integral to productivity. This vision aligns in part with the hope expressed by Gregg (2018), who argues that CWS operators share a desire for more meaningful work, actively playing with the constraints of the traditional work-week paradigm and producing different orientations toward time.

This ideology is situated within the broader debate on "post-work," which serves as an umbrella term "for imaginaries of a future society where work, as we have come to know it, no longer exists" (Fast & Jansson, 2024, p. 6). In such a scenario, automation and reduced working hours are expected to free up time for leisure, personal pursuits, community involvement, and well-being.

However, the discourse of integration raises critical questions. While hard work, ambition, and determination are in no way devalued by CWSs, the promise of a perfect fusion between life and work must be analyzed with caution. The attempt to internalize personal and wellness activities within the work sphere through dedicated programs may represent a form of incorporation of free time rather than its genuine liberation, thereby maintaining a society intensely focused on productivity.

10. Design and Psycho-Environmental Aspects

10.1. Coworking Spatial Characteristics

The evolving landscape of hybrid work necessitates a corresponding shift in the design of workplaces. Despite this need, the understanding of the spatial and environmental design of flexible workspaces remains a relatively limited area of research. Non-standard work forms and platform work have prompted much discussion on the governance of work contracts, but the materiality of workspaces has not been truly considered beyond health and safety issues (Johns et al., 2024). Few systematic analyses have been conducted on the spatial organization of CWSs, which are often treated as a phenomenon completely separate from the broader workplace context. The history of office architecture is marked by the continuous introduction of new concepts, each presented as innovative, productive, and convenient, with the aim of dismantling traditional routines. This tendency to repackage old ideas as significant innovations makes it necessary to examine the wider development of workplace design to critically evaluate the true novelty of concepts like coworking.

The core question is whether coworking represents a completely new type of workspace or merely reflects existing organizational norms (such as supporting collaborative relationships and prioritizing the user experience). What's certain is that contemporary workspaces are in a state of constant redevelopment, and there is not yet a definitive template for the networked office. "The lack of empirical research into the spaces and behaviours of coworking and the tendency for it to be considered in isolation make it all too easy to overestimate its potential innovations" (Privett, 2020, p. 212). To understand how the spatial strategies of CWSs are evolving, it is necessary to highlight some key themes in current workplace design trends: (a) Densification of corporate space; (b) Using space to promote desired behaviours; (c) Increasingly varied palette of settings; (d) Symbol/identity-rich environments; (e) Blurring typological boundaries; (f) Need to account for time and change (Ibidem).

Certain spatial characteristics are common to the majority of CWSs. In order of scale, starting from the building level, the most widespread situation is the preference for open floorplates, often featuring a light touch over architectural insertions. There is a noticeable reuse of non-office stock, such as former industrial or retail buildings. Moving down in scale to the overall zoning, settings are most often broadly clustered according to type, creating zones for different activities. In multi-floor spaces, social and meeting facilities are typically placed on the ground floor, or each floor has a large open-plan social area, usually near the main circulation (and often placed directly adjacent to the entrance). Circulation is typically simple, with clear sight lines to maximize ease of orientation. High levels of internal visibility and transparency characterize the interiors, whether they are open plan or extensively glazed. Spatial strategies like enlarged interstitial areas at the boundary between the internal and external space have been identified as a common feature in coworking and represent a clear departure from a traditional corporate reception area (Privett, 2020).

The great variability of CWSs design is evident in their physical layout. A conventional design typically features an open floor plan with shared workspaces to facilitate interaction. Com-

pared to traditional multi-tenant offices, CWSs offer more informal areas, such as coffee corners, a kitchen, meeting rooms, lounge space, and other informal areas (Weijs-Perrè et al., 2019). A typical space combines informal and creative areas with functional office spaces (Orel, 2015).

The size of a space is a strategic choice: smaller environments tend to foster a more cohesive community with stronger bonds, while larger ones offer a broader network of opportunities, albeit with weaker ties (Howell, 2022).

A key factor is the workstation type. According to Deskmag (2016), the average occupation density of CWSs is 130 square feet per desk (global mean), with a median figure of 100 square feet per desk. Many spaces offer "hot desks"—large areas with seating available on a "first-come, first-served" basis. The primary motivation for implementing hot desking is to reduce costs through space savings, which makes this configuration increasingly sought after by companies looking to maximize the use of their workstations. *"Hot desking by definition is a system in a work office where each space is available for each worker, rather than reserved for specific person, so it is possible for the same space to be occupied by different person along the day of week"* (Nurdin et al., 2024, p. 140). However, this spatial strategy seems to be linked to a lack of informal social interactions (Hirst, 2011).

Others provide dedicated desks at a higher fee, or even private offices. The choice among these options influences the frequency of social interactions and helps define the space's culture.

The development of CWSs suggests a move toward enclosure from their largely open-plan origins, an apparent privileging of collaboration, and the rise of the "hybrid" CWS with the introduction of private offices. The proportion of common areas seems to be decreasing. Although coworking's initial success was built on its open-plan layout, this configuration did not solve the issues associated with it. For this reason, many providers are now offering both open-plan workstations and private offices. This can be described as a hybrid model that blends some of the qualities of a more traditional serviced office with CWSs. When the percentage of private offices exceeds a certain threshold—a situation that typically occurs in larger spaces—it creates a scenario that seems contrary to the popular perception of CWS as a collaborative free-for-all. The trend toward private offices may suggest a prioritization of more clearly profitable spaces at the expense of social and collaborative areas that generate less value (Privett, 2020).

CWSs also vary in amenities, which can include furnishings, WiFi, printing, 24/7 access, and exercise equipment. Some even offer on-site lodging or childcare. Additionally, many coworking networks have multiple locations, offering independent workers the flexibility to choose where to work (e.g., Merkel, 2015). The types and characteristics of spaces typically found in CWSs are summarized in Table 2.

Type of space	Characteristics
OPEN PLAN WORKSTATIONS	Provide all necessary equipment/resources for individual work in an open-plan space; the most consistent feature is a relatively short run of two or three desks with no dividers in between desks or desk runs.
PRIVATE OFFICES	Enclosed space containing workstations and storage for one or more people, minimally furnished and unbranded to allow occupants to personalise space.
PHONE/FOCUS BOOTHS	Small, enclosed booths for individual short-term occupation.
MEETING ROOMS	Simple and minimally furnished, with wheeled or modular tables in larger rooms and at least one fully glazed wall; enclosed spaces designed for people to meet or learn together (conventional layout with chairs around a central table); technology provision consists of a simple wall mounted display.
INFORMAL MEETING SPACES	Small free-standing tables (round-four person tables or rectangular tables for up to ten people) and chairs in open plan space and semi-enclosed meeting booths (if they were not directly adjacent to a kitchen), located adjacent to at least one partition rather than in the centre of open plan space.
KITCHEN	Pantries, dedicated kitchen and breakfast bars, typically semi-enclosed with more than one point of entry, adjacent to either breakout or informal meeting space, located on primary circulation routes, providing shared seating either in the form of a high bench with bar stools or a large shared table.
BREAKOUT, LOUNGE SPACES	Domestic style furniture with a combination of sofas and chairs, side tables and area rugs, and either against a partition or in a corner.

Table 2 – Main types and characteristics of spaces within CWSs

Typically, CWSs implement Activity-Based Working (ABW), providing a complex of diverse spaces, each tailored for specific activities or operational modes. ABW was identified as the dominant strategy for organising open-plan coworking interiors. Introduced in 1985, this is arguably not particularly spatially innovative, although global take-up has been variable. Nevertheless, the increasing demand for private offices is gradually reducing this diversity in some CWSs, which are evolving towards a more homogeneous and less varied structure. Below are a number of spatial strategies common to CWSs:

- Patterns of zoning and adjacencies
- Relationship of communal areas to the entrance
- Provision of attractors in key locations
- Fluid interface between external and internal spaces
- Reprogrammable rather than mono-functional space
- Hybrid elements
- Some common patterns within individual settings

- Low differentiation between open plan settings
- Informal and domestic references
- Use of interior design elements to support identity/branding strategy

Privett (2020) highlighted seven spatial features of CWSs linked to specific work experiences (Table 3). A branded space is essential, as all CWSs must present a unique identity and culture to attract prospective members. Designing for interaction is a consistent theme, whether it's for building community or for more work-related, "generative" interactions. The space's ability to adapt to change is also important, which can be seen in multi-functional and reprogrammable areas, or the ability to quickly alter partitions so member organizations can scale up or down. Permeability and hybrid elements are key for offering a range of services to increase revenue and get as many potential members as possible through the door. Finally, user-centeredness is a recurring theme: spaces and services are consistently tailored to the needs of their members, with values, services, broader offerings, and spatial organization all customized for the community.

Aspect	Characteristics	Experience-related element
1. Branded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expression of identity • Symbolism • Distinctiveness • Marketing • Curating community 	Facilitating the creation of distinctive identity/culture that members could identify with
2. Flexible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-use • Changing populations • 24/7 use • User control • Flexible planning • Loose fit/Polyvalence 	Adapting to member needs
3. Permeable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationship to city • Connected to externalities • Role of "gatekeeper" • Microclusters • Open access 	Feeling of inclusivity by virtue of open access and partnership with external business to add value
4. Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community • Social capital • Network building • Curated events • Space around events 	Add value by facilitating social connections
5. Generative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge exchange • Iterative capacity • Diverse populations • Visibility • Attractors • Serendipitous encounters 	Add value by facilitating growth of networks
6. User-centred	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service provision • Bottom-up planning • Member oriented • User control 	Tune space and service to the needs of members

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitation 	
7. Hybrid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital/Physical • Learning • Cultural events • Hospitality • Retail 	Expand the offer beyond simple provision of work-space to a more hospitality-oriented offer

Table 3 – Link between spatial characteristics of CWSs and member experience (adapted from Privett, 2020)

CWSs seem to emphasize spatial configurations and strategies to bring people together, while also focusing on autonomy in space use, flexibility, and a high-quality user experience. However, there is a lack of in-depth research exploring how these values are manifested in the physical space, and how or where interactions actually take place. The role of space in interactions within CWSs has been largely underestimated. While the importance of the host in nurturing this aspect is undeniable, spatial affordances and design elements still play a crucial role. Limited analyses have been conducted on the spatial strategies employed by CWSs to promote interaction, and no structured mapping of interaction patterns has been carried out (Privett, 2020). Several dimensions of physical space have been identified as influencing interactions within organizational contexts, with a particular focus on overall spatial configuration, visibility, movement, and proximity. Communication between colleagues decreases rapidly with distance, with very few spontaneous interactions occurring beyond 30 meters (the so-called "Allen curve"; Allen, 1977), making proximity a significant factor in communication patterns. There is, therefore, a strong relationship between communication and physical distance, where vertical separation typically has a more negative effect than horizontal separation (e.g., Kabo et al., 2015). By using "attractors", visibility, and managing movement flows, the overall spatial context creates the potential for continuous serendipitous encounters. However, interaction is not solely a function of physical distance, highlighting the social norms that govern proximity and interactions between people.

Innovative office design is the cornerstone of modern CWSs. The most effective environments are meticulously conceived to increase productivity, foster collaboration, and promote well-being. A significant emerging trend is the proliferation of CWS locations featuring zoned areas. These spaces move beyond traditional open-plan layouts by integrating designated zones for individual focused work and team-based collaboration, complemented by communal areas reserved for breakout sessions and relaxation. In the pursuit of truly productive coworking environments, private spaces are becoming a fundamental, fixed component. Open-plan configurations are consequently evolving toward shared spaces that offer greater autonomy, such as specialized "quiet pods," which are essential for deep concentration.

The study by Pan et al. (2025), conducted in a CWS in London, investigated the association between workspace design and the behavior and preferences of its occupants, building a data-driven model to predict workstation occupancy in relation to design characteristics. The dataset included sensor-detected occupancy, on-site measured and simulated environmental variables, computed spatial metrics, and human-voted preferences. The combined effects of thermal comfort (temperature and humidity), visual comfort (artificial light and exposure to natural light), and spatial metrics (connectivity and isovist field) were analyzed to understand their overall impact on space occupancy and user preferences. The study's objective was to

present a data-driven analytical framework for evaluating the utilization of flexible workspaces and to demonstrate predictive capabilities by identifying associations between environmental and spatial variables and occupancy patterns, offering a tool to guide evidence-based design and manage flexible workspaces. The analysis highlights the importance of spatial and environmental metrics, revealing that areas or workstations with high spatial connectivity and wider visual fields tend to attract more occupants. In addition, environmental variables like temperature and natural light level show positive effects on increasing workstation occupancy.

The results of a previous study by the same research group (Pan et al., 2023) showed that shared working areas are significantly preferred and utilised for communication and general working when they are located near windows or in more open, connected, and visible locations.

Conversely, semi-enclosed spaces—which offer less visibility and greater privacy—are preferred for focused working. For hybrid working, the most valued feature was the flexibility offered by multi-use opportunities within the space. These findings offer data-driven insights for human-centric space planning and the design of future office spaces, particularly in the context of hybrid working setups, hot-desking, and co-working systems.

The research by Weijs-Perrée et al. (2019) analyzed the preferences for spatial characteristics by coworking users through the administration of a questionnaire completed by 219 respondents from 25 CWSs in the Netherlands. The results show that the main motivations for coworkers to work in a CWS were the need to have a workspace outside their home that would allow them to work at an affordable price in a stimulating work environment. The most important features in choosing a specific CWS were accessibility and the atmosphere/interior of the spaces. These results provide coworking owners or managers with useful information on user preferences, by offering spaces with good accessibility both by private transport and public transport, a semi-open layout, and welcoming interiors.

The application of artificial intelligence (AI) is also becoming increasingly interwoven with office interior design. AI-enabled systems are not only able to automate desk and amenity reservations but also manage aspects like Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning control (HVAC). Lighting can be personalized for maximum productivity, while automated heating systems can reduce carbon footprints and make spaces more eco-friendly.

10.2. Space Aesthetics

Aesthetics is the least explored dimension in organizational studies, referring to our sensory reactions to a physical environment and its elements. It typically includes specific design features such as colors, materials, artwork, and overall design. This is distinct from the broader field of organizational aesthetics, which emphasizes the materiality of daily routines and studies how individuals and groups operate within organizations by listening to their feelings, desires, tastes, talents, and passions (Strati, 2010). The aesthetic dimension of an organization provides a way to understand organizational life based on immediate sensory reactions (sight, hearing, smell, and touch) to its material components (products, physical environments, and

material practices). Beyond simply “beautifying” the physical environment, aesthetics can also inspire and motivate (Baldessarelli, Stigliani & Elsbach, 2022).

Most existing research in this area falls within the field of environmental psychology. Aesthetics can be used to create specific sensory experiences (Heft & Nasar, 2000) and is believed to foster a general sense of belonging by generating a unique atmosphere and meaning over time. This is because people form emotional bonds with the objects around them. Aesthetics has also been linked to place attachment, influencing individual experiences and creating shared interactive experiences (Elsbach & Bechky, 2007). Furthermore, workplaces that are cognitively and perceptually stimulating have been conceptually associated with enhanced creativity, although the evidence is scattered (Haner, 2005). It has also been found that enriched workplaces, compared to those with minimal decoration, can positively influence employee concentration, engagement, satisfaction, and perceived productivity (Haslam & Knight, 2010; Nieuwenhuis et al., 2014).

The physical environment can be viewed as a system of non-verbal communication that conveys information about the organization, its values, culture, and expected behaviours (Duffy, 2008). From this perspective, the symbolic functions of space can be seen as a powerful tool for strategic management (Skogland & Hansen, 2017). The increasing recognition of this power, combined with the rise of the aesthetic in everyday life, has been argued to have resulted in an "aestheticization" of the workplace in which the whole workspace is constructed as the embodiment of the desired culture (Khanna et al., 2013; Skogland and Hansen, 2017).

Design is a crucial tool for creating a strong, unique identity in an increasingly crowded market. The aesthetic presentation of the space is not merely decorative; it's a key differentiator, symbolically expressing the brand's identity while also providing members with a level of architectural quality they typically couldn't afford on their own. However, a potential tension must be managed: the coworking brand's need for a distinctive market identity must be balanced against the need for space and identity from its members. Some spaces address this by treating the interiors as a "blank canvas," allowing members to characterize them with their personal touches. Ultimately, the space needs physical flexibility to accommodate continuous change. For this reason, a coworking space's design is never truly finished; instead, it remains in a state of "perpetual beta" (Marlow, 2011)—constantly evolving and improving.

At first glance, CWSs may seem similar, bringing together a mixed group of entrepreneurs and atypical workers in a shared common environment. However, there is a remarkable variety of spaces that differ in resources, atmosphere, and other distinctive criteria. Consequently, for a founder, the choice of a space is not dictated solely by its location, but also by how its characteristics fit the specific needs of its target. Different design elements of these spaces can significantly influence the overall experience of their users.

Today's employees expect much more from their workplaces. Beyond traditional comfort, they want designer furniture, dedicated rest areas like napping pods, and even free barista coffee. These perks are no longer seen as simple extras but as fundamental requirements for a modern work environment. Many companies and CWSs like Google and WeWork are integrating unusual design elements and luxury amenities into their offices. This includes climbing

walls, slides between floors, and theme-park-style meeting rooms, which make the environments more dynamic and fun. Organizations implement these "creative spaces" to attract future employees, to express their innovative corporate culture, and to increase communication and creativity among their personnel (Thoring et al., 2020). It seems that "great workplace design drives creativity and innovation" (Gensler, 2016, p. 3).

Based on the spatial analysis of CWSs conducted by Privett (2020), examining both floor plans and interior décor, it can be stated that these spaces have moved away from their DIY roots. Compared to greater initial uniformity, they are now characterized by increasing diversity, which is an expression of a more mature market. This diversity can also be observed even within spaces belonging to the same network, suggesting that the most important factor in terms of overall allocation is the need to tailor the space to the local member community.

A fundamental aspect of CWSs is the overall atmosphere, or "vibe". While some environments are designed to replicate the serious and professional appearance of a traditional office, many others aim to reflect the culture of "Silicon Valley" startups, including features such as ping-pong tables, beanbag chairs, and various types of games.

It is possible to identify the following main styles (Privett, 2020):

- "Classic" style: exposed services, raw materials, reclaimed furniture and timber and plants all widely associated with the popular image of coworking;
- Minimalist corporate: white and clean, often with the aim of providing a neutral background for member activity;
- Polished corporate: an exclusive aesthetic that is more typically associated with corporate space or high-quality business lounges;
- Minimal intervention: simply occupying existing space with minimal intervention and simple, low budget office furniture;
- Local low budget: artwork and murals with local references, a range of contract and non-contract furniture, plants, feature lighting, minimal interventions to the existing place;
- High low budget: drawing on the exposed structure/warehouse aesthetic associated with coworking, but making structural insertions/design statements on a larger scale with higher quality fitting and furnishings;
- Work as play: a broadly playful approach, highly distinctive visual identity drawing on bright colours and graphics/themes of "fun", games tables or over-scaled objects;
- Hospitality space: sophisticated aesthetic drawing on hospitality environments (hotel lobbies, bars or urban cafés for style references).

The most frequent themes can be grouped into: industrial/heritage (exposed structure and services, with materials such as brick, concrete and reclaimed timber accompanied by vintage objects and non-contract furniture), home (introduction of domestic references such as rugs and non-contract furniture, centrality of the kitchen, large shared tables acting as symbolic heart), and localism (integrating references to local context, incorporating traditional or local materials, and the use of traditional building forms) (Privett, 2020).

Although digital connectivity is a precondition for being a member of a CWS, the full use of these spaces is often linked to the presence of analog technology (such as typewriters, vinyl records, or analog cameras) and activities that promote disconnection (like board games or yoga). These elements become an emblem of CWSs, enhancing their creativity and appeal. Indeed, CWSs are full of "analog spatial markers" (e.g., stickers, painted signage) that coexist with digital technology, offering a mix of connectivity and disconnection. This kind of *"old-world nostalgia for the vintage and retro"* is a distinctive feature of the post-digital aesthetic (Humayun & Belk, 2020, p. 635).

That mix of elements, which creates a distinctive atmosphere, is further shaped by the influence of contemporary visual trends. In his ethnographic study in Manhattan, Grazian (2020) found that CWSs are "design-intensive settings" whose aesthetic is heavily influenced by popular Instagram trends, featuring colourful layouts, inspirational signs, and "low-slung couches with decorative pillows" (p. 997). This design is intended to foster a sense of cultural identity and spatial order among like-minded workers who seek a comfortable yet disciplined place to work.

In today's office, work is equally carried out and narrated through aesthetics. The visual and textual representations of contemporary workspaces popularized by design and architecture firms, social media, and pop culture have a major influence in how we conceive work, how we value it, and how we perform it. Jalili's (2021) study analyzes office aesthetics—a concept that denotes the visual homogeneity in the architecture, interior design, and supplies found in offices worldwide, including CWSs. Jalili argues that this uniformity is closely linked to the prevailing narratives surrounding work within the current neoliberal system, which tend to perpetuate excessive, meaningless, and precarious labor that is often gendered and racialized. This idealized narrative, often championed by architectural firms and amplified by social media, serves to obscure the reality of labor that is frequently precarious, alienating, and fundamentally unequal. From this perspective, the promotional depictions of open-plan offices harbor profound dissonances. Although these spaces are rigorously marketed as boosters of collaboration and productivity, empirical studies indicate they are often experienced as noisy and distracting environments, resulting in a negative impact on workers' well-being and concentration. Furthermore, the highly-celebrated "flexibility" within these spaces is seldom interpreted as a direct benefit for the employee. Instead, it is often critiqued as a means for companies to utilize precarious employment contracts, devoid of the traditional benefits associated with stable work. Consequently, this rhetoric of a "democratic workplace" ultimately conceals established hierarchies and structural economic insecurities.

This pervasive narrative is constructed through the visual representation of offices and the accompanying promotional texts, both of which forge a rhetoric that defines work as ubiquitous and inescapable. In this context, flexibility serves primarily to allow organizations to impose financial and existential insecurity more readily, while simultaneously advertising their alternative open working spaces (Gregg, 2011). The aesthetic of "cool" office design is often used to attract younger employees, yet it contributes to an environment where older workers consistently feel uncertain about their role, given that age is frequently perceived as a liability. Furthermore, the visual representation of the successful business professional remains nar-

row, often—if not always—portraying a heterosexual, strong, cisgender, white man who exhibits emotional control. Office aesthetics function as a tool that reproduces and consolidates gender, race, and class stereotypes. A striking example is the visual representation of reception areas: office photographs almost invariably depict women seated at the reception desk, thereby reinforcing the notion that they are relegated to support roles rather than leadership positions. This visual representation is closely linked to the persistent expectation that women undertake unpaid emotional labor (such as event organizing or ambient care), in addition to their official duties.

This imbalance is further exacerbated by the trend of "resimercial design," which merges the aesthetics of the office with the domestic environment. The term *resimercial* results from the combination of the words *residential* and *commercial*, and refers to a layout and furnishing style that brings the homey feel of residential furniture into the workplace. This approach to office architecture tries to distance itself from "old corporate" design, while encouraging the idea that personal and professional spheres should not be separated anymore. This fusion disproportionately projects onto employees (and specifically onto women) the responsibility of creating and maintaining a welcoming, familial atmosphere. The inherent risk of this trend is two-fold: the absorption of private life into working hours, and the internalization of unrecognized emotional labor as an integral part of the professional role.

Cederström and Fleming (2012) emphasize the problematic nature of bringing the home into the office through their concept of "formalized informality." This dynamic occurs when organizations demand that employees "just be themselves" in order to profit from this imitation of private life. When the workplace is presented as a space for living rather than working—where one can decorate a desk with family photos or play music—the reality of merging work and home spaces can eliminate the freedom to live outside of work for many. Simultaneously, this formalized informality allows corporations to exploit employees' social skills in a labor market increasingly reliant on content production, networking, creativity, and other forms of immaterial labor.

The aesthetics, design, and architecture of contemporary workplaces narrate our current working modalities perhaps more eloquently than the actual labor performed within them. It is therefore crucial to decode and critically question the narratives created in these spaces, as their visual and textual discourses carry significant implications extending beyond the work environment to influence individuals' lives and society as a whole. From this broader perspective, the most salient consequence of contemporary office design is its role in supporting, promoting, and perpetuating a work-centered society.

10.3. Psychological Needs Related to Space

When designing CWSs, various psychological needs related to the space must be considered. In the theoretical framework of environmental psychology, these needs are essential for ensuring the comfort and well-being of users, extending the notion of environmental comfort beyond physical parameters like temperature, light, and noise absence. For CWSs, attention to these aspects is crucial, as it directly impacts members' experience and productivity. The most relevant needs are (Pazzaglia & Tizi, 2022):

- **Sense of security and perception of control:** Feeling safe and secure in an environment reduces stress levels and positively impacts mental health. The perception of safety increases comfort and promotes well-being. The ability to influence one's work environment is crucial. In CWSs, this can translate into the ability to adjust the lighting at one's desk, the temperature control, or the seating position. Having control over one's space leads to greater satisfaction, a sense of productivity, and overall well-being.
- **Privacy:** This is a fundamental need that allows people to regulate their social interactions. In CWSs, an inadequate perception of privacy can be a source of stress. Although open-plan layouts are widespread, it is essential that the design offers areas that ensure confidentiality, such as enclosed offices or reserved spaces, which may be preferred by some users.
- **Navigation and wayfinding:** The clarity of the design and the ease with which people can orient and move within an environment are fundamental to comfort. A design that does not create obstacles or confusion reduces the risk of frustration. Additionally, varying the width of corridors can make the spatial experience more interesting and stimulate exploration.
- **Clear affordances:** The features of an environment should clearly communicate the possibilities for action that it offers. For example, intuitive handles, visible buttons, and a layout that suggests the space's functions all contribute to comfort. These visual and tactile cues not only guide users in how to use the space but also reinforce a sense of competence and reduce the anxiety associated with interacting with an unfamiliar environment.
- **Sensory stimulation:** An environment that stimulates all the senses (sight, hearing, touch, smell) in a congruent way contributes to a rich and positive experience. For example, using natural materials like wood can have restorative effects, such as reducing blood pressure and stress levels. Sensory experience is subjective and can have different effects on different people.
- **Universal design:** The application of Universal Design principles is crucial for designing CWSs. This approach focuses on creating environments that are accessible and usable by the widest range of people possible, regardless of physical or cognitive ability. The goal is to remove architectural and cognitive barriers to ensure all members, including those with disabilities or reduced mobility, can navigate and work with autonomy and dignity.
- **Space personalization:** Personalization is key to the success of modern CWSs, as it meets a fundamental psychological need for users to feel a sense of identity. Today's professionals seek tailored experiences that go beyond generic solutions. To achieve this, coworking operators must focus on two main areas: skilled staff and hyper-localization. Hiring qualified professionals like community managers and hospitality experts is essential for creating a positive user experience. Furthermore, spaces should adapt their design, services, and events to reflect local traditions and values.
- **Place attachment:** The concept refers to the emotional and cognitive bond a person develops with a particular location. In CWSs, this bond is crucial and is influenced by three key dimensions: place identity, where the space reflects a member's professional and personal values; place dependence, where the space provides essential re-

sources and services not easily found elsewhere; and social bonding, where the location acts as a catalyst for relationships and community. Research shows that this emotional connection is strengthened by designs that promote informal interaction, allow for personalization, and support a sense of belonging, highlighting that the physical layout is as important as the functional efficiency of the space.

In summary, CWSs should be designed not just for efficiency but to support members' well-being. Stressors, both environmental (such as noise and air pollution) and socio-environmental (like lack of privacy and overcrowding), must be minimized. Providing options that allow members to control their space, ensuring areas that offer privacy, facilitating wayfinding, and incorporating a design that positively stimulates the senses are all crucial actions for creating an effective and welcoming coworking environment.

10.4. Environmental Stressors

Without adequate planning, workspaces, including CWSs, can become a source of environmental and socio-environmental stress for users (Baroni & Berto, 2013). This stress can have a negative impact on workers' health, well-being, and productivity. Below is an overview of the main stressors and their importance in the design of these environments (Pazzaglia & Tizi, 2022).

Environmental Stressors

These factors are related to the physical characteristics of the environment.

- **Noise:** Noise is a major stressor in modern workspaces, as it can distract, reduce concentration, and elevate stress levels. In CWSs, noise often comes from conversations, phones, and equipment. Studies show that unpredictable or uncontrollable noise is particularly detrimental to productivity and can lead to a sense of helplessness.
- **Thermal conditions:** Suboptimal temperatures and humidity can cause discomfort and negatively affect performance. An environment that is too hot or too cold can become a constant distraction, making it difficult for members to focus on their work.
- **Air quality:** Poor indoor air quality, caused by inadequate ventilation or chemical emissions, can lead to symptoms like headaches and fatigue. This factor is often overlooked but has a significant impact on the long-term health and cognitive function of users.
- **Light:** Both insufficient and excessive lighting, such as screen glare, can cause eye strain and headaches. On the other hand, access to natural light has been shown to have positive effects on mood, sleep cycles, and overall well-being, making it a crucial element to consider in design.

Socio-Environmental Stressors

These factors arise from the interaction between people and the environment.

- **Lack of privacy:** In open-plan CWSs, the lack of visual and acoustic privacy can be highly stressful. Feeling constantly observed or not having a dedicated area for private

calls or conversations can generate anxiety and insecurity. Privacy isn't just about being alone; it's about the perceived ability to control interactions with others.

- Invasion of personal space and territory: The invasion of personal space is a crucial socio-environmental stressor, especially in high-density environments like CWSs. Personal space is an invisible, mobile zone surrounding each individual—a protective "bubble" that changes based on culture, gender, age, and context. When this bubble is invaded without permission, it can lead to discomfort, anxiety, and stress. In CWSs, a lack of adequate personal space is a common source of stress. The high density of desks and open-plan layouts can lead to excessive physical proximity, resulting in a loss of control over one's distance from others, increased vigilance (the need to constantly monitor people to avoid interruptions), and a lack of privacy.
- Overcrowding: The density of people in an environment can lead to feelings of overcrowding, which reduces one's sense of control and increases anxiety. The perception of overcrowding is subjective and depends not only on the number of people but also on the configuration of the space itself.

10.5. Restorative Coworking Spaces

The field of environmental psychology, anchored by seminal concepts like Attention Restoration Theory (ART; Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989) and Stress Recovery Theory (SRT; Ulrich, 1983), provides a robust foundation for integrating environmental restorativeness into contemporary workplace design. Restorativeness refers to the capacity of an environment to replenish depleted cognitive resources, mitigate mental fatigue, and reduce physiological stress responses (cfr. *Restorative environments*, Staats, 2012).

In high-demand professional settings, particularly collaborative CWSs, employees often experience sustained directed attention fatigue (DAF), which impairs concentration, performance, and emotional regulation. Scientific evidence suggests that exposure to restorative environments, often characterized by elements of nature, enables an effortless form of attention known as *soft fascination*.

For organizations, the strategic inclusion of restorative qualities—such as natural light, access to views of greenery, indoor plants, and dedicated "quiet pods"—is no longer a mere amenity but a critical job resource. Research consistently demonstrates a positive correlation between perceived environmental restorativeness and reduced job stress, increased job satisfaction, and elevated levels of work engagement (Bellini et al., 2015). Integrating these principles into the design of CWSs represents a paradigm shift, moving design beyond mere functionality to actively supporting the long-term well-being and sustained cognitive performance of the contemporary workforce.

The biophilic interior design trend is also set to dominate CWSs. The concept of biophilia, defined as the innate human tendency to affiliate with natural systems and processes (Wilson, 1984), provides the theoretical framework for enhancing environmental restorativeness. This intrinsic connection is directly operationalized in practice through Biophilic Design, an approach that purposefully integrates nature—or elements resembling it—into the built environment (Kellert, Heerwagen & Mador, 2008; Lefosse, Van Timmeren & Ratti, 2023). In the

context of contemporary workplaces, and particularly CWSs, biophilic design is a strategic investment in human performance. Empirical evidence confirms that biophilic elements—such as direct access to nature, natural light, materials echoing natural forms (e.g., wood and stone), and patterns that mimic fractal geometry—yield measurable cognitive benefits. Specifically, the presence of these elements has been shown to reduce stress hormones, increase cognitive function, and enhance creativity among occupants (Browning & Ryan, 2020; Browning et al., 2014). Therefore, for CWSs to fulfill their potential as truly restorative territories, they must transcend mere aesthetic inclusion and adopt Biophilic Design principles as a fundamental strategy for supporting sustained mental vitality and well-being.

However, the need for workplace restoration extends beyond the physical environment; it encompasses the crucial domain of cognitive relief from digital demands. This shift parallels a growing scientific and sociological interest in the strategies of digital disconnection and media withdrawal, even if partial (e.g., Lomborg & Ytre-Arne, 2021). This phenomenon responds to a broader societal trend towards "disconnection." The problems that motivate it are manifold: at the individual level, they manifest as feelings of dependence, distraction, and information overload; at the organizational level, they translate into reduced productivity; at the political level, they raise concerns about digital surveillance. These dynamics, which challenge the normalization of permanent connectivity and digital dependence, indicate the advent of a post-digital condition. In this context, concepts like "post-digital territoriality" (Fast & Jansson, 2024) emerge as a prospective way to manage connectivity in the era of data colonialism and intrusive "datafication."

The organizational characteristics of CWSs make them inherently vulnerable to digital intrusion and over-connectivity. In line with the post-digital condition, the true mission of coworking is not just connectivity, but, as suggested by Migliore et al. (2021), to serve as intermediary territories that facilitate distributed work practices, composed of physical and digital connections, as well as formal and informal interactions. These dynamics require a level of relational hybridization that balances presence and distance. Part of the appeal of these spaces lies in their ability to provide an "identity anchoring environment" (Bacevice & Spreitzer, 2023) for aspiring creative workers and knowledge workers. In this context, voluntary digital disconnection has been increasingly recognized as a means to promote well-being and work-life balance, as well as a sign of social distinction (Fast et al., 2021; Hesselberth, 2018; Syvertsen, 2017). This trend is also reflected in management literature, which highlights the benefits of "deep work" and "digital minimalism" (Newport, 2016, 2019; Goodin, 2017; Rauch, 2018), emphasizing the importance of spaces that support not only connectivity but also deep concentration and targeted disconnection.

While digital infrastructures are still rudimentary for coordinating flexible offices (Richardson, 2021), concrete measures exist to compensate for the digital fatigue, stress, and frustration that afflict contemporary knowledge workers.

In this context, the vision of Alex Hillman, founder of Indy Hall, is particularly illuminating: he describes coworking not as a workspace industry, but as a true "happiness industry" that humanizes work (King, 2017). By providing analog services and promoting disconnection (such as board games, ping-pong, yoga, and mindfulness), most CWSs become a place that balances

hard computer work with joyful recreation away from screens. The ambivalent approach to digital media, together with methodologies aimed at freeing workers from overload, helps to create spaces where productivity and leisure activities coexist.

However, a critical look is necessary. Purser (2018), for example, dismisses corporate mindfulness programs as a *"disciplined but myopic self-help doctrine, which transfers the risk and responsibility for well-being onto the individual"* (p. 107). This perspective prompts us to reflect on the fact that the responsibility for well-being cannot be delegated solely to the worker.

11. Conclusions and Recommendations

Initially conceptualized as "third places" situated between the home and the traditional office and developed as a response to the inherent limitations of freelance work, such as isolation and the challenges of homeworking, CWSs have undergone significant evolution. Today, they represent the primary workplace for millions of knowledge workers in key global hubs.

The rapid proliferation of these multi-tenant offices is attributable to a convergence of structural shifts in the professional and urban landscape. These enabling factors include the adoption of new work modalities, the rise of the sharing economy, the surging demand for organizational flexibility, the hybrid utilization of public spaces as workspaces, the growth in technological adoption, and the increasing number of autonomous workers. All these elements collectively contribute to a redefined and diminished need for conventional office space (Weijs-Perrère et al., 2019).

While it remains a small part of the global office market, the coworking sector continues to grow and evolve. The current dynamics reveal a rapid evolution: new spaces tend to be larger than older ones, existing operators are actively expanding, and efficiency metrics are increasing as they serve more members per square foot. A significant portion of this overall industry growth stems from new entrants seeking distinctive offers. This activity, combined with the expanding presence of corporate occupiers and employees, is driving recent market trends toward niche communities that allow for specialized service provision. Simultaneously, market consolidation is accelerating as larger, better-established operators acquire smaller businesses to diversify their offerings or expand revenue streams. This all occurs within a landscape where the quality of digital integration is becoming paramount. High expectations from competition and new entrants, including corporate entities, are collectively driving innovative approaches to space and services. The increasing attractiveness of coworking is further evidenced by its incorporation into corporate space portfolios and the development of large coworking chains that replicate the concept across multiple locations.

Beyond market expansion, the growing appeal of CWSs is fundamentally rooted in their demonstrable functionality and capacity to generate value for their members. The functionality of CWSs—encompassing the facilities, services, and activities associated with these new working arrangements—has garnered increasing academic attention. CWSs are recognized for their significant potential in driving the development of local knowledge economies, offering advantages that can be synthesized into three key areas (Bouncken, Kraus & Martínez-Pérez, 2020). First, they provide flexible and affordable infrastructure: shared workspaces rich in amenities and comfort, proving to be an economically viable solution for freelancers, self-employed workers, and small entrepreneurs. Second, CWSs deliver Value-Added Services (VAS), such as mentorship and business planning support, which include training sessions, workshops, and business tutoring. These services are crucial for enhancing the skills of knowledge workers and significantly increasing startup survival rates. Finally, these environments foster robust networking opportunities that stimulate collaboration and the creation of synergies among coworkers and member entrepreneurs within the community.

Despite the proven organizational and community advantages, it is essential to contextualize CWSs within their inherent material constraints. Notwithstanding their emphasis on community-building, CWSs remain concrete, physically owned, and managed entities that are profoundly shaped by processes of urban real estate development and speculation. This raises interesting, yet under-researched, questions concerning the underlying business strategies of these spaces (Yates et al., 2024). Consequently, CWSs cannot simply offer physical space; to maintain viability, they must function as hybrid territories capable of catalyzing community development and fostering innovation, while simultaneously upholding clear economic sustainability.

Looking toward future research implications (Howell, 2022), it is hypothesized that CWSs can function as a novel source of social capital. This occurs when a community of entrepreneurs interacts and engages in reciprocal support, providing referrals and introductions to key stakeholders (e.g., clients, investors, employees).

Coworking also offers a rich context for studying emerging questions related to organizational planning and boundaries. Organizational boundaries are traditionally defined as the demarcation between an organization and its environment. In CWS, these boundaries are inherently blurred. A collective identity connects the members of a coworking community, despite them formally working for diverse organizations. Furthermore, CWS have significant implications for spatial proximity theories and their impact on innovation, knowledge sharing, and knowledge spillovers.

Finally, in light of recent industry shifts, CWSs are poised to play a crucial role in the evolving future of work. With several companies announcing plans to become "all-remote" organizations—eliminating central offices or headquarters and allowing employees to work from anywhere—some are now considering offering their staff a "coworking stipend" as a direct benefit. This trend underscores the growing acceptance of CWSs as a formalized component of the corporate real estate strategy.

However, capitalizing on this potential requires new approaches to workplace evaluation, especially given the impending integration of advanced technologies and the recognized gap in empirical knowledge. Parallel to the increasing corporate adoption of coworking, the next significant wave of workplace innovation will be data-led, as evidenced by the proliferation of numerous proprietary sensor systems already on the market for capturing a wide range of real-time information. While this technology represents a huge potential advancement in understanding how the workplace is actually used, research highlights two crucial dangers in relying exclusively on sensor technology (Privett, 2020). Both risks suggest the need for the careful integration and development of design approaches that draw on both 'big data' technologies and qualitative user feedback, leveraging each to enrich the understanding provided by the other.

Although there has been significant organizational interest in coworking, it has not been sufficiently connected to the broader body of knowledge on workplace behavior. To determine if coworking represents a truly unique space type, it is essential to use existing organizational

literature as a point of reference. This approach reveals a significant gap between design intentions and reality, a gap exacerbated by the lack of empirical evidence on the relationship between space and behavior. Since space is increasingly recognized as a strategic tool and coworking has an inherently bottom-up orientation, it is crucial to focus on the perspective of end-users rather than just the designers' choices. To fully understand the function of these spaces, we must study intangible qualities like affect, experience, and values from the users' perspective. This requires adopting new frameworks and approaches for design and evaluation that place the users at the center of the process (Privett, 2020).

Ultimately, coworking “would seem to represent a bottom-up model of space provision with a responsiveness to member needs that is distinctly different from traditional organisational provision. If workplaces are to be designed more closely around user experience, this points to a need to understand what experience means to the people who inhabit them. This suggests the need to develop new frameworks and approaches that can be used to guide workplace design and evaluation” (Privett, 2020, p. 250).

The coworking phenomenon has now moved beyond the experimental phase, presenting itself as a heterogeneous ecosystem that includes highly professional spaces, corporate networks, and resilient, community-based initiatives. The recent evolution—from the “avant-garde” phase to the dominance of neo-corporate models and the re-emerging focus on resilient and territorialized models—requires an organic rethinking of organizational forms that can reconcile economic sustainability, social impact, and quality of use. The following recommendations are intended to offer operational guidelines for operators, policymakers, designers, and researchers to promote innovative, inclusive, and scalable organizational models.

I. STRATEGIC MODEL REORIENTATION AND FINANCIAL RESILIENCE

New organizational models must shift the focus from purely spatial efficiency to relational value and financial robustness, balancing local autonomy with network coherence.

1. Governance, Ownership, and Scalability

Future CWS models must achieve a strategic balance between embeddedness and scalability by promoting hybrid multi-site networks. These networks require central management to guarantee essential minimum standards (connectivity, security, privacy) but strong local autonomy for adapting content, events, and design.

- **Participatory governance:** New forms of governance should incentivize cooperative and hybrid models of member-owned property, especially in rural or peripheral contexts, to strengthen social sustainability. Such structures should incorporate hybrid cooperatives that combine private shares with public or philanthropic funding to mitigate initial economic risk.
- **Multi-stakeholder boards:** The introduction of multi-stakeholder governance is mandated, involving management boards composed of representatives from users, operators, local institutions, and key partners (universities, incubators). This encourages

co-design and shared responsibility while mandating the adoption of transparent social reporting mechanisms.

- Decentralized strategy: The organizational model must formally incorporate its role as a strategic mediator of work, moving toward a Post-Digital Territoriality framework. This includes utilizing the "hub and spoke" organizational formula in rural areas: a central node sharing resources and programs with satellite units in neighboring towns to improve local reach and regeneration.

2. Revenue Diversification and Financial Tools

To ensure financial robustness, CWSs must adopt a comprehensive strategy of revenue source diversification, moving beyond sole dependence on desk leasing.

- Integrated revenue streams: Integrate traditional membership fees with consumption-based models (pay-per-use), event space rental, and the offering of specialized professional services (accounting, communication). Further stability is gained through corporate partnerships for creating satellite stations for client employees.
- Public support and incentives: A fundamental pillar lies in activating public support mechanisms. This involves promoting local calls for proposals and using micro-credit instruments to support community-oriented CWS start-ups. Specific tax incentives should also be proposed for activities demonstrating measurable social impact, such as the inclusion of disadvantaged groups or the reuse of historic buildings.
- Formalizing corporate integration: Capitalize on the all-remote trend by offering the "Coworking Stipend"—tailored benefit packages that formalize the CWS as a component of the corporate real estate strategy, ensuring stable revenue streams and integration into the formal organizational fabric of client companies.

II. HUMAN-CENTRIC DESIGN AND RELATIONAL MANAGEMENT

Organizational models must prioritize the quality of the user experience (QoE), focusing on physical and relational design elements that actively promote well-being, sustained cognitive performance, and equity.

1. Organizational and Environmental Design for Restoration

The adoption of hybrid and modular structures is imperative to optimize the quality of use, harmoniously integrating open space areas, quiet pods, and private offices.

- Biophilic and restorative infrastructure: The organizational model must treat design elements derived from biophilia and Attention Restoration Theory (ART) not as superficial décor, but as critical infrastructure investments. Organizational policy should mandate that a minimum percentage of floor space be dedicated to truly restorative elements (natural light, acoustic separation), rather than purely high-density workstations.
- Addressing digital fatigue: Clear usage policies and a digital "code of conduct" are fundamental. New models must Formalize Digital Boundaries by explicitly offering digital

disconnection services or zoned areas (e.g., analog rooms, distraction-free pods) as essential Value-Added Services (VAS). This counters the narrative of work as "ubiquitous and inescapable."

- Evidence-based design audits: CWS operators should commit to routine Post-Occupancy Evaluations (POE) that specifically measure the restorative impact of design elements on user self-efficacy and stress reduction, directly linking design choices to organizational outcomes.

2. Community Care, Equity, and Inclusion

Community management must formally recognize "care" as a profession and actively mitigate risks of precarity and exclusion.

- Professionalizing care: Stabilize the role of the Community Manager as a central figure with recognized competencies, ranging from mediation and event design to entrepreneurial tutoring and diversity & inclusion management. Training should be provided through certified programs combining soft skills, network building, and engagement monitoring tools.
- Structured integration and support: Implement structured integration programs (onboarding, matchmaking, mentoring) for new members to facilitate the creation of meaningful initial ties and mitigate the risk of "working alone together." Crucially, the model must provide resources to mitigate the "resimercial burden"—the uncompensated emotional labor often required to create a familial atmosphere—by incorporating paid support staff for event organization and ambient care.
- Targeting and aesthetic equity: To ensure a positive social impact, implement policies of targeting and differential pricing for disadvantaged categories (NEETs, women entrepreneurs, low-income SMEs). Furthermore, to counteract visual narratives that reinforce traditional, exclusionary power structures, the CWS strategy must intervene in aesthetic representation by developing Visual Equity Guidelines for marketing and internal photography that intentionally showcase diverse age, race, and gender representation across all roles. Age-Inclusive Design must also be integrated to signal respect across all demographics.
- Redefining flexibility: New organizational models must reclaim the meaning of flexibility, which is often criticized for masking precarity. This requires Contractual Transparency in membership tiers that explicitly address the well-being component, legitimizing rest as a performance driver.

III. MONITORING, INNOVATION, AND RISK MITIGATION

The future of CWS is fundamentally evidence-based, requiring rigorous measurement, transparent technology, and active strategies to mitigate territorial and social risks.

1. Technology, Interoperability, and Data Governance

The success of coworking networks is linked to the adoption of integrated and interoperable platforms that move beyond proprietary solutions.

- Open standards: Implement multi-site management systems capable of centralizing functions (booking, invoicing, usage analytics) while promoting the use of open APIs for seamless integration with external partners (universities, service providers). Avoiding proprietary solutions that create technological lock-in and favoring open standards facilitates member mobility and long-term sustainability.
- Transparency and privacy: It is mandatory to establish rigorous data protection and transparency policies. This includes drafting clear policies on the collection and use of occupancy data, ensuring the informed consent of members, and providing transparent reporting on the use of sensors and telemetry technologies. Data governance practices must categorically prevent any form of predatory or unethical use of members' personal data.

2. Evidence-Based Measurement and Research

The next wave of organizational innovation must be driven by data and qualitative user insight, not merely designer intuition.

- Hybrid evaluation frameworks: Implement a system of operational and social KPIs (occupancy rate, retention, collaborations, satisfaction score, quantifiable local impact). Evaluation should utilize a methodological mix that deliberately combines quantitative sensor data with qualitative user feedback (e.g., deep interviews, experience mapping). Sensor data should be used to ask better questions about user experience, not solely to measure cost efficiency.
- Proactive research agenda: Define a strategic research and experimentation agenda. This involves promoting studies on the effectiveness of community care practices, access equity, and the measurement of creativity and innovation produced within CWSs. Concurrently, it is crucial to incentivize the execution of controlled pilots to test new pricing models and governance structures.
- Prioritizing intangible qualities: Organizational research agendas must shift focus to studying intangible qualities—such as affect, experience, and values—from the end-user's perspective, aligning with the understanding that coworking is a bottom-up model of space provision.

3. Rural Development and Risk Mitigation

Models must be adapted to low-density contexts and actively manage negative social externalities.

- Context-adapted rural models: In rural areas, priority must be given to multi-purpose configurations that integrate the coworking function with local public services, training, and cultural events. This requires establishing robust partnerships with local administrations for the regeneration of unused building spaces and the generation of economic spin-offs.
- Mitigation of gentrification: The expansion of CWSs introduces the primary risk of gentrification and social exclusion. It is crucial to closely monitor impacts on the local real estate market and implement corrective measures, such as applying controlled rents,

collaborating with local property owners, and entering into long-term lease agreements that include explicit social clauses.

- Preserving social capital: A second imperative is to limit the "commodification" of the community. To preserve the essential relational value, it is necessary to guarantee and protect spaces and moments dedicated to self-managed and free community activities, preventing excessive monetization of interactions from draining the social capital.

The preceding analysis establishes that CWS are hybrid territories profoundly shaped by socio-economic forces and shifting user demands. The true measure of a successful CWS model lies not in its physical footprint, but in its capacity to serve as a resilient and equitable territory that genuinely supports human flourishing and innovation in a post-digital age.

The implementation of integrated, contextualized, and experimental approaches is the only path for CWS to consolidate as social and productive infrastructures capable of supporting work transitions that are more equitable, resilient, and characterized by reduced vulnerabilities. For both sector operators and policy-makers, the recommended path is clear: experiment with local prototypes, measure their effectiveness with scientific rigor, share best practices and standards, and disseminate the collected evidence to build a coworking ecosystem that is simultaneously professional, inclusive, and deeply rooted in its territories.

References

- Akhavan M. (2021). Third places for work: A comprehensive review of the literature on coworking spaces and makerspaces. In I. Mariotti, S. Di Vita, M. Akhavan (Eds.), *New work-places – Location patterns, urban effects and development trajectories* (pp. 13-32), Cham: Springer International Publishing. Doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-63443-8
- Alfano V., Mariotti I., Marra M., & Vecchione G. (2023). I want to break free: The influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on work–life balance satisfaction, regional studies. *Regional Science*, 10(1): 70–88. DOI: 10.1080/ 21681376.2023.2167608
- Aroles J., Cecez-Kecmanovic D., Dale K., Kingma S.F., & Mitev N. (2021). New ways of working (NWW): Workplace transformation in the digital age. *Information and Organization*, 31(4): 100378. DOI: 10.1016/j.infoandorg.2021.100378
- Allen T.J. (1977). *Managing the Flow of Technology*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Allen T.D., Golden T.D., & Shockley K.M. (2015). How effective is telecommuting? Assessing the status of our scientific findings. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 16(2): 40–68. DOI: 10.1177/1529100615593273
- Aloisi A. (2022). Automation, augmentation, autonomy: Labour regulation and the technological transformation of managerial prerogatives. In T. Gyulavári & E. Menegatti (Eds.), *Decent work in the digital age: European and Comparative Perspectives* (p. 245 f.). Hart Publishing.
- Aloisi A., & Corazza L. (2022). Tra flessibilità organizzativa e sviluppo sostenibile. Il South Working nella prospettiva giuslavoristica. In M. Mirabile & E. Militello (Eds.), *South Working: Per un futuro sostenibile del lavoro agile in Italia*. Donzelli Editore.
- Ananian P., Shearmur R., Borde M.A., Lachapelle U., Paulhiac F., Tremblay D.G., & Rodrigue T. (2024). Coworking spaces in Montreal (Canada): Moving beyond classic location patterns. *Geoforum*, 152: 104016. DOI: 10.1016/j. geoforum.2024.104016
- Appel-Meulenbroek R., Weijs-Perrée M., Orel M., Gauger F., & Pfnür A. (2021). User preferences for coworking spaces: A comparison between the Netherlands, Germany and the Czech Republic. *Review of Managerial Science*, 15: 2025-2048. DOI: 10. 1007/ s11846- 020- 00414-z
- Aroles J., Mitev N., & de Vaujany F.-X. (2019). Mapping themes in the study of new work practices. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 34(3): 285-299. DOI: 10.1111/ntwe.12146
- Arvidsson A. (2018). Value and virtue in the sharing economy. *The Sociological Review*, 66(2): 289-301. DOI: 10.1177/0038026118758531
- Avdikos V., & Merkel J. (2019). Supporting open, shared and collaborative workspaces and hubs: Recent transformations and policy implications. *Urban Research & Practice*, 13(3): 348-357. DOI: 10.1080/17535069.2019.1674501
- Ayodele T.O., Ogunbayo O.T., Kajimo-Shakantu K., & Babatunde T. (2022). Coworking space practices: Assessing space users' preferences and challenges in ibadan, Nigeria. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 24(4): 256–272. DOI: 10.1108/JCRE-03-2021-0011
- Babb C., Curtis C., & McLeod S. (2018). The rise of shared work spaces: A disruption to urban planning policy? *Urban Policy and Research*, 36(4): 1–17. DOI: 10.1080/08111146.2018.1476230
- Bacevice P.A., & Spreitzer G.M. (2023). 'It's like, instant respect': Coworking spaces as identity anchoring environments in the new economy. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 38(1): 59-81. DOI: 10.1111/ntwe.12254

- Bähr U., Biemann J., Lietzau J., Hentschel P., & Bertelsmann S. (Eds.). (2020). *Coworking im ländlichen Raum: Menschen, Modelle, Trends*. [Coworking in rural areas: People, models, trends]. DOI: 10.11586/2020076
- Balachandra L., Briggs T., Eddleston K., & Brush C. (2019). Don't pitch like a girl!: How gender stereotypes influence investor decisions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(1): 116–137. DOI: 10.1177/1042258717728028
- Baldessarelli G., Stigliani I., & Elsbach K.D. (2022). The aesthetic dimension of organizing: A review and research agenda. *Academy of Management Annals*, 16(1): 217-257. DOI: 10.5465/annals.2020.0198
- Bandinelli C., Gandini A. (2019) Hubs vs networks in the creative economy: Towards a 'collaborative individualism'. In R. Gill, A. Pratt, & T. Virani (Eds.), *Creative Hubs in Question* (pp. 89-110), London: Routledge.
- Baroni M.R., & Berto R. (2013). *Stress ambientale: Cause e strategie di intervento*. Roma: Carocci.
- Bednář P., & Danko L., 2020. Coworking Spaces as a Driver of the Post-Fordist City: A Tool for Building a Creative Ecosystem. *European Spatial Research and Policy*, 27 (1): 105-125. DOI: 10.18778/1231-1952.27.1.05
- Bednář P., Danko L., & Smékalová L. (2023). Coworking Spaces and Creative Communities: Making Resilient Coworking Spaces Through Knowledge Sharing and Collective Learning. *European Planning Studies*, 31(3): 490–507. DOI: 10.1080/09654 313.2021.1944065
- Bednář P., Mariotti I., Rossi F., & Danko L. (2021). The evolution of coworking spaces in Milan and Prague: Spatial patterns, diffusion, and urban change. In M. Orel, O. Dvouletý, & V. Ratten (Eds.), *The Flexible Workplace. Human Resource Management*. Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-62167-4_4
- Bellini D., Ramaci T., & Bonaiuto M. (2015) The Restorative Effect of the Environment on Organizational Cynicism and Work Engagement. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 3: 124–135. DOI: 10.4236/jhrss.2015.33017
- Benner M. (2021). Retheorizing Industrial–Institutional Coevolution: A Multidimensional Perspective. *Regional Studies*, 56(9): 1524–1537. DOI: 10.1080/00343 404.2021.1949441
- Bennis W.M., & Orel M. (2025). Four models of the coworking concept to facilitate remote higher education. *Facilities*, 43(7-8): 426–443. DOI: 10.1108/F-02-2024-0031
- Berdicchia D., Fortezza F., & Masino G. (2023). The key to happiness in collaborative workplaces. Evidence from coworking spaces. *Review of Managerial Science*, 17(4): 1213–1242. DOI: 10.1007/s11846-022-00558-0
- Bergner Y., & Chen O. (2018). Deep making: Curricular modules for transferable content-knowledge and scientific literacy in makerspaces and FabLabs. *Proceedings of the 17th ACM Conference on Interaction Design and Children*, 551-556. ACM.
- Blagoev B., Costas J., & Kärreman D. (2019). 'We are all herd animals': Community and organizational in coworking spaces. *Organization*, 26(6): 894-916. DOI: 10.1177/1350508418821008
- Bokányi E., Novák M., Jakobi Á., & Lengyel B. (2022). Urban Hierarchy and Spatial Diffusion over the Innovation Life Cycle. *Royal Society Open Science*, 9(5): 211038. DOI: 10.1098/rsos.211038.

- Bouncken R.B., Aslam M.M., & Reuschl A.J. (2018). The Dark Side of Entrepreneurship in Coworking Spaces. In: A. Tur Porcar, & D. Ribeiro Soriano (Eds.), *Inside the mind of the entrepreneur: Contributions to management science* (pp. 135-147), Cambridge: Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-62455-6_10
- Bouncken R., Kraus S., & Martínez-Pérez J. F. (2020). Entrepreneurship of an institutional field: The emergence of coworking spaces for digital business models. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 16(4): 1465–1481. DOI: 10.1007/s11365-020-00689-4
- Bouncken R.B., Ratzmann M., Barwinski R., & Kraus S. (2020). Coworking spaces: Empowerment for entrepreneurship and innovation in the digital and sharing economy. *Journal of Business Research*, 114: 102-110. DOI: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.03.033
- Bouncken R.B., & Reuschl A.J. (2018). Coworking-spaces: How a phenomenon of the sharing economy builds a novel trend for the workplace and for entrepreneurship. *Review of Managerial Science*, 12(1): 317-334. DOI: 10.1007/s11846-016-0215-y
- Brouwer A., Mariotti I., van Ommeren J. (2004). The Firm Relocation Decision: An Empirical Investigation. *Annals of Regional Science*, 38(2): 335–347. DOI: 10.1007/s00168-004-0198-5
- Brown G. (2009). Claiming a corner at work: Measuring employee territoriality in their workspaces. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 29(1): 44–52. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvp.2008.05.004
- Brown G., Lawrence T.B., & Robinson S.L. (2005). Territoriality in organizations. *Academy of Management Review*, 30(3): 577–594. DOI: 10.2307/20159145
- Brown J. (2017). Curating the “third place”? Coworking and the mediation of creativity. *Geoforum*, 82: 112-126. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoforum.2017.04.006
- Browning W.D., & Ryan C.O. (2020). *Nature inside: A biophilic design guide*. London: Riba Publishing.
- Browning W.D., Ryan C.O., & Clancy J.O. (2014). *14 patterns of biophilic design*. New York: Terrapin Bright Green, LLC. <https://www.terrapinbrightgreen.com/reports/14-patterns/>
- Brübach-Schlickum S. (2016). Coworking als alternatives Arbeitsplatzkonzept–Fallstudie Combiat 56. In *Arbeitsplatz der Zukunft* (pp. 273–290). Wiesbaden: Springer Gabler.
- Bughin J., Lund S., & Remes J. (2016). Rethinking work in the digital age. *McKinsey Quarterly*, (Oct). Retrieved from <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/organization/our-insights/rethinking-work-in-the-digital-age>
- Campos-Castillo C., & Hitlin S. (2013). Copresence: Revisiting a building block for social interaction theories. *Sociological Theory*, 31(2): 168–192. DOI: 10.1177/0735275113489811
- Capdevila I. (2013). Knowledge dynamics in localized communities: Spaces as microclusters. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.2414121
- Capdevila I. (2017). A typology of localized spaces of collaborative innovation. In M. van Ham, D. Reuschke, R. Kleinhans, C. Mason, & S. Syrett (Eds.), *Entrepreneurial Neighbourhoods* (pp. 80-97), Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Ceccarelli M. (2008). Renaissance of machines in Italy: From Brunelleschi to Galilei through Francesco di Giorgio and Leonardo. *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, 43(12): 1530–1542. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2008.01.001
- Cederström C., & Fleming P. (2012). *Dead Man Working*. Winchester: Zero Books.

- Centner R. (2008). Places of privileged consumption practices: Spatial capital, the dot-com habitus, and San Francisco's internet boom. *City & Community*, 7(3): 193-223. DOI: 10.1111/j.1540-6040.2008.00258.x
- Cerqueira E.D.V., Motte-Baumvol B., Chevallier L.B., & Bonin O. (2020). Does working from home reduce CO2 emissions? An analysis of travel patterns as dictated by workplaces. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 83: 102338.
- Charalampous M., Grant C.A., Tramontano C., & Michailidis E. (2019). Systematically reviewing remote e-workers' well-being at work: A multidimensional approach. *European Journal of Work & Organizational Psychology*, 28(1): 51-73. DOI: 10.1080/1359432X.2018.1541886
- Choudhury P.R. (2020). Our work-from-anywhere future. Best practices for all-remote organizations. *Harvard Business Review* (November-December). Retrieved October 31, 2025 from <https://hbr.org/2020/11/our-work-from-anywhere-future>
- Ciccarelli F.C., Mariotti I., & Rossi F. (2025). The role of geographical location for work-life balance satisfaction: Insights from Italian coworking spaces. *Applied Geography*, 174: 103485. DOI: 10.1016/j.apgeog.2024.103485.
- Cisco Systems. (2015). *How-To Guide: Creating Exceptionally Collaborative Workplaces*. Retrieved from https://www.cisco.com/c/dam/m/en_emarketing/offers/collaboration/workplace-transformation/pdfs/co-07-collaborative-workplace-how-to-wp-cte-en-uk.pdf. Accessed on October 1, 2025.
- Clayton P., Feldman M., & Lowe N. (2018). Behind the scenes: Intermediary organizations that facilitate science commercialization through entrepreneurship. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 32(1): 104-124. DOI: 10.5465/amp.2016.0133
- Clifton N., Füzi A., & Loudon G. (2019). Coworking in the digital economy: Context, motivations, and outcomes. *Futures*, 135: 102439. DOI: 10.1016/j.futures.2019.102439
- Countouris N., De Stefano V., Piasna A., & Rainone S. (Eds.). (2023). Introduction. In *The Future of Remote Work* (pp. 7-17). European Trade Union Institute (ETUI), Brussels.
- Corazza L. (2022). Il lavoro senza mobilità: Smart working e geografia sociale nel post-pandemia. *Lavoro e Diritto*, 2, 431-448. DOI: 10.1441/103989
- Corvec S.S.-L. (2023). Which transport modes do people use to travel to coworking spaces (CWSs)? *Multimodal Transportation*, 2(2): 100078. DOI: 10.1016/j.multra.2023.100078
- Couldry N., & Mejias U.A. (2019). *The costs of connection: How data is colonizing human life and appropriating it for capitalism*. Stanford University Press
- Coworking.com. (2023). *About coworking*. <https://coworking.com/about/> (Retrieved 10/26/2025)
- Davidson A. (2015). What Hollywood can teach us about the future of work. *The New York Times Magazine*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2015/05/10/magazine/what-hollywood-can-teach-us-about-the-future-of-work.html>
- Dähner S., Reibstein L., Slupina M., Klingholz R., Hennig S., & Gruchmann G. (2019). Urbane Dörfer: Wie digitales Arbeiten Städter aufs Land bringen kann [Urban Villages: How Digital Working Can Bring City Dwellers to the Countryside] (1. Auflage ed.). Berlin: Berlin-Institut für Bevölkerung und Entwicklung and Neuland21 e.V. Retrieved October 31, 2025, from https://www.berlin-institut.org/fileadmin/Redaktion/Publikationen/PDF/BI_UrbaneDoerfer_2019.pdf

- Danko L., Bednar P., Lux G., Kalman J., Belvončíková E., Horeczki R., & Balint D. (2024). Coworking Spaces and Mid-Sized Cities in Peripheral Contexts: Conceptualising Development Trajectories. *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie*. DOI: 115. 10.1111/tesg.12622.
- Davenport T.H., & Pearlson K. (1998). Two cheers for the virtual office. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 39(4): 51.
- De Guzman G.V., & Tang A.I. (2011). *Working in the unoffice: A guide to coworking for indie workers, small businesses, and nonprofits*. San Francisco, CA: Night Owls Press LLC.
- Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities (DLUHC). (2022). *Levelling up the United Kingdom*. HM Government. Retrieved October 31, 2025 from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1052706/Levelling_Up_WP_HRES.pdf
- de Peuter G., Cohen N.S., & Saraco F. (2017). The ambivalence of coworking: On the politics of an emerging work practice. *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, 20(6): 687-706. DOI: 10.1177/1367549417732
- Deskmag. (2012). *Seven tips to help a coworking space run smoothly*. Retrieved from <https://www.deskmag.com/en/coworking-tools-tips/seven-tips-to-help-a-coworking-space-run-smoothly-480>. Accessed on October 1, 2025.
- Deskmag. (2016). *Deskmag Global Coworking Survey 2016* [Online]. Retrieved October 31, 2025 from <http://www.deskmag.com/en/coworking-statistics-all-results-of-the-global-coworking-survey-research-studies-948>
- Deskmag. (2019). *The 2019 Global Coworking Survey*.
- Deskmag (2022). *Coworking Space Trends 2021-22*.
- Di Marino M., Rehunen A., Tiitu M., & Lapintie L. (2021). New Working Spaces in the Helsinki Metropolitan Area: Understanding Location Factors and Implications for Planning. *European Planning Studies*, 31(3): 508–527. DOI: 10.1080/09654313.2021.1945541
- Di Risio A. (2018). *Coworking spaces for artists and creatives*. Retrieved 10/26/2025 at: <https://www.coworkingresources.org/blog/coworking-spaces-for-artists-and-creatives>
- Donini A. (2017). Nuova flessibilità spazio-temporale e tecnologie: L'idea del lavoro agile. In P. Tullini (Ed.), *Web e lavoro: Profili evolutivi e di tutela* (p. 77 f.). Giappichelli.
- Donnelly R. & Johns J. (2020) Recontextualizing work and HRM in the digital economy: A new integrated framework for theory and practice. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(1): 84-105. DOI: 10.1080/09585192.2020.1737834
- Dousay T.A. (2017). Defining and differentiating the makerspace. *Educational Technology*, 57(2): 69–74. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44430528>
- d'Ovidio M., & Cossu A. (2016). Culture is reclaiming the creative city: The case of Macao in Milan – Italy. *City, Culture and Society*, 8: 7–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.ccs.2016.04.001
- Duffy F. (2008). *Work and the City*. London: Black Dog Publishing.
- Elsbach K.D., & Bechky B.A. (2007). It's More Than a Desk: Working Smarter through Leveraged Office Design. *California Management Review*, 49(2): 80–101. DOI: 10.2307/41166384
- Endrissat N., & Leclercq-Vandelannoitte A. (2021). From sites to vibes: Technology and the spatial production of coworking spaces. *Information and Organization*, 31(4): 100353. DOI: 10.1016/j.infoandorg.2021.100353
- Engstler M., & Mörgenthaler L. (2018). *Kreativwirtschaft im Ländlichen Raum: Kommunikationskonzept und Förderansätze: Situation und Potenziale von Coworking zur Förderung*

der Kreativwirtschaft im Ländlichen Raum in Baden-Württemberg [Creative Industries in Rural Areas: Communication Concept and Funding Approaches. Situation and Potentials of Coworking for the Promotion of the Creative Industries in Rural Areas in Baden-Wuerttemberg]. ISBN: 978-3-945495-32-2

Errichiello L., & Pianese T. (2019). Toward a theory on workplaces for smart workers. *Facilities*, 38(3/4): 298–315. DOI: 10.1108/F-11-2018-0137

Eurofound. (2022). *Working conditions in the time of COVID-19: Implications for the future, European working conditions telephone survey 2021 series*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

Fai F.M., Tomlinson P.R., & Barzotto M. (2024). Coworking spaces and regional development: A role for policy. *Regional Studies*, 1-16. DOI: 10.1080/00343404.2024.2399282

Fast K. (2021). The disconnection turn: Three facets of disconnective work in post-digital capitalism. *Convergence*, 27(6): 1615-1630. DOI: 10.1177/13548565211033382

Fast K. (2024). Who has the right to the coworking space? Reframing platformed workspaces as elite territory in the geomeia city. *Space and Culture*, 27(1): 48-62. DOI: 10.1177/12063312221090429

Fast K., & Jansson A. (2019). *Transmedia work: Privilege and precariousness in digital modernity*. London: Routledge

Fast K., & Jansson A. (2023). The post-digital self: How transmedia dissolves the boundaries of work and tourism. In M. Freeman, & J. Dalby (Eds.), *Transmedia Selves*. London: Routledge.

Fast K., & Jansson A. (2024). Working in the comfort zone: Understanding coworking spaces as

post-digital, post-work and post-tourist territory. *Digital Geography*, 7, 100103. DOI: 10.1016/j.diggeo.2024.100103

Fast K., Lindell J., & Jansson A. (2021). Disconnection as distinction. In A. Jansson, & P. C. Adams (Eds.), *Disentangling: The geographies of digital disconnection*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Feifer M. (1985). *Going places. The ways of the tourist from Imperial Rome to the present day*. London: MacMillan.

Feld S.L. (1981). The focused organization of social ties. *The American Journal of Sociology*, 86 (5): 1015–1035.

Felstead A., Jewson N., & Walters S. (2005). *Changing Places of Work*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Ferreira J.J., Fernandes C., Raposo M., Thurik R., & Faria J. (2015). Entrepreneur location decisions

across industries. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 12: 985–1006. DOI: 10.1007/s11365-015-0370-7

Fiorentino S. (2018). Re-making urban economic geography. Startups, entrepreneurial support and the makers movement: A critical assessment of policy mobility in Rome. *Geoforum; Journal of*

Physical, Human, and Regional Geosciences, 93: 116–119. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoforum.2018.05.016

Fiorentino S. (2019). Different typologies of 'co-working spaces' and the contemporary dynamics of local economic development in Rome. *European Planning Studies*, 27(9): 1768–1790. DOI: 10.1080/09654313.2019.1620697

- Foertsch C. (2021). Coworking forecast: The 'next normal' outlook. Deskmag.com (January 05, 2021). Retrieved October 31, 2025 from <https://www.deskmag.com/en/coworking-city-country-profiles/2021-coworking-forecast-the-next-normal-scenario-outlook>
- Formica P. (2016). The innovative coworking spaces of 15th-century Italy. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved October 31, 2025 from <https://hbr.org/2016/04/the-innovative-coworking-spaces-of-15th-century-italy>
- Fu Y., Li Y., & Li X. (2023). Coexisting or Coworking? The Reconfigured Office Spaces in Two Emerging Global Cities. *Journal of Urban Affairs*, 47(5): 1691–1708. DOI: 10.1080/07352166.2023.2242531
- Fuzi A. (2015). Co-working spaces for promoting entrepreneurship in sparse regions: The case of South Wales. *Regional Studies, Regional Science*, 2(1): 462–469. DOI: 10.1080/21681376.2015.1072053
- Gandini A. (2015). The rise of coworking spaces: A literature review. *Ephemera: Theory and Politics in Organizations*, 15(1): 193-205.
- Gandini A. (2019). Labour process theory and the gig economy. *Human Relations*, 72(6): 1039–1056. DOI: 10.1177/0018726718790002
- Gandini A., & Cossu A. (2019). The third wave of coworking: “Neo-corporate model” versus resilient practice. *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, 24(2): 430–447. DOI: 10.1177/1367549419886060
- Garrett L.E., Spreitzer G.M., & Bacevice P.A. (2017). Co-constructing a sense of community at work: The emergence of community in coworking spaces. *Organization Studies*, 38(6): 821–842. DOI: 10.1177/0170840616685354
- Gartner. (2025). *Gartner Identifies the Top Trends Shaping the Future of Cloud*. Retrieved from <https://www.gartner.com/en/newsroom/press-releases/2025-05-13-gartner-identifies-top-trends-shaping-the-future-of-cloud>. Accessed on October 1, 2025.
- Gensler (2016). *U.S. Workplace Survey 2016* (Report). San Francisco: Gensler.
- Gerosa A. (2024). *The hipster economy: Taste and authenticity in late modern capitalism*. UCL Press.
- Goffman E. (1963). *Behavior in Public Places*. Free Press.
- Goodin T. (2017). *Off: Your digital detox for a better life*. Lewes: Ilex.
- Grabher G., Melchior A., Schiemer B., Schüßler E., & Sydow J. (2018). From being there to being aware: Confronting geographical and sociological imaginations of copresence. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 50(1): 245–255. DOI: 10.1177/0308518X17743507
- Granstrand O., & Holgersson M. (2020). Innovation ecosystems: A conceptual review and a new definition. *Technovation*, 90-91: 102098. DOI: 10.1016/j.technovation.2019.102098
- Grazian D. (2020). Thank god it's Monday: Manhattan coworking spaces in the new economy. *Theory and Society*, 49(5/6): 991–1019. DOI: 10.1007/s11186-019-09360-6
- Greenberg J., & Mollick E. (2017). Activist choice homophily and the crowdfunding of female founders. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 62(2): 341–374. DOI: 10.1177/0001839216678847
- Gregg M. (2011). *Work's Intimacy*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Gregg M. (2018). From careers to atmospheres. In S. Schaefer, M. Andersson, E. Bjarnason, et al.

- (Eds.), *Working and Organizing in the Digital Age* (pp. 83–94), Lund: The Pufendorf Institute for Advanced Studies, Lund University Press.
- Grote G., & Guest D. (2017). The case for reinvigorating quality of working life research. *Human Relations*, 70(2): 149–167. DOI: 10.1177/0018726716654746
- Halford S. (2005). Hybrid workspace: re-spatialisations of work, organisation and management. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 20(1): 13–33. DOI: 10.1111/j.1468-005X.2005.00141.x
- Hallen B., Davis J., & Murray A. (2020). Entrepreneurial network evolution: Explicating the structural localism and agentic network change distinction. *Academy of Management Annals*, 14(2): 1067–1102. DOI: 10.5465/annals.2018.0063
- Halvitigala D., Antoniadou H., & Eves C. (2018, July). CoWorking culture—challenges and opportunities for office landlords. In *Pacific Rim Real Estate Society Conference*. Auckland: PRRES Inc.
- Hamari J., Sjöklint M., & Ukkonen A. (2016). The sharing economy: Why people participate in collaborative consumption. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(9): 2047–2059. DOI: 10.1002/asi.23552
- Hampel C., Tracey P., & Weber K. (2020). The art of the pivot: How new ventures manage identification relationships with stakeholders as they change direction. *Academy of Management Journal*, 63(2): 440–471. DOI: 10.5465/amj.2017.0460
- Haner U.E. (2005). Spaces for creativity and innovation in two established organisations. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 14(3): 288–298. DOI: 10.1111/j.1476-8691.2005.00347.x
- Hartmann M. (2016). Coworking oder auch die (De-) Mediatisierung von Arbeit. In *Medien-Arbeit im Wandel* (pp. 177–204). Wiesbaden: Springer VS.
- Hartog L.M., Weijts-Perrée M., & Appel-Meulenbroek H.A.J.A. (2018). The influence of personality on user satisfaction: Multi-tenant offices. *Building Research and Information*, 46(4): 402–416. DOI: 10.1080/09613218.2017.1307015
- Haslam S.A., & Knight C. (2010). The relative merits of lean, enriched and empowered offices: An experimental examination of the impact of workplace management strategies on well-being and productivity. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 16(2): 158–172. DOI: 10.1037/a0019292
- Heinzel V., Georgiades S., & Engstler M. (2021). Corporate coworking – A catalyst for collaboration, creativity, and innovation. In M. Orel, O. Dvouletý, & V. Ratten (Eds.), *The flexible workplace: Coworking and Other Modern Workplace Transformations* (pp. 81–96). Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-62167-4_5
- Herrera J., De las Heras-Rosas C., Rodríguez-Fernández M., & Ciruela-Lorenzo A.M. (2022). Teleworking: The link between worker, family and company. *Systems*, 10(5): 134. DOI: 10.3390/systems10050134
- Hesselberth P. (2018). Discourses on disconnectivity and the right to disconnect. *New Media & Society*, 20(5): 1994–2010. DOI: 10.1177/1461444817711449

- Hirst A. (2011). Settlers, vagrants and mutual indifference: unintended consequences of hot-desking. *Journal of Organisational Change Management*, 24(6): 767–788. DOI: 10.1108/09534811111175742
- Hislop D. & Axtell C. (2007). The neglect of spatial mobility in contemporary studies of work: The case of telework. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 22(1): 34–51. DOI: 10.1111/j.1468-005X.2007.00182.x
- Hislop D., & Axtell C. (2009). To infinity and beyond? Workspace and the multi-location worker. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 24(1): 60–75. DOI: 10.1111/j.1468-005X.2008.00218.x
- Hölzel M., Kolsch K.H., & de Vries W. (2022). Location of Coworking Spaces (CWSs) Regarding Vicinity, Land Use and Points of Interest (POIs). *Land*, 11 (3): 354. DOI: 10.3390/land11030354
- Hossain M., & Sarkar S. (2023). Frugal Entrepreneurship: Profiting With Inclusive Growth. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 70(11): 3812–3825. DOI: 10.1109/TEM.2021.3088589
- Houghton K.R., Foth M., & Hearn G. (2018). Working from the other office: Trialling co-working spaces for public servants. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 77 (4): 757–778. DOI: 10.1111/1467-8500.12317
- Howell T. (2022). Coworking spaces: An overview and research agenda. *Research Policy*, 51(2): 104447. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2021.104447
- Huang H., Liu Y., Liang Y., Vargas D., & Zhang L. (2020). Spatial Perspectives on Coworking Spaces and Related Practices in Beijing. *Built Environment*, 46 (1): 40–45. DOI: 10.2148/benv.46.1.40
- Hughes C., & Jackson C. (2015). Death of the high street: Identification, prevention, reinvention. *Regional Studies, Regional Science*, 2(1): 237–256. DOI: 10.1080/21681376.2015.1016098
- Humayun M., & Belk R. (2020). The analogue diaries of postdigital consumption. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 36(7–8): 633–659. DOI: 10.1080/0267257X.2020.1724178
- IEEE Spectrum. (2023). *The Path Towards Digitalization and the Future*. Retrieved from <https://spectrum.ieee.org/siemens-digitalization>. Accessed on October 1, 2025.
- ILO. (2020). Defining and measuring remote work, telework, work at home and home-based work. *ILO policy brief* [online]. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/sites/default/files/wcmsp5/groups/public/%40dgreports/%40stat/documents/publication/wcms_747075.pdf
- International Workplace Group (IWG). (2022). *The Future of Work*. Retrieved from <https://work.iwgplc.com/assets/docs/The-Future-of-Work.pdf>. Accessed on October 1, 2025.
- Ivaldi S., Pais I., & Scaratti G. (2018). Coworking(s) in the Plural: Coworking Spaces and New Ways of Managing. In S. Taylor, S. Luckman S. (Eds.), *The New Normal of Working Lives. Dynamics of Virtual Work*, Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-66038-7_11
- Jalili P. (2021). Office aesthetics: Narratives around contemporary labor through representations of office spaces. *The Journal of Kitsch, Camp and Mass Culture*, 1: 106–119.
- Johns J., Yates E., Charnock G., Pitts F.H., Bozkurt Ö., & Ozdemir Kaya D.D. (2024). Coworking Spaces and Workplaces of the Future: Critical Perspectives on Community, Context and Change. *European Management Review*. DOI: 10.1111/emre.12654
- Johnson L.C. (2003). From hybrid housing to cybrid neighborhoods: Case studies of five decentralized tele-workspaces. *Journal of Architectural and Planning Research*, 20(2): 136–152.

- Jones D., Sundsted T., & Bacigalupo T. (2009). *I'm outta here! How coworking is making the office obsolete.*
- Josef B., & Back A. (2018). Coworking as a new innovation scenario from the perspective of mature organisations. In *International OFEL conference on governance, management and entrepreneurship* (pp. 491–507). Zagreb: Centar za istraživanje i razvoj upravljanja doo.
- Kabo F., Hwang Y., Levenstein M., & Owen-Smith J. (2015). Shared paths to the lab: A sociospatial network analysis of collaboration. *Environment and Behaviour*, 47(1): 57–84. DOI: 10.1177/0013916513493909
- Kaplan R., & Kaplan S. (1989). *The Experience of Nature: A Psychological Perspective*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (MA).
- Kellerman A. (2009). The end of spatial reorganization? Urban landscapes of personal mobilities in the information age. *Journal of Urban Technology*, 16(1): 47–61. DOI: 10.1080/10630730903076510
- Kellert S.R., Heerwagen J., & Mador M. (Eds.) (2008). *Biophilic Design: The Theory, Science, and Practice of Bringing Buildings to Life*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken (NJ).
- Kera D. (2012). Hackerspaces and DIYbio in Asia: Connecting science and community with open data, kits and protocols. *Journal of Peer Production*, 2(June): 1–8.
- Khanna R., Guler I., & Nerkar A. (2016). Fail often, fail big, and fail fast? Learning from small failures and R&D performance in the pharmaceutical industry. *Academy of Management Journal*, 59(2): 436–459. DOI: 10.5465/amj.2013.1109
- Khanna C., van der Voordt T.J.M., & Koppels P. (2013). Corporate real estate mirrors brand: A conceptual framework and practical applications. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 15 (3/4): 213–230. DOI:
- King S. (2017). Coworking is not about workspace: It's about feeling less lonely. *Harvard Business Review*, Dec 28, 2017.
- Knapp M.T., & Sawy A. (2021). Coworking spaces in small cities and rural areas: A qualitative study from an operator and user perspective. In M. Orel, O. Dvoutely, & V. Ratten (Eds.), *The Flexible Workplace. Human Resource Management*. Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-62167-4_7
- Kojo I. & Nenonen S. (2016) Typologies for co-working spaces in Finland – what and how? *Facilities*, 34(5/6): 302–313. DOI: 10.1108/F-08-2014-0066
- Krause I. (2019). Coworking spaces: Windows to the future of work? Changes in the organizational model of work and the attitudes of the younger generation. *Foresight and STI Governance*, 13(2): 52–60. DOI: 10.17323/2500-2597.2019.2.52.60
- Kraus S., Bouncken R.B., Gormar L., Gonzalez-Serrano M.H., & Calabuig F. (2022). Coworking spaces and makerspaces: Mapping the state of research. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(1): 100161. DOI: 10.1016/j.jik.2022.100161
- Krauss G. (2019). Les espaces de coworking et les trajectoires sociales de leurs fondateurs et utilisateurs: Études de cas dans le sud-ouest de l'Allemagne dans une ville moyenne et dans une petite commune périphérique. In G. Krauss, & D.-G. Tremblay (Eds.), *Tiers-lieux. Travailler et entreprendre sur les territoires: Espaces de coworking, fablabs, hacklabs...* (pp. 19–40). Presses universitaires de Rennes.

- Kurland N.B., & Cooper C.D. (2002). Manager control and employee isolation in telecommuting environments. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 13(1): 107–126. DOI: 10.1016/S1047-8310(01)00051-7
- Lan J., & Feng T. (2025). Role of remote working center in a hybrid work culture. *Cities*, 159: 105754. DOI: 10.1016/j.cities.2025.105754
- Leclercq-Vandelannoitte A. (2021). Do coworking spaces promise a revolution or spark revenge? A Foucauldian spatio-material approach to the re-spatialization of remote work in coworking spaces. In N. Mitev, J. Aroles, K. A. Stephenson, & J. Malaurent (Eds.), *New Ways of Working: Organizations and Organizing in the Digital Age* (p. 151-174). Palgrave Macmillan. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-61687-8_7
- Leclercq-Vandelannoitte A., & Isaac H. (2016). The new office: How coworking changes the work concept. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 37(6): 3-9. DOI: 10.1108/JBS-10-2015-0105
- Leducq D. (2021). Les espaces de coworking: Des instruments de résilience territoriale pour l'après-Covid? *Netcom*, 35(1/2). DOI: 10.4000/netcom.5677
- Lefosse D., Van Timmeren A., & Ratti C. (2023). Biophilia upscaling: A Systematic literature review based on a three-metric approach. *Sustainability*, 15: 15702. DOI: 10.3390/su152215702
- le Loarne S., Razgallah M., Maalaoui A., & Kraus S. (2022). Becoming a green entrepreneur: An advanced entrepreneurial cognition model based on a practiced-based approach. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 18(2): 801–828. DOI: 10.1007/s11365-021-00791-1
- Le Nadant A.L., Marinos C., & Krauss G. (2018). Les espaces de coworking : Le rôle des proximités dans les dynamiques collaboratives. *Revue française de gestion*, 272(3): 121–137. DOI: 10.3166/rfg.2018.00233
- Lescarret C., Lemercier C., & Le Floch V. (2022). Coworking spaces vs. home: Does employees' experience of the negative aspects of working from home predict their intention to telework in a coworking space? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. DOI: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1079691
- Li Y., Zhang X., Lu F., Zhang Q., & Wang Y. (2014). Internet addiction among elementary and middle school students in China: A nationally representative sample study. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior and Social Networking*, 17(2): 111–116. DOI: 10.1089/cyber.2012.0482
- Liff S., & Lægran A.S. (2003). Cybercafés: Debating the meaning and significance of Internet access in a café environment. *New Media & Society*, 5(3): 307–312. DOI: 10.1177/14614448030053001
- Lin C.Y. (2021). State Strategy in the Trans-Local Branding of a Creative Industry Cluster: A Case Study of the Product Design Industry in Taipei. *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie*, 112(3): 274–287. DOI: 10.1111/tesg.12463
- Lindtner S., Hertz G.D., & Dourish P. (2014). Emerging sites of HCI innovation: Hackerspaces, hardware startups & incubators. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 439–448). New York, NY: ACM.
- Lomborg S., & Ytre-Arne B. (2021). Advancing digital disconnection research: Introduction to the special issue. *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 27(6): 1529–1535. DOI: 10.1177/13548565211057518

- Lorne C. (2020). The limits to openness: Co-working, design and social innovation in the neoliberal city. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 52(4): 747–765. DOI: 10.1177/0308518X19876941
- Lunau T., Bambra C., Eikemo T.A., van der Wel K.A., & Dragano N. (2014). A balancing act? Work–life balance, health and well-being in European welfare states. *The European Journal of Public Health*, 24(3): 422–427. DOI: 10.1093/eurpub/cku010
- Manzini-Ceinar I.M., & Mariotti I. (2021). The Effects of Covid-19 on Coworking Spaces: Patterns and Future Trends. In I. Mariotti, S. Di Vita, & M. Akhavan (Eds.), *New Workplaces – Location Patterns, Urban Effects and Development Trajectories: A Worldwide Investigation* (pp. 277–297). Springer International Publishing, Cham.
- Marchegiani L., & Arcese G. (2018). Collaborative spaces and coworking as hybrid workspaces: Friends or foes of learning and innovation? In P. Boccardelli, M.C. Annosi, F. Brunetta, & M. Magnusson (Eds.), *Learning and innovation in hybrid organizations* (pp. 51-71), Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-62467-9_4
- Mariotti I., Akhavan M., & Di Matteo D. (2021). The geography of coworking spaces and the effects on the urban context; are pole areas gaining? In I. Mariotti, S. Di Vita, & M. Akhavan (Eds.), *New workplaces – Location patterns, urban effects and development trajectories. A worldwide investigation* (pp. 169–194). Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-63443-8
- Mariotti I., Tomas E., Micek G., & Mendez-Ortega C. (Eds.). (2024). *Evolution of new working spaces: Changing nature and geographies*. Routledge
- Mariotti I., Akhavan M., & Rossi F. (2023). The preferred location of coworking spaces in Italy: An empirical investigation in urban and peripheral areas. *European Planning Studies*, 31(3): 467–489. DOI: 10.1080/09654313.2021.1895080
- Marlow O. (2011), Designing a successful coworking space. Retrieved October 31, 2025 from <https://www.deskmag.com/en/coworking-tools-tips/designing-a-successful-coworking-space-183>
- Mayerhoffer M. (2020) Growth factors of the coworking industry: The case of Prague. *Journal of Property Investment & Finance*, 38(3): 203–212. DOI: 10.1108/JPIF-12-2019-0164
- Mayerhoffer M. (2021). The Impact of Covid-19 on Coworking Spaces: Evidence from Germany. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 23(3): 170–185. DOI: 10.1108/JCRE-10-2020-0044
- Mazmanian M., Orlikowski W. J., & Yates J. (2013). The autonomy paradox: The implications of mobile email devices for knowledge professionals. *Organization Science*, 24(5): 1337-1357. DOI: 10.1287/orsc.1120.0806
- McWilliams D. (2015). *The Flat White Economy: How The Digital Economy is Transforming London and Other Cities of the Future*. Overlook Press.
- Mendez-Ortega C., Micek G., & Malochleb K. (2022). How do Coworking Spaces Coagglomerate with Service Industries? The Tale of Three European Cities. *Cities*, 130: 1–14. DOI: 10.1016/j.cities.2022.103875.
- Merkel J. (2015). Coworking in the city. *Ephemera: Theory & Politics in Organization*, 15(2): 121–139.
- Merkel J. (2019). 'Freelance isn't free.' Co-working as a critical urban practice to cope with informality in creative labor markets. *Urban Studies*, 56(3): 526–547. DOI: 10.1177/0042098018782374

- Merrell I., Füzi A., Russell E., & Bosworth G. (2021). How rural coworking hubs can facilitate well-being through the satisfaction of key psychological needs. *Local Economy: The Journal of the Local Economy Policy Unit*, 36(7-8): 606–626. DOI: 10.1177/02690942221075598
- Messenger J.C., & Gschwind L. (2016). Three generations of telework: New ICTs and the (r)evolution from home office to virtual office. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 31(3): 195–208. DOI: 10.1111/ntwe.12073
- Meunier J. (2018). After more than a decade, 'co-working' is now officially 'coworking'. Retrieved 26/10/2025 at <https://allwork.space/2018/10/after-more-than-a-decade-co-working-is-now-officiallycoworking/>
- Micek G., Baycan T., & Lange B. (2024). A taxonomy of new working spaces. In I. Mariotti, et al. (Eds.), *Evolution of new working spaces: Changing nature and geographies* (pp. 21–34), Routledge.
- Migliore A., Ceinar I.M., & Tagliaro C. (2021). Beyond Coworking: From Flexible to Hybrid Spaces. In M. Orel, O. Dvouletý, & V. Ratten (Eds.), *The Flexible Workplace. Human Resource Management*. Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-62167-4_1
- Mitev N., de Vaujany F.-X., Laniray P., Bohas A., & Fabbri J. (2019). Co-working Spaces, Collaborative Practices and Entrepreneurship. In K. Riemer, S. Schellhammer, & M. Meinert (Eds.), *Collaboration in the Digital Age* (pp. 15-43). DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-94487-6_2
- Moriset B. (2014). Building new places of the creative economy. The rise of coworking spaces. Paper presented at the 2nd Geography of Innovation International Conference 2014, Utrecht.
- Morisson A. (2018). A typology of places in the knowledge economy: Towards the fourth place. In *International symposium on new metropolitan perspectives* (pp. 444-451). Cham: Springer.
- Nakano D., Shlach M., Koria M., Vasques R., dos Santos E.G., & Virani T. (2020). Coworking spaces in urban settings: Prospective roles? *Geoforum*, 115: 135–137. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoforum.2020.04.014
- Neuberg B. (2005, August 9). *Coworking—Community for Developers Who Work From Home*. Retrieved October 30, 2025 from <http://codinginparadise.org/weblog/2005/08/coworking-community-for-developers-who.html>
- Newport C. (2016). *Deep work: Rules for focused success in a distracted world*. Hachette UK.
- Newport C. (2019). *Digital minimalism: On living better with less technology*. London: Penguin.
- Nieuwenhuis M., Knight C., Postmes T., & Haslam S.A. (2014). The relative benefits of green versus lean office space: Three field experiments. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied*, 20(3): 199–214. DOI: 10.1037/xap0000024
- Nurdin D.A., Firmansah D., Hafifi A., & Darwis M. (2024). Smart-Working and Hot Desking Application Development using Agile and Extreme Programming Method at Xtra Cowork. *JISA (Jurnal Informatika dan Sains)*, 7(2): 140–147.
- O'Brien S.A. (2019). WeWork isn't just selling desk space. It's selling a new way of life. CNN Business. Retrieved 10/26/2025 at: <https://edition.cnn.com/2019/05/03/tech/wework-culture/index.html>
- OECD. (2021). *Measuring Telework in the COVID-19 Pandemic*. Report, OECD Digital

- Economy Papers, 314. DOI: 10.1787/0a76109f-en
- Oldenburg R. (1999). *The great good place*. Berkshire.
- O'Leary M.B., Wilson J.M., & Metiu A. (2014). Beyond being there: The symbolic role of communication and identification in perceptions of proximity to geographically dispersed colleagues. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(4): 1219–1244. DOI: 10.25300/MISQ/2014/38.4.13
- Orel M. (2015). Working in co working spaces: The social and economic engagement of European youth. In Youth Partnership (Ed.), *Perspectives on youth, Vol. 2: Connections and disconnection* (pp. 133–139). Strasbourg: Council of Europe Publ.
- Orel M. (2021). Life is better in flip flops. Digital nomads and their transformational travels to Thailand. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 15(1): 3–9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCTHR-12-2019-0229>
- Orel M., & Bennis W.M. (2021). Classifying changes. A taxonomy of contemporary coworking spaces. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 23(4): 278-296. DOI: 10.1108/JCRE-12-2020-0061
- Orel M., & Dvouletý O. (2020). Transformative changes and developments of the Coworking Model: A narrative review. In: V. Ratten (eds), *Technological progress, inequality and entrepreneurship: Studies on entrepreneurship, structural change and industrial dynamics* (pp. 9–27), Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-26245-7_2
- Orlikowski W.J. (2007). Sociomaterial practices: Exploring technology at work. *Organization Studies*, 28(9): 1435–1448. DOI: 10.1177/ 0170840607081138
- Pajevic F., & Shearmur R. (2020). Where Are the Knowledge Workers? The Case of Silicon Valley North in Ontario, Canada. In I. Mariotti, S. Di Vita, & M. Akhavan (Eds.), *Location Patterns, Urban Effects and Development Trajectories* (pp. 233–250). Springer, Cham.
- Pan J., Cho T.Y., Sun M., Debnath R., Lonsdale N., Wilcox C., & Bardhan R. (2023). Future workspace needs flexibility and diversity: A machine learning-driven behavioural analysis of co-working space. *PLoS ONE*, 18(10): e0292370. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0292370
- Pan J., Cho T.Y., Sun M., Steemers K., & Bardhan R. (2025). Environmental and spatial dynamics in a flexible workspace for hybrid work: A data-driven design framework. *Building and Environment*, 270: 112544. DOI: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2025.112544
- Parrino L. (2015). Coworking: Assessing the role of proximity in knowledge exchange. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, 13(3): 261–271. DOI: 10.1057/kmrp.2013.47
- Pazzaglia F., & Tizi L. (2022). *Che cos'è il restorative design*. Roma: Carocci.
- Petriglieri G., Ashford S.J., & Wrzesniewski A. (2019). Agony and ecstasy in the gig economy: Cultivating holding environments for precarious and personalized work identities. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 64(1): 124–170. DOI: 10.1177/0001839218759646
- Pfeffer C. (2024). Hybrid Copresence: Issues of Re-Spatialization of Remote Work in Coworking Spaces. *M@n@gement*, 27(4): 58–80. DOI: 10.37725/mgmt.2024.8054
- Privett I. (2020). *Experience Unbound: The Effects of Coworking on Workplace Design Practice*. Phd thesis, Royal College of Art, London (UK).
- Prochazka V., & Wingartz N. (2019). *Innovation und Digitalisierung in den Kommunen und Landkreisen Baden-Württembergs: Status Quo, Herausforderungen, Bedarfe, Handlungsempfehlungen*. Fraunhofer-Institut für Arbeitswirtschaft und Organisation IAO Universität Stuttgart. DOI: 10.24406/publica-fhg-299783
- Purser R.E. (2018). Critical perspectives on corporate mindfulness. *Journal of Management, Spirituality & Religion*, 15(2): 105–108. DOI: 10.1080/14766086.2018.1438038
- Putra G.B., & Agirachman F.A. (2016). Urban coworking space: Creative tourism in digital

- nomads perspective. In *Proceedings of Arte-Polis 6 international conference* (pp. 169–178).
- Rallet A., & Torre A. (2004). Proximité et localisation. *Économie rurale*, 280(1): 25–41. DOI: 10.3406/ecoru.2004.5470
- Raphael R. (2017). *WeWork for chefs: How one coworking incubator fuels food innovation*. Retrieved 26/10/2025 at: <https://www.fastcompany.com/40457426/wework-for-chefs-how-one-co-working-incubator-fuels-food-innovation>
- Rauch J. (2018). *Slow media: Why 'slow' is satisfying, sustainable and smart*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Remøy H., & Van der Voordt T. (2013). *Adaptability – How to accommodate changing user preferences*. Paper presented at European Real Estate Society Conference, Vienna, Austria.
- Resch B., Hoyer, P., & Steyaert C. (2021). Affective Control in New Collaborative Work: Communal Fantasies of Purpose, Growth and Belonging. *Organization Studies*, 42(5), 787–809. DOI: 10.1177/0170840620941616
- Reuschke D., Clifton N., & Fisher M. (2021). Coworking in homes – Mitigating the tensions of the freelance economy. *Geoforum*, 119: 122–132. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoforum.2021.01.005
- Richardson L. (2021) Coordinating office space: digital technologies and the platformization of work. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 39(2): 347–365. DOI: 10.1177/0263775820959677
- Ross P., & Ressa S. (2015). Neither office nor home: Coworking as an emerging workplace choice. *Employment Relations Record*, 15(1): 42–57. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/143905270>
- Rothe P., Lindholm A., Hyvönen A., & Nenonen S. (2011). User preferences of office occupiers: Investigating the differences. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 13(2): 81–97. DOI: 10.1108/14630011111136803
- Rozentale I., & Lavanga M. (2014). The 'Universal' Characteristics of Creative Industries Revisited: The Case of Riga. *City, Culture and Society*, 5(2): 55–64. DOI: 10.1016/j.ccs.2014.05.006
- Rus A., & Orel M. (2015). Coworking: A community of work. *Teorija in Praksa*, 52(6): 1017–1038.
- Saiz A. (2020). Bricks, mortar, and proptech: The economics of IT in brokerage, space utilization and commercial real estate finance. *Journal of Property Investment & Finance*, 38(4): 327–347. DOI: 10.1108/JPIF-10-2019-0139
- Salento A. (2018). Digitalisation and the regulation of work: Theoretical issues and normative challenges, *AI & Society*, 33(1), 369 ff. DOI:10.1007/s00146-017-0738-z
- Salovaara P. (2015). What can the coworking movement tell us about the future of workplaces. In A. Ropo, P. Salovaara, E. Sauer, & D. De Paoli (Eds.), *Leadership in spaces and places* (pp. 27–48). Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar. DOI: 10.4337/9781783477920.00008
- Salvador T., Sherry J.W., & Urrutia A. E. (2005). Less cyber, more café: Enhancing existing small businesses across the digital divide with ICTs. *Information Technology for Development*, 11(1): 77–95. DOI: 10.1002/itdj.20004
- Sandoval M. (2018). From passionate labour to compassionate work: Cultural co-ops, do what you love and social change. *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, 21(2): 113–129. DOI: 10.1177/1367549417719011
- Sargent K., Cooper J., Mellwig B., & McDonald M. (2018). Coworking and the disruption of the current corporate real estate model. *Corporate Real Estate Journal*, 7(3): 267–276. DOI: 10.69554/JMKX4413

- Saxenian A. (2014). The Silicon Valley model: Economic dynamism, social exclusion. In M. Castells, & P. Himanen (Eds.), *Reconceptualizing Development in the Global Information Age* (pp. 28–51). Oxford Academic. DOI: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198716082.003.0003
- Scaillerez A., & Tremblay D.-G. (2019). Travailler et collaborer autrement: Les espaces de coworking, une approche apparentée aux communautés de pratique. In G. Krauss, & D.-G. Tremblay (Eds.), *Tiers-lieux. Travailler et entreprendre sur les territoires: Espaces de coworking, fablabs, hacklabs...* (p. 143–156). Presses universitaires de Rennes.
- Schopf J., Roche J., & Hubert G. (2015). Co-working and innovation: New concepts for academic libraries and learning centres. *New Library World*, 116(1/2): 67–78. DOI: 10.1108/NLW-06-2014-0072
- Seo J., Lysiankova L., Ock Y.S., & Chun D. (2017). Priorities of coworking space operation based on comparison of the hosts and users' perspectives. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 9(8): 1494. DOI: 10.3390/su9081494
- Sewell G., & Taskin L. (2015). Out of sight, out of mind in a new world of work? Autonomy, control, and spatiotemporal scaling in telework. *Organization Studies*, 36(11): 1507–1529. DOI: 10.1177/0170840615593587
- Shalley C.E. (1995). Effects of coaction, expected evaluation, and goal setting on creativity and productivity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 38(2): 483–503. DOI: 10.5465/256689
- Shearmur R., & Alvergne C., 2002. Intrametropolitan Patterns of High-order Business Service Location: A Comparative Study of Seventeen Sectors in Ile-de-France. *Urban Studies*, 39(7): 1143–1163. DOI: 10.1080/00420980220135536
- Shepard J.M. (2018). Understanding co-working with the growth and development of freelancers. *Management and Organizational Studies*, 5(2): 1. DOI: 10.5430/mos.v5n2p1
- Skogland M.A.C., & Hansen G.K. (2017). Change your space, change your culture: Exploring spatial change management strategies. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 19(2): 95–110. DOI: 10.1108/JCRE-07-2016-0024
- Sobyra R., Sigler T., & Charles-Edwards E. (2022). Unbalanced growth in the labourscape: Explaining regional employment divergence. *Regional Studies*, 56(7): 1059–1070. DOI: 10.1080/00343404.2021.1972958
- Spinelli C. (2018). *Tecnologie digitali e lavoro agile*. Bari: Cacucci.
- Spinuzzi C. (2012). Working alone together: Co-working as emergent collaborative activity. *Journal of Business and Technical Communication*, 26 (4): 399–441. DOI: 10.1177/1050651912444070
- Spinuzzi C. (2015). *All edge: Inside the new workplace networks*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Spreitzer G., Bacevice P., Garrett L. (2015a). Why people thrive in coworking spaces. *Harvard Business Review*, 93 (9), 28–30.
- Spreitzer G., Garrett L., & Bacevice P. (2015b). Should your company embrace coworking? *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 57(1): 27–29.

- Spreitzer G., Bacevice P., & Garrett L. (2017). Coworking communities as enablers of thriving at work. In C.L. Cooper, & M.P. Leiter (Eds.), *The Routledge Companion to Wellbeing at Work* (pp. 197–207). London: Routledge.
- Staats H. (2012). *Restorative Environments*. In S. Clayton (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Environmental and Conservation Psychology*, New York, Oxford University Press, pp. 445–58.
- Stam W. (2010). Industry event participation and network brokerage among entrepreneurial ventures. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(4): 625–653. DOI: 10.1111/j.1467-6486.2009.00909.x
- Stam E., & van de Vrande V. (2017). Solopreneurs and the Rise of Co-working in the Netherlands. In M. van Ham, D. Reuschke, R. Kleinhaus, C. Mason, & S. Syrett (Eds.), *Entrepreneurial Neighbourhoods* (pp. 65–79). Edward Elgar Publishing, *Towards an Understanding of the Economies of Neighbourhoods and Communities*. DOI: 10.4337/9781785367243.00012
- Sullivan J. (2017). Considering employee needs during a catastrophe requires innovative recovery plans: Why traditional workplace recovery solutions are outdated. *Journal of Business Continuity & Emergency Planning*, 10(3): 259–267. DOI: 10.69554/VAJV9518
- Surman T. (2013). Building social entrepreneurship through the power of coworking. *Innovations: Technology, Governance, Globalization*, 8(3–4): 189–195. DOI: 10.1162/INOV_a_00195
- Syvertsen T. (2017). *Media resistance: Protest, dislike*. Abstention: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Tæihagh A. (2017). Crowdsourcing, sharing economies and development. *Journal of Developing Societies*, 33(2): 191–222. DOI: 10.1177/0169796X1771100
- Taskin L. (2006). Télétravail: Les enjeux de la déspatialisation pour le management humain. *Interventions économiques*, 34: 1–21. DOI: 10.4000/interventionseconomiques.680
- Taskin L. (2010). La déspatialisation. Enjeu de gestion. *Revue française de gestion*, 202(3): 61–76. <https://www.cairn.info/revue-francaise-de-gestion-2010-3-page-61.htm>
- Thornton N., Engert M., Hein A., & Krcmar H. (2023). Finding new purpose for vacancies in rural areas: A taxonomy of coworking space business models. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 19: 1394–1423. DOI: 10.1007/s11365-023-00867-0
- Thoring K., Mueller R.M., Desmet P., & Badke-Schaub P. (2020). Spatial design factors associated with creative work: A systematic literature review. *Artificial Intelligence for Engineering Design, Analysis and Manufacturing*, 34: 300–314. DOI: 10.1017/S0890060420000232
- Timm-Bottos J., & Reilly R.C. (2015). Learning in third spaces: Community art studio as storefront university classroom. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 55(1-2): 102–114. DOI: 10.1007/s10464-014-9688-5
- Tiraboschi M. (2017). Il lavoro agile tra legge e contrattazione collettiva: La tortuosa via italiana verso la modernizzazione del diritto del lavoro. *Diritto delle Relazioni Industriali*, 335, 921 f.
- Toivonen T. (2016). What is the social innovation community? Conceptualizing an emergent collaborative organization. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 7(1): 49–73. DOI: 10.1080/19420676.2014.997779
- Tomaz E., & Aboutalebi Tabrizi H. (2024). The evolution of non-traditional workplaces: From third places to hybrid places. In I. Mariotti, et al. (Eds.), *Evolution of new working spaces: Changing nature and geographies* (pp. 7-20), Routledge.
- Tomaz E., Moriset B., & Teller J. (2022). Rural Coworking Spaces in the Covid-19 Era: A

- Window of Opportunity? In I Mariotti, M. Di Marino, & P. Bednář (Eds.), *The COVID-19 pandemic and the future of working spaces* (pp. 122-135), Routledge. DOI: 10.4324/9781003181163-12
- Ton D., Arendsen K., de Bruyn M., Severens V., van Hagen M., van Oort N., & Duives D. (2022). Teleworking during COVID-19 in the Netherlands: Understanding behaviour, attitudes, and future intentions of train travellers. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 159: 55–73. DOI: 10.1016/j.tra.2022.03.019
- Tuan Y.F. (1977). *Space and Place: The Perspective of Experience*. University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, MN.
- Ulrich R.S. (1983). Aesthetic and Affective Response to Natural Environment. In I. Altman, & J.F. Wohlwill (Eds.), *Behavior and the Natural Environment: Advances in Theory and Research vol. VI: Human Behavior and Environment* (pp. 85–125). Plenum Press, New York-London.
- Urry J. (2007). *Mobilities*. Cambridge: Polity.
- U.S. Department of Energy. (2021). *Energy and Employment Report*. Retrieved from <https://www.energy.gov/policy/2021-us-energy-and-employment-report>. Accessed on October 1, 2025.
- van Blokland A. B. (2018). *London's hottest coworking spaces have childcare for your kids*. Retrieved 27/10/2025 at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/anettebvanblokland/2018/07/17/londons-hottestcoworking-spaces-have-childcare-for-your-kids/#3e9c04bd7631>
- Veneziani B. (1987). Nuove tecnologie contratto di lavoro: Profili di diritto comparato. *Diritto del Lavoro e delle Relazioni Industriali*, 33, 1–60.
- Vidaillet B., & Bousalham Y. (2020). Coworking spaces as places where economic diversity can be articulated: Towards a theory of syntopia. *Organization*, 27(1): 60–87. DOI: 10.1177/1350508418794003
- Virginia G., & Colin L. (2001). Friction and inertia: Business change, corporate real estate portfolios and the UK office market. *Journal of Real Estate Research*, 22(1-2): 59–80. DOI: 10.1080/10835547.2001.12091055
- Vissa B. (2012). Agency in action: Entrepreneurs' networking style and initiation of economic exchange. *Organization Science*, 23(2): 492–510. DOI: 10.1287/orsc.1100.0567
- Vogl T., & Akhavan M. (2022). A Systematic Literature Review of the Effects of Coworking Spaces on the Socio-Cultural and Economic Conditions in Peripheral and Rural Areas. *Journal of Property Investment & Finance*, 40(5): 465–478. DOI: 10.1108/JPIF-12-2021-0108
- Voll J., Cordes C., & Henkels W.-N. (2021). *Coworking-Kultur im ländlichen und urbanen Raum*. German Coworking Federation. <https://www.coworking-germany.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Expertise-GCF-2021-CW-SatdtLand.pdf>
- Wang B., & Loo B.P. (2017). Hubs of internet entrepreneurs: The emergence of co-working offices in Shanghai, China. *Journal of Urban Technology*, 24(3): 67–84. DOI: 10.1080/10630732.2017.1285124
- Wardner P. (2012). Understanding the Role of "Sense of Place" in Office Location Decisions. 1–13. *18th annual Pacific-Rim Real Estate Society Conference Adelaide, Australia, 15–18 January 2012*.
- Wasserman N. (2012). *The founder's dilemmas: Anticipating and avoiding the pitfalls that can sink a startup*. Princeton University Press.

- Waters-Lynch J., Duff C. (2019). The affective commons of Coworking. *Human Relations*, 74 (3): 383–404. DOI: 10.1177/0018726719894633
- Waters-Lynch J., & Potts J. (2017). The social economy of coworking spaces: A focal point model of coordination. *Review of Social Economy*, 75(4): 417-433. DOI: 10.1080/00346764.2016.1269938
- Waters-Lynch J.M., Potts J., Butcher T., Dodson J., & Hurley J. (2016). *Coworking: A Transdisciplinary Overview*. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.2712217
- Webster J., & Randle K. (Eds.). (2016). *Virtual workers and the global labour market*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. DOI: 10.1057/978-1-137-47919-8
- Weijs-Perrée M., Appel-Meulenbroek H. A.J.A., de Vries B., & Romme A.G.L. (2016). Differences between business center concepts in the Netherlands. *Property Management*, 34(2): 100-119. DOI: 10.1108/PM-04-2015-0015
- Weijs-Perrée M., van de Koeving J., Appel-Meulenbroek R., & Arentze T. (2019). Analysing user preferences for co-working space characteristics. *Building Research & Information*, 47(5): 534-548. DOI: 10.1080/09613218.2018.1463750
- Wijngaarden Y. (2023). 'I like the "buzz", but I also suffer from it': Mitigating interaction and distraction in collective workplaces. *Human Relations*, 76(12): 1881–1903. DOI: 10.1177/00187267221121277
- Wilson J.M., O'Leary M.B., Metiu A., & Jett Q.R. (2008). Perceived proximity in virtual work: Explaining the paradox of far-but-close. *Organization Studies*, 29(7), 979–1002. DOI: 10.1177/0170840607083105
- Wright D. (2018). Match made in heaven: Investment benefits of coworking spaces in historic sacred places. <https://hdl.handle.net/1813/70815>
- Yates E., Charnock G., Pitts F.H., Johns J., & Bozkurt Ö. (2024). From coworking to competing? Business models and strategies of UK coworking spaces beyond the COVID-19 pandemic. *Competition & Change*, 28(1): 123-143. DOI: 10.1177/10245294231197798
- Zaheer S., & Mosakowski E. (1997). The dynamics of the liability of foreignness: A global study of survival in financial services. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(6): 439–463. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3088186>
- Zhang X., Liang H., & Yin Z. (2025). Spaces of collaboration? Geography and functionality of coworking spaces in China. *Applied Geography*, 175: 103507. DOI: 10.1016/j.apgeog.2025.103507
- Zhang S., Moeckel R., Moreno A.T., Shuai B., & Gao J. (2020). A work-life conflict perspective on telework. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 141: 51–68. DOI: 10.1016/j.tra.2020.09.007
- Zhao S. (2003). Toward a taxonomy of copresence. *Presence*, 12(5): 445–455. DOI: 10.1162/105474603322761261
- Zuboff S. (2019). *The age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*. New York: Hachette/PublicAffairs